

NATIONAL CENTRAL UNIVERSITY

GRADUATE INSTITUTE OF ASTRONOMY

DOCTORAL THESIS

**Tracing Historic Mass Loss from
Evolved Stars with Thermal
Emission from Cold Dust**

Author: Thavisha Erandinie DHARMAWARDENA

Supervisors: Prof. Chung-Ming KO
and
Dr. Francisca KEMPER

June 2019

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國立中央大學

天文研究所
博士論文

利用冷塵埃的熱輻射追蹤主序後星質量
流失歷史

研究生：戴維莎

指導教授：高仲明
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中華民國 108 年 6 月

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Tracing Historic Mass Loss from Evolved Stars with Thermal Emission from Cold Dust

Abstract

Thavisha Erandinie DHARMAWARDENA

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Evolved stars play a key role in the life cycle of dust in the universe. Through strong winds and supernovae they inject the material reprocessed in their cores to the interstellar medium, replenishing the interstellar medium with heavy elements. As evolved stars are so numerous they are extremely effective in this role. In this thesis we study this mass loss delving deep into their past, exploring dust mass-loss events which occurred throughout their lifetime as evolved stars. The typical treatment of evolved stars has been to only account for present day mass loss or assume they are quasi-stable undergoing constant mass loss throughout their lifetime. Historic mass loss can be effectively traced using thermal emission from the dust which cools down as it moves away from the central star. We exploit Herschel/PACS far-infrared ($70\ \mu\text{m}$, $100\ \mu\text{m}$ and $160\ \mu\text{m}$) and JCMT/SCUBA-2 sub-millimetre ($450\ \mu\text{m}$ and $850\ \mu\text{m}$) observations to study this historic mass loss. These two sets of observations are especially powerful, tracing the radial variation in the circumstellar envelopes of evolved stars. We establish the presence of variations in mass loss for a sample of Milky Way evolved stars by studying features observed in surface-brightness, temperature, dust mass-column density and spectral index of dust emissivity radial profiles. By comparing these results to predictions for a constant-outflow model we find significant deviations between the total dust masses determined for the two scenarios, demonstrating that the effect of mass-loss variations cannot be ignored. We determine the complexities of the detached shell of U Ant with the aid of radiative transfer modelling, prompting the need for further study at higher angular resolution. The analysis of the sub-mm periodicity of IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti, two well-known evolved stars, shows that it may be possible to use sub-mm light curves of evolved stars to study the nature of dust formation/destruction in their inner envelope effectively. The optical

and sub-mm light curves of IRC+10216 shows an offset in phase of $\sim 3/4$. Using radiative transfer modelling as well as findings in literature we attribute the sub-mm variability and phase lag to both the relationship between stellar pulse and dust formation/destruction cycle as well as a second unknown mechanism which needs to be narrowed down in the future. Moving on from the Milky Way to the Magellanic clouds we combine cutouts of evolved stars identified in the mid-infrared but not detected in the far-IR. The cutouts are generated from the Herschel HERITAGE survey at $100 \mu\text{m}$ allowing a statistical study of the existence or absence of a far-IR component as a result of cold dust in these evolved stars. We successfully produce detections for three stacks comprised of the highest mass-loss rate sources, showcasing the merits of the stacking method. With this thesis we emphasise the variations in structure and hence historic mass loss of evolved stars. By doing so we highlight the importance of including these variations in studies which include dust production by evolved stars in the future.

利用冷塵埃的熱輻射追蹤主序後星質量流

失歷史

摘要

戴維莎

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主序後星在宇宙塵埃的生命週期中扮演關鍵角色。由於主序後星數量眾多，因此能有效率的透過強恆星風和超新星噴發其核心中合成的原料，並以此提供星際介質中的重元素。在這篇論文中，我研究了主序後星的質量流失，深入研究並探索它們過去一生中的塵埃質量流失事件。主序後星的典型研究方法是僅考慮當前的質量流失，或假設它們在其生命週期中經歷近似穩定的質量流失。塵埃從恆星中心離開時會冷卻，可以利用塵埃的熱輻射有效地追其質量流失歷程。本論文使用Herschel / PACS遠紅外望遠鏡（波長70微米、100微米和160微米）和JCMT / SCUBA-2次毫米波望遠鏡（450微米和850微米）來觀測。這兩組觀測結果非常強大，可追主序後星周圍包層的徑向變化。本論文透過觀察研究表面亮度、溫度、塵埃質量 - 柱密度和徑向的塵埃輻射率光譜指數中的特徵，確定了銀河系主序後星取樣的質量流失變化。將這些結果與恆定流出模型的預測進行比較，本論文發現此兩種情景決定的總塵埃質量間有顯著偏差。因此進一步顯示了質量流失變化的影響不容忽視。本論文利用輻射轉移模型確定了唧筒座U星的分離殼層複雜性，並指出進一步研究的需要。兩個著名主序後星IRC + 10216和鯨魚座 θ 星的次毫米波週期的分析顯示，可能可使用主序後星的次毫米波光變曲線來有效研究它們包層內部的塵埃形成和分解性質。IRC + 10216顯示可見光和次毫米觀測的偏移相位約為 $3/4$ 。使用模型預測和過去的報告，顯示恆星脈衝和塵埃形成/分解之間的關係。這篇論文包含了位於銀河系及麥哲倫雲星系，在中紅外波段觀測到但遠紅外波段沒有觀測到的主序後星。由Herschel HERITAGE普查計劃，波長為100微米的調查，可以對這些主序後星中冷塵埃的遠紅外波段成份存在與否進行統計研究。本論文成功提出由最高質量流失率來源組成的三疊檢測，展示了堆疊法的優點。本論文展示結構的變化率及質量流失歷程，並強調這些在銀河系及之外的天體，分析研究其塵埃產生的重要性。

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List of Publications

1. **T.E. Dharmawardena**, F. Kemper, P. Scicluna, et al., *Extended dust emission from nearby Asymptotic Giant Branch stars*, MNRAS 479, 536-552, 2018.
2. A. Saintonge, C.D. Wilson, . . . , **T.E. Dharmawardena**, et al., *JINGLE, A JCMT legacy survey of dust and gas for galaxy evolution studies: I. Survey overview and first results*, MNRAS 481, 3497-3519, 2018.
3. M Smith, C. J. R. Clark, , **T.E. Dharmawardena**, et al., *JINGLE, a JCMT legacy survey of dust and gas for galaxy evolution studies: II. SCUBA-2 850 μ m data reduction and dust flux density catalogues*, MNRAS 486, 4166-4185, 2019.
4. **T.E. Dharmawardena**, F. Kemper, S. Srinivasan, et al., *The Nearby Evolved Stars Survey: I. JCMT/SCUBA-2 Sub-millimetre detection of the detached shell of U Antliae*, submitted to MNRAS, 20 pages.
5. **T.E. Dharmawardena**, F. Kemper, J.G.A. Wouterloot, et al., *Sub-mm variability of IRC+10216 and α Ceti*, submitted to MNRAS, 12 pages.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Shortly after the Big Bang the universe consisted only of the 3 lightest elements: Hydrogen, Helium and Lithium. All elements heavier than that were later synthesised in stars and released into their surroundings through various methods of mass loss.

Material from the Interstellar Medium (ISM) is consumed in the formation of stars. It is recycled and released at the later stages of the stars' lives through pulsation driven circumstellar winds and Supernovae (SNe) giving rise to the life cycle of interstellar matter.

Baryonic matter is comprised of two main components, namely gas and dust. Although cosmic dust constitutes only 1% of the baryonic mass in the universe, it plays a crucial role in galaxies and their evolution. Dust acts as a catalyst for the formation of key molecules such as H_2 and a sink for metals. Dust cooling counteracts internal pressure in molecular clouds leading to star formation and nucleosynthesis. Thus it is important to understand the life cycle of dust in the universe as part of the life cycle of matter. This cycle is illustrated in Fig. 1.1.

As demonstrated in Fig. 1.1, evolved stars are responsible for injecting dust and gas reprocessed throughout their main-sequence life time into the ISM. This replenishes the ISM with heavy elements creating conditions for star formation and thus ensuring the continuation of the cycle of matter.

Figure 1.1 The life cycle of matter. Material processed by nucleosynthesis is released into the ISM through circumstellar mass-loss from evolved stars (Giants) and SNe. This matter is then reprocessed during the star-formation process (Figure by NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center; http://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/teachers/lessons/xray_spectra/images/life_cycles.jpg).

Low to intermediate mass ($0.8 - 8 M_{\odot}$) main sequence stars exhaust the Hydrogen (H) in their core, causing core contraction. Their outer layers expand and cool causing the star to become a Red Giant. Once the temperature of the core increases sufficiently ($\sim 3 \times 10^8$ K), core Helium (He) burning begins and the star moves onto the Horizontal Branch of the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram. Following this stage the star will move on to the Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) after the completion of core-He burning and begin shell H- and He-burning. The H- and He-burning shells in AGB stars surround a degenerate CO-core.

While giants evolving from high mass stars do emit more matter into the ISM individually, as a group AGB stars due to their large numbers are one of the most effective producers of dust and heavy elements in the universe. AGB stars primarily produce C, contribute to the production of Li, N, O, Ne and undergo the s-process (Lattanzio et al., 1996, Karakas, 2014). The typical mass-loss rates of AGB stars range from $\sim 10^{-7}$ to $10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (e.g. Danilovich et al., 2015). Boyer et al. (2012) find that dust production by Carbon-rich AGB stars (discussed below) contribute up to $\sim 91\%$ of the total dust produced by evolved stars in the Magellanic Clouds.

AGB stars are inherently variable. The variability in AGB stars is a result of stellar pulsations with brightness variations occurring on the scales of hundreds of days. As a result of instabilities, the convective layers of the star undergoes periodic expansion and contraction giving rise to these stellar pulsations (Höfner & Olofsson, 2018). These large-amplitude long-period pulsations lift photospheric material, cooling it significantly (to ~ 1000 K). As material is lifted up it collides with material above it resulting in shocks which increase the densities locally. In these elevated densities dust condensation is thought to take place (Habing & Olofsson, 2003, and references therein). The newly formed grains are subject to radiation pressure which aids the pulsation driven winds to carry the dust outwards ejecting it to the ISM together with gas which is dragged along.

A schematic diagram of the structure of a typical AGB star as discussed here is shown in Fig. 1.2, which highlights the physical processes which occurs in and around the dust formation zone. The figure demonstrates how the stellar pulses dredge material from the convective core and raise them up. As shown here, the dust formed is accelerated out to the ISM from the CSE by strong radiation pressure driven winds.

AGB stars are typically characterised into three different chemical classes:

- 1) Carbon (C) – rich:** Towards the later stages of an AGB star’s life Carbon is formed in the He-fusion shell as a byproduct of the triple- α process. In low mass AGB stars ($< 4 M_{\odot}$) this C material is brought up to the surface of the star as a result of the third-dredge up process (cycle of convection). This enriches the stellar envelope with C causing the $C/O > 1$ resulting in C-rich AGB stars. The dust chemistry in the CSEs of C-rich AGB stars is predominantly amorphous carbon. It is also assumed C-rich AGBs are late stage evolutionary AGBs (Habing & Olofsson, 2003, and references therein). Every $\sim 10^4 - 10^5$ years, the He-shell has sufficient He build up that it begins He-fusion releasing tremendous amounts of energy ($\sim 10^8 L_{\odot}$ at peak; Pols et al., 2001). During this process H-fusion in the shell temporally ceases. The stellar luminosity increases and processed material, especially C, is dredged up from the shells towards the surface. This is an extremely violent process known as a

Figure 1.2 Schematic diagram of an AGB star. The inert C/O core is surrounded by H/He fusion shells. Material dredged up from these regions is lifted up to the dust formation zones where they cool. Shocks caused as a result of material interactions increase the density in this zone and dust formation is thought to take place. Pulsation-driven strong winds carry material formed in the dust formation zones out to the circumstellar envelope and from there to the ISM (Figure by J.Hron; <http://www.univie.ac.at/agb/agbdetail.html>).

thermal pulse (or He-shell flash), which results in the star losing a significant amount of its mass (Willems & de Jong, 1988). All C-rich stars begin as intermediate mass O-rich ($\sim 2 - 4M_{\odot}$; see below) AGB stars and it is thought thermal pulses are what convert an AGB star into C-rich. Following multiple thermal pulses the material expelled from the envelope will become planetary nebulae and the core a white dwarf.

2) Oxygen (O) – rich: The C at the base of the convective envelopes in high mass AGB stars ($4 - 8 M_{\odot}$) is burned away by a process known as hot bottom burning. Hot bottom burning is when the convective envelope of an AGB star reaches sufficient temperatures for nucleosynthesis. This occurs when the convective envelope extends down to the H-shell kick-starting nuclear fusion in a thin layer of the convective envelope. The hot bottom burning process consumes ^{12}C , while producing ^{13}C and ^{14}N (Lattanzio et al., 1996). This process leaves the stellar atmosphere dominated

by O ($C/O < 1$) giving rise to the O-rich AGB stars (Habing & Olofsson, 2003, and references therein). Some intermediate mass AGB stars ($\sim 2 - 4M_{\odot}$) begin as O-rich and after undergoing a number of thermal pulses will be converted into C-rich. During the transition from O- to C-rich the dust chemistry of the CSE will be converted from silicates and metal oxides of the O-rich AGB stars to that of C-rich described above. AGB stars in the low mass range of $< 2 M_{\odot}$ never produce sufficient C and remains as O-rich stars throughout their life time.

3) S-type: This type of AGBs are thought to be at an intermediate stage of the evolution along the AGB. Their atmospheres are some where in between C-rich and O-rich and characterised by the presence of ZrO, with $C/O \sim 1$ (Ramstedt et al., 2017).

High mass stars ($10 - 30 M_{\odot}$) undergo their evolution at a much faster pace than their low – intermediate mass counter parts, typically spending their life within or close to the parent molecular cloud. Within 5 – 20 million years they exhaust their core Hydrogen, begin H – shell burning around the He core and evolve into the Red Super Giant (RSG) Phase. One to two million years later they will have used up the He in their core and begin C burning. This fusion process continues all the way to Iron core formation reaching the end of the RSG phase. At this point the RSG will undergo core-collapse and explode creating a Supernova (e.g., Murdin & Murdin, 1985, Ekström et al., 2012, Fraser et al., 2014).

RSGs typically undergo significant mass loss, losing up to 60% of their initial mass prior to exploding as supernovae (Meynet et al., 2015). The amount of mass lost during the RSG phase is important since variations in mass loss result in variation to the evolutionary pathways (e.g: type of SNe). In certain extreme cases high enough mass loss may prevent the formation of supernova, instead forming super AGB stars with continuing mass-loss. In some other cases a *failed* supernova occurrence may take place, where the newly formed black hole consumes the star from the inside resulting in a much fainter explosion (Reynolds et al., 2015). All these various evolutionary tracks will result in different ISM enrichment pathways.

The metallicity of the environment in which a star forms effects its evolution including while on the AGB (Karakas, 2014). Metals are defined in astronomy as elements heavier than Helium. AGB stars formed in metal-poor environments have a lower abundance of C and O. Therefore intermediate mass O-rich AGBs which are converted into C-rich require less C to be produced for the conversion to occur. Therefore in low metallicity environments like the Magellanic clouds we may see fewer O-rich stars compared to the Milky Way. Theoretically metallicity is expected to effect the mass-loss and dust production of AGB stars (McDonald & Trabucchi, 2019). However, the limited observational analyses suggest that metallicity has no effect on either mass-loss rates (van Loon et al., 2008) or dust production in AGB stars (Boyer et al., 2017).

The SAGE (Surveying the Agents of Galaxy Evolution) collaboration has carried out extensive studies into the dust budget and production in the Magellanic Clouds (Meixner et al., 2006). Using Spitzer near and mid-IR observations they have determined that collectively AGB stars produce $\sim 1.9 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the Large Magellanic clouds (LMC), while RSGs produce a total of $\sim 2.0 \times 10^{-6} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Riebel et al., 2012). Therefore the total dust-production rate in the LMC by evolved stars is $\sim 2.1 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. In the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC) AGBs produce $\sim 8.39 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ of dust. The yearly RSG dust production in the SMC is $4.6 \times 10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Srinivasan et al., 2016). This leads to a total dust-production rate of $\sim 8.9 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ by evolved stars in the SMC.

Given the above total dust production rates and the total dust masses in the LMC and SMC reported by Gordon et al. (2014), it would take 92 Gyr and 35 Gyr respectively for the dust in the ISM to be replenished by evolved stars. This is significantly longer than the Hubble time giving rise to the so-called *Dust Budget Crisis* (further discussed in Morgan & Edmunds, 2003, Rowlands et al., 2014). This suggests alternative dust production mechanisms are required (e.g., Jones, 2001, Elvis et al., 2002, Fulvio et al., 2017). However theoretical modelling by Schneider et al. (2014) including realistic star formation histories predict vastly shorter time scales, consistent with AGB stars and SNe as main dust producers, assuming dust destruction is negligible.

Due to brightness limitations only the highest mass-losing evolved stars can be detected beyond the Magellanic clouds. The dust production by extreme AGB stars in the M33 was determined to be $7.25 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ by Jones et al. (2015a). The authors used Spitzer near/mid-IR observations to carry out this study. Additionally using near and mid-IR observations from the UKIRT telescope, Javadi et al. (2013) determined the mass production from massive evolved stars in the inner kpc^2 M33 galaxy and found a total mass-loss rate (taking into account SNe) of $0.006 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$.

There are fewer studies analysing the dust production rate by evolved stars in the Milky Way. Primarily this is due to high extinctions along many lines of sight, foreground confusion and poorly constrained distances. Jura & Kleinmann (1989) determined a total dust mass return of $3 - 6 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ to the Milky Way using a sample of 63 dusty AGB stars within $\sim 25 \text{ kpc}^2$. Once again this survey used near/mid-IR observations from the IRAS telescope. Following a long gap in such analysis, nearly 30 years later Trejo et al., *in prep.*, has determined the dust production rates in a more systematic manner using a volume-limited sample of AGB stars, in the Solar neighbourhood. They find a total dust budget of $\sim 1.3 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for a sample of ~ 1600 stars, within 1 kpc from the Sun and a total dust budget of $\sim 4.1 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for a sample of ~ 5800 stars, within 2 kpc from the Sun.

As discussed above most surveys into the dust production by evolved stars have been carried out using near/mid-IR observations, as their SEDs peak in this range. At these wavelengths, the vast majority of the thermal dust emission comes from the warm, innermost, recent dust ejecta. Cooler, more distant, historic mass-loss contributes little to the emission at mid-infrared wavelengths. Evolved stars in these studies are therefore often treated as quasi-stable systems, without incorporating treatment of their evolution, while their winds are treated as spatially and temporally homogeneous outflows.

In order to fully understand the effects of evolved stars on the life cycle of dust and their total contribution of dust into the ISM it is crucial to understand these mass-loss variations taking into account the long term historic dust mass loss. Far-IR and Sub-mm

wavelengths are sensitive to cool (< 50 K) dust emission and hence ideal to study these extended circumstellar envelopes, evaluating the historic mass loss from evolved stars.

A few studies analysing historic mass-loss show variations and structures in CSEs of evolved stars. The Herschel Mass-loss of Evolved StarS survey (MESS; [Groenewegen et al., 2011](#)), observed ~ 75 evolved stars using far-IR Herschel/PACS to analyse their CSEs. This is one of the few large surveys analysing historic dust mass-loss to date and the authors found CSEs with varying structure extending out to $1' - 2'$ (see Fig. 1.3; [Groenewegen et al., 2011](#), [Cox et al., 2012](#)). IRC+10216 (a well know C-rich AGB star) was observed by [Mauron et al. \(2013\)](#) in the optical and by [Decin et al. \(2011\)](#) in the far-IR. The two works show historic dust ejecta of IRC+10216 extending out to $\sim 46''$ and $\sim 5.2'$ respectively with the circumstellar envelope possessing arc-like structures.

Figure 1.3 A sample of PACS $70 \mu\text{m}$ observations from [Cox et al. \(2012\)](#) obtained as part of the Herschel MESS survey ([Groenewegen et al., 2011](#)). These observations show the variations in the circumstellar envelope structure observable at long wavelengths. Left: \omicron Ceti - AGB; Middle: α Ori - RSG; Right: IRC+10216 - AGB.

Water vapour in the Earth's atmosphere absorbs most far-IR radiation. Therefore for optimal far-IR observational capabilities we require space telescopes. However since the end of the Herschel mission in 2013 our capabilities have been significantly limited, with only the SOFIA mission and a handful of balloon missions in existence at the moment. We expect this limitation to continue for at least a further decade. Further at these wavelengths the ability to discern dust properties (e.g., spectral index of dust emissivity and opacity) is limited, while the sub-mm wavelength is sensitive to these properties. The combination of longer sub-mm wavelengths along with far-IR studies is particularly powerful and can help overcome this.

Sub-mm studies of the historic mass-loss of evolved stars are typically either limited to analysis of the central ejecta assuming constant mass-loss rate and/or limited to studying only the CO gas mass loss component. [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) observed the sub-mm dust continuum of nine evolved stars using the APEX/LABoCa instrument. However the low sensitivity of LABoCa meant the authors were only able to analyse the central component and a small amount of extended emission for a handful of sources.

Therefore, due to the reasoning described above there has been a need to study the historic dust mass loss of evolved stars in detail which will take into account the various instabilities, variations and structure. The analysis in this thesis has been carried with the aim of contributing to this effort.

In this thesis we have analysed the historic dust mass loss of evolved stars, its effects and contributions into the ISM both in the Milky Way and the LMC. This analysis was carried out primarily using far-IR observations from the Herschel telescope's Photometric Array Camera and Spectrograph instrument (PACS; [Poglitsch et al., 2010](#)) and sub-millimetre (sub-mm) observations from the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope's (JCMT) Sub-millimetre Common-User Bolometer Array 2 (SCUBA-2) instrument ([Holland et al., 2013](#)). Observations from these two instruments are ideal for surveying the extended circumstellar envelopes of evolved stars as we are able to trace the radial variations effectively.

This thesis is separated into four main chapters, with an introduction (this chapter) and a final conclusion. In chapter 2 we analyse a sample of AGB and RSG stars in the solar neighbourhood. We have studied their extended circumstellar envelopes and determined CSE dust properties and dust production rates. In the third chapter we delve deeper into analysing a detached shell source U Ant in order to determine its shell structure and how it was formed. In the fourth chapter we analyse the sub-mm variability of two of the most well known galactic AGB stars (IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti). In the fifth chapter we move beyond the Milky Way into the Magellanic Clouds to study the far-IR dust emission from evolved stars detected by the Spitzer surveys in the mid-IR. The overall results of these studies are summarised and concluded in chapter 6, the final chapter of this thesis.

Chapter 2

Extended Dust Emission from Nearby Evolved Stars

The work in this chapter is published by Dharmawardena et al. (2018) under the title Extended Dust Emission from Nearby Evolved Stars in MNRAS (doi: 10.1093/mnras/sty1422). The work in this chapter is fully reproducible and the scripts and data required to reproduce this analysis, figures and tables can be downloaded from <https://github.com/Thavisha/EvolvedStarsDustEmission>.

Abstract

We present JCMT SCUBA-2 450 μm and 850 μm observations of 14 Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars (9 O-rich, 4 C-rich and 1 S-type) and one Red Supergiant (RSG) in the Solar Neighbourhood. We combine these observations with *Herschel*/PACS observations at 70 μm and 160 μm and obtain azimuthally-averaged surface-brightness profiles and their PSF subtracted residuals. The extent of the SCUBA-2 850 μm emission ranges from 0.01 to 0.16 pc with an average of $\sim 40\%$ of the total flux being emitted from the extended component. By fitting a modified black-body to the four-point SED at each point along the radial profile we derive the temperature (T), spectral index of dust emissivity (β) and dust column density (Σ) as a function of radius. For all the sources, the density profile deviates significantly from what is expected for a constant mass-loss rate, showing that all the sources have undergone variations in mass-loss during this evolutionary phase. In combination with results from CO line emission, we determined the dust-to-gas mass ratio for all the sources in our sample. We find that, when sources are grouped according to their chemistry, the resulting average dust-to-gas ratios are consistent with the respective

canonical values. However we see a range of values with significant scatter which indicate the importance of including spatial information when deriving these numbers.

2.1 Introduction

The origin of interstellar dust in galaxies remains only partially understood. A major problem faced by researchers currently in this area is the so-called *dust budget crisis* (e.g. [Morgan & Edmunds, 2003](#), [Rowlands et al., 2014](#)). The Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars in high-redshift galaxies have not yet had enough time to evolve into their mass-losing phase. Therefore assuming these stars are the primary contributors of dust and heavy elements of these galaxies we are unable to explain their interstellar dust masses observed, thus giving rise to the dust-budget crisis. Even in nearby galaxies, where sufficient time has elapsed for the formation of AGB stars, the dust-production rates (DPR) by AGB stars seem to be insufficient to explain the interstellar dust reservoir. For instance, at the current DPR by AGB stars and Red Supergiants (RSGs) for the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC), it would take 92 Gyr, significantly longer than a Hubble time, to produce the existing interstellar dust reservoir ([Gordon et al., 2014](#), [Boyer et al., 2012](#)). For the LMC similar conclusions can be drawn, as a replenishment time scale of 35 Gyr results from the DPR derived by [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#). While an ongoing effort to address the dust budget crisis is focused on the exploration of additional sources of dust that contribute to the interstellar dust reservoir, i.e., dust creation during supernovae explosions (e.g. [Bianchi & Schneider, 2007](#), [Gall et al., 2011](#)), dust production by active galactic nuclei ([Elvis et al., 2002](#)), and dust formation in the interstellar medium (ISM) (e.g. [Jones, 2001](#), [Fulvio et al., 2017](#)); it remains crucial to fully understand the production of dust by evolved stars, particular those on the AGB.

AGB stars have main-sequence masses in the range 1–8 M_{\odot} . They have evolved off the Main Sequence and are currently undergoing He- and H-shell burning, while a strong stellar wind develops, in which dust formation occurs (see [Habing & Olofsson, 2003](#), and

references therein). Although individual, more massive stars ($M > 8 M_{\odot}$) expel a larger dust mass into the ISM during both their supergiant and supernova stages, AGB stars are so numerous that as a group they contribute a significant amount of dust to the ISM. This makes them extremely effective in replenishing the interstellar dust reservoir, as well as contributing the products of nucleosynthesis to the galactic chemical evolution.

To establish the importance of AGB stars in the life cycle of dust in galaxies, the DPR has been determined for a number of nearby galaxies, including the LMC (Riebel et al., 2012), the SMC (Srinivasan et al., 2016), in the central kpc² of M33 (Javadi et al., 2013), and M32 (Jones et al., 2015a). The advantage of studying the AGB population in external galaxies is that the distances – and thus the luminosities – of the stars are known, which is not the case in the Milky Way. Extinction in the Galactic Plane limits the determination of a Galactic DPR in the Solar Neighborhood (Jura & Kleinmann, 1989, Trejo et al. *in prep.*), with significant uncertainties due to the difficulties in determining the luminosities. All these determinations of the integrated DPR rely on fitting of the spectral energy distribution (SED) of point sources, dominated by mid-infrared emission, using for instance the GRAMS model grid (Srinivasan et al., 2011, Sargent et al., 2011), and assuming a constant mass-loss rate (MLR).

Here, we investigate whether this constant MLR assumption is reasonable, by studying extended thermal dust emission at sub-millimetre (sub-mm) wavelengths from nearby AGB stars. We compare these resolved measurements to the expected results assuming a constant MLR. Past enhancement in MLRs will thus be revealed and we will be able to evaluate the reliability of DPRs determined by mid-infrared SED fitting. We are also able to then determine whether a cold dust reservoir exists that is not represented in these fits.

Two recent studies Ladjal et al. (2010) and Cox et al. (2012) have attempted to spatially resolve the thermal emission in the circumstellar environments of evolved stars. Ladjal et al. (2010) carried out aperture photometry of a sample of nine evolved stars observed at 870 μm with the LABoCa instrument on APEX, showing that four of the nine stars were extended at 870 μm . They also derived the total dust mass and the dust MLR for these

objects. Cox et al. (2012) generated an image atlas of nearby AGB stars at 70 and 160 μm using observations from the *Herschel* Space Observatory’s ‘Photometric Array Camera and Spectrograph’ instrument (PACS; Poglitsch et al., 2010). This revealed 78 sources with extended emission.

In order to expand the statistics provided by the sample studied by Ladjal et al. (2010), we have selected a sample of 15 sources from the *Herschel* atlas published by Cox et al. (2012) showing extended emission more than 1’ away from the central position for followup with the Sub-millimetre Common-User Bolometer Array 2 (SCUBA-2) instrument on the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope (JCMT). Compared to LABoCa, SCUBA-2 has better sensitivity and a larger field of view of $\sim 45 \text{ arcmin}^2$ (Holland et al., 2013). Combining these SCUBA-2 continuum observations at 450 μm and 850 μm with the *Herschel*/PACS observations at 70 μm and 160 μm allows us to study the extended thermal emission due to a cold thermal dust component. Thus we are able to trace the dust mass-loss history in better detail than what may be achieved with *Herschel* data alone.

This study is a pilot for the Nearby Evolved Star Survey (NESS¹) (Scicluna et al., *in prep*) which targets a volume-limited sample of Galactic AGB stars in both continuum and CO line emission. The NESS observations are being carried out using multiple sub-mm telescopes, including the JCMT, and the resulting data will be analysed to derive robust statistics of stellar dust and gas return to the Galactic ISM.

This chapter is organised as follows: In Sect. 2.2 we present the sample and observation strategy along with the data reduction methods used. We then derive and analyse the radial surface-brightness profile and its PSF-subtracted equivalent (i.e. the residual profile; Sect. 2.4.1). Subsequently we derive and discuss radial profiles of the temperature (T), spectral index of dust emissivity (β), and dust column density (Σ) (Sect. 2.4.2). Section 2.4.4 present the total dust masses, dust mass-loss rates and dust-to-gas ratio measurements and their implications. Finally, our findings are summarised in Sect. 2.5.

¹<http://www.eaobservatory.org/jcmt/science/large-programs/ness/>

2.2 Observations and Data Reduction

2.2.1 Source selection and SCUBA-2 observations

The observations presented in this chapter were carried out as part of programs M15AI65 and M15BI047 on the JCMT, which aimed to study both the dust and the gas mass-loss rates and histories of nearby AGB stars. Therefore these programs also included both SCUBA-2 continuum and HARP CO(3-2) line observations.

The sources in both the M15AI65 and M15BI047 samples were selected from the *Herschel* MESS (*mass-loss from Evolved StarS*) survey sample (Groenewegen et al., 2011), showing extended emission out to a radius $\geq 1'$ at PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$ (Cox et al., 2012). With CO(3-2) observations in mind, we also stipulated the presence of strong CO(3-2) line emission with a peak $T_{\text{MB}} \gtrsim 2$ K. Observing time allocated and telescope scheduling constraints then further restricted us to SCUBA-2 observations for 14 objects, with a fifteenth object (IRC +10216) being a calibration source and thus having sufficient archival observations available to be included in the analysis of the sample. Furthermore, our observations of *o* Cet, the archetypal Mira, another JCMT pointing calibration source, have been supplemented with archival data.

The sample is summarised in Tab. 2.1, which shows the source IRAS name, Identifier, RA and Dec. The table also presents the source type and chemistry (C-rich AGB star (C-AGB), O-rich AGB star (O-AGB), or Red Supergiant (RSG)). The distance and terminal velocities obtained from literature. Further we also present the observation program ID and total observing times for the JCMT SCUBA-2 observations.

We used the SCUBA-2 receiver (Holland et al., 2013, Chapin et al., 2013) on the JCMT to simultaneously generate continuum maps at both $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ of the 13 AGB stars and one RSG. The targets were observed using the SCUBA-2 DAISY scan pattern observing mode with a scan velocity of $155''\text{s}^{-1}$ along the scan axis.

We also obtained JCMT HARP CO 3-2 observations for our sample via the M15AI65 and M15BI047 programs in order to study the gas mass emission in our sample. However this is beyond the scope of this chapter and these observations will be combined with the NESS sample and analysed for a later publication.

2.2.2 SCUBA-2 data reduction

The SCUBA-2 data was downloaded from the Canadian Astronomy Data Centre (CADC)² digital archives. The reduction of this data was done using the Starlink ORAC-DR pipeline (Currie et al., 2014, Jenness & Economou, 2015). Specific reduction recipes are available for extended emission (REDUCE SCAN EXTENDED SOURCE) and point sources (REDUCE SCAN ISOLATED SOURCE; Chapin et al. (2013)). Although we are looking for extended emission, the extent of this emission is relatively small and weak compared to the bright central point source, causing the radial profile to deviate only slightly from the point spread function (PSF). Thus, we elected to use the REDUCE SCAN ISOLATED SOURCE recipe with some edited parameters, as it uses the position of the peak emission by fitting a PSF to each observation to calibrate the pointing of each observation.

By default, the REDUCE SCAN ISOLATED SOURCE recipe assumes the emission to be zero beyond a radius of $1'$ from the central pixel³ for the first few iterations. As we are interested in detecting emission extending beyond $1'$, we adjusted the recipe and the constraint radius was set to $1.5'$. Extending the radius beyond this value would result in an artificial effect known as *blooming* where the source emission is blended with and hence confused with the background emission. A smaller radius than the chosen one would result in an artefact known as *negative bowling* where the pipeline enhances the central point source significantly while resulting in an artificial negative region beyond the central point source. The chosen radius results in a compromise between the two effects to enhance as much extended emission, while minimising the said artefacts.

²<http://www.cadc-ccda.hia-ihp.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/en/jcmt/>

³<http://starlink.eao.hawaii.edu/devdocs/sc21.htx/sc21.html>

Table 2.1 Source Information and Observation Details

IRAS	Identifier	RA (J2000) (hh:mm:ss)	Dec(J2000) (dd:mm:ss)	Type	Chemistry	Distance (pc)	v_∞ ^(e) (km s ⁻¹)	Program ID	Observation Time (s)
10131+3049	CIT 6 (RW LMi)	10:16:02.28	+30:34:19.0	AGB	C-rich	440 ± 132 ^(a)	20.8	M15BI047	7591
21439-0226	EP Aqr	21:46:31.85	-02:12:45.9	AGB	O-rich	113.6 ± 8.1 ^(b)	11.5	M15BI047	5606
03507+1115	IK Tau	03:53:28.87	+11:24:21.7	AGB	O-rich	260.0 ± 10.0 ^(b)	18.5	M15BI047	7583
01037+1219	IRC+10011 (WX Psc)	01:06:25.98	+12:35:53.1	AGB	O-rich	740.0 ± 222 ^(a)	19.8	M15BI047	7448
09452+1330	IRC+10216 (CW Leo)	09:47:57.41	+13:16:43.6	AGB	C-rich	130.0 ± 13.0 ^(b)	14.5	archival	~156000
23320+4316	LP And	23:34:27.53	+43:33:01.2	AGB	C-rich	630.0 ± 189 ^(a)	14.0	M15BI047	7475
...	NML Cyg	20:46:25.54	+40:06:59.4	RSG	...	1610.0 ± 120.0 ^(c)	33.0	M15AI65	7116
02168-0312	<i>o</i> Ceti (Mira)	02:19:20.79	-02:58:39.5	AGB	O-rich	91.7 ± 10.2 ^(b)	8.1	M15BI047 + archival	~179000
23558+5106	R Cas	23:58:24.87	+51:23:19.7	AGB	O-rich	125.8 ± 16.4 ^(b)	13.5	M15BI047	7541
09448+1139	R Leo	09:47:33.49	+11:25:43.7	AGB	O-rich	71.3 ± 13.5 ^(b)	9.0	M15BI047	7473
14219+2555	RX Boo	14:24:11.63	+25:42:13.4	AGB	O-rich	190.8 ± 22.9 ^(b)	9.0	M15BI047	9448
04566+5606	TX Cam	05:00:51.22	+56:10:54.2	AGB	O-rich	380.0 ± 114 ^(a)	21.2	M15BI047	7649
10350-1307	U Hya	10:37:33.27	-13:23:04.4	AGB	C-rich	208.3 ± 10.0 ^(b)	8.5	M15BI047	7481
19126-0708	W Aql	19:15:23.35	-07:02:50.4	AGB	S-type	340.0 ± 102 ^(d)	20.0	M15AI65	7275
13462-2807	W Hya	13:49:02.00	-28:22:03.5	AGB	O-rich	104.3 ± 12.2 ^(c)	8.5	M15AI65	5618

The distances were obtained from the following publications: ^(a) De Beck et al. (2010), ^(b) McDonald et al. (2017), ^(c) Zhang et al. (2012), ^(d) Guandalini & Busso (2008).

^(e): The terminal velocities were obtained from De Beck et al. (2010). For sources with distances from De Beck et al. (2010) and Guandalini & Busso (2008) no published uncertainties on the distances were available and therefore we assume an uncertainty of ±30%.

However, this also means we may be ignoring possible extended emission beyond $1.5'$. The detected extended emission limits can therefore be interpreted as the lower limits to the possible extended emission if this were the case. However we demonstrate in section 2.3 that this is very unlikely to be an issue and that the extended emission determined is reliable.

2.2.3 IRC+10216 (CW Leo) and *o* Cet (Mira) SCUBA-2 data reduction

IRC+10216 and *o* Cet have been used by the JCMT as SCUBA-2 calibration sources since 2009 and 2011 respectively. Therefore in addition to the few scan science observations, a large number of short pointing observations (~ 1100) are available via the CADC archive. We reduced all publicly available data to obtain two sets of deep maps at $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ suitable for detecting extended circumstellar shell emission. The total observation times for the two sources were 43.6 h and 49.9 h respectively, which includes both the calibration and science observations. A full list of observations used is available in the GitHub repository.

Calibration (JCMTCAL) scan maps for IRC+10216 were available for the years 2010, 2011, 2014, and 2015 totalling to 2.8 h of observations and for *o* Cet for the years 2014 and 2015 (M15BI047) totalling 2.1 h. These maps were all downloaded simultaneously and reduced together using the same reduction method as described in Sect. 2.2.2.

The observation times for the pointing observations ranged from a couple of seconds to a couple of minutes. These calibration pointing observations were reduced using the REDUCE SCAN pipeline. This pipeline worked best for the pointing observations as it was a good balance between the REDUCE SCAN EXTENDED SOURCES pipeline and the REDUCE SCAN ISOLATED SOURCE pipeline; it reduces the effects of both *negative bowling* and *blooming*. The pipeline utilises the same reduction parameters as the REDUCE SCAN ISOLATED SOURCE pipeline however, it does not have the constraining radius and is also

optimised to remove any artificial large-scale emission. Since we are co-adding a large number of pointing-only observations there is no risk of background emission dominating when this pipeline is used (unlike the scan observations for the other sources in our sample where the background is mapped to a certain degree as well).

Once the pipeline has processed all the individual observations, the reduced observations are registered to a single position preparing them for co-addition. The position is chosen by fitting a 2D Gaussian to a single image to identify its peak. Once we identify the peaks for all the other images in a similar manner they are registered to the initial image's peak position. Once this process is done all the images are co-added to make a single map for each year. The entire process is repeated for the observations for all years. The resulting maps are again registered and co-added to make two single deep maps of all the pointing observations for both the $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ data sets.

2.2.4 Herschel PACS data

The data from the MESS survey were available for public access from the *Herschel* Science Archive⁴ (HSA). We downloaded pre-reduced data for observations carried out by the MESS survey using the PACS instrument (Poglitsch et al., 2010). The MESS survey carried out PACS photometer observations using the *scan map* observing mode at a medium scan speed of $20''\text{s}^{-1}$ in the blue ($70\mu\text{m}$) and red ($160\mu\text{m}$) wavelength filters covering scan lengths ranging from $6'$ to $34'$ depending on target (Groenewegen et al., 2011). We downloaded level 2.5 data products⁵ for the MESS PACS observations used in this study. This is the highest level of publicly-available reduced MESS data products in the HSA. The data products were calibrated using PACS calibration version *PACS-CAL_72_0*.

The MESS survey also observed a sample of galactic AGB stars using the *Herschel* Spectral and Photometric Imaging REceiver (SPIRE; Griffin et al., 2010). These observations cover three wavebands centred at 250, 350, and $500\mu\text{m}$. We found that only seven of

⁴<http://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/herschel/science-archive>

⁵<https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/herschel/data-products-overview>

the fifteen sources in our sample were observed using SPIRE by the MESS survey and including only those sources would affect the homogeneity of the sample and methodology. Additionally the SPIRE beam FWHM are $18''$ at $250\ \mu\text{m}$, $24''$ at $350\ \mu\text{m}$, and $42''$ at $500\ \mu\text{m}$. In this study, we are most interested in tracing circumstellar structure with typical angular diameters of $\sim 20''$ to $\sim 60''$ at sub-millimetre wavelengths. The smallest beam size of $18''$ at $250\ \mu\text{m}$ it self is $\sim 40\%$ larger than the SCUBA-2 $850\ \mu\text{m}$ beam, the lowest resolution data. Hence including the SPIRE observation would reduce the angular resolution at which the data could be analysed as the data must be interpreted on the scales corresponding to the lowest resolution observations (see Sec.2.3.2). Considering these factors we do not consider the SPIRE data in this study.

The *AKARI* Far-Infrared Surveyor's (FIS) MLHES survey (*Excavating Mass Loss History in Extended Dust Shells of Evolved Stars*; (Izumiura et al., 2009)), observed the sources in our sample at $65\ \mu\text{m}$, $90\ \mu\text{m}$, $140\ \mu\text{m}$ and $160\ \mu\text{m}$. However the data are not yet publicly available. Therefore we could not include them. The *AKARI* FIS All Sky Survey (Doi et al., 2009) observations were not deep enough in order to detect extended emission and thus not useful for the objectives of this study.

2.3 Extended Dust Emission

2.3.1 Surface-brightness profiles

We determined azimuthally-averaged stellar surface-brightness profiles assuming spherical symmetry for each source at all four available wavelengths (PACS $70\ \mu\text{m}$ and $160\ \mu\text{m}$ and SCUBA-2 $450\ \mu\text{m}$ and $850\ \mu\text{m}$).

In order to determine the amount of extended emission we compared the derived surface-brightness profiles to the telescope PSF (beam) profiles. The left hand panels in Fig. 2.1(a) depict the radial profiles for IRC+10216 at all four wavelengths. The blue dotted lines

indicate the azimuthally-averaged surface-brightness profiles and the grey solid lines represent the beam profile of each instrument at the given wavelength.

The SCUBA-2 beam at each wavelength, is comprised of two Gaussian components; a main beam component and a secondary error-beam component. The beam shape is determined to be the normalised sum of these two components, where each component is scaled by a beam amplitude factor (Dempsey et al., 2013).

The *Herschel*/PACS PSF exhibits a 2D Gaussian core and a much more complex 3-lobe structure, the shape of which was determined over a wide dynamic range using combined observations of Mars and the asteroid Vesta (Bocchio et al., 2016). The 3-lobe structure lies at around the 10 per cent level of the peak flux, and its orientation depends on the telescope position angle at the time of observation. It is customary to use deconvolution on imaging observations to interpret resolved structure, wherein the orientation of the PSF is critical to avoiding the creation artefacts in the process (e.g. Liseau et al., 2010, Marshall et al., 2011, Decin et al., 2011, Marshall et al., 2014, Ertel et al., 2014, Marshall et al., 2016, Hengst et al., 2017). Here, we are combining imaging data across a broad range of wavelengths and signal-to-noise, sampling them at the lowest spatial resolution (JCMT SCUBA-2 $850\mu\text{m}$). We therefore adopt azimuthally-averaged radial source profiles for our interpretation as the S/N of the SCUBA-2 observations is insufficient to warrant deconvolution and azimuthal averaging is the only way to recover as much extended emission as possible. To ensure homogeneity we therefore also azimuthally average the PACS source and PSF data. This is vital as statistical methods for interpreting heterogeneous data are prohibitively complex and not yet well established. Further azimuthal averaging and re-sampling smooths out the complex structure of the PACS PSF making the precise orientation at the time of observation immaterial.

As the PSF is also dependent on the scan speed of the observation, with faster scan speeds exhibiting more elongated ellipsoidal PSFs, this facet of the PSF structure must be accounted for. We have therefore used PSFs observed under the same scan speed as the PACS observations we wish to examine (i.e. observations taken at $20''s^{-1}$). Furthermore,

Table 2.2 Telescope Instrumental Information

	Herschel PACS photometer ¹		JCMT SCUBA-2 ²	
	70 μm	160 μm	450 μm	850 μm
Primary beam FWHM (arcsec)	5.46 \times 5.76	10.65 \times 12.13	7.9	13
Secondary beam FWHM (arcsec)	–	–	25	48
Main beam rel. amplitude	–	–	0.94	0.98
Secondary beam rel. amplitude	–	–	0.06	0.02

¹ http://herschel.esac.esa.int/Docs/PACS/html/pacs_om.html

² [Dempsey et al. \(2013\)](#)

the FWHM of the PACS PSF has been shown to be time-variable at levels of 3-10 per cent, depending on the waveband of observation ([Kennedy et al., 2012](#)). The 70 μm band is most critically affected, with an uncertainty in the FWHM of 10%. However, this uncertainty is negligible for our sample as we do not observe any extended emission at ~ 1 FWHM from the central PSF. Additionally when converting the radii into physical distances and look-back times the uncertainty on the source distance far outweighs any uncertainties introduced on the radii measured by the well calibrated PACS PSF.

Appropriate PACS PSFs were downloaded from the Deep *Herschel*/PACS point spread functions VizieR online data catalogue ([Bocchio et al., 2016](#)). The beam FWHMs and parameters of both telescopes are summarised in Tab. 2.2.

As depicted in Fig. 2.1(a) the PSF profiles were scaled to the peaks of the surface-brightness profiles in order to compare to our data. Knowing that we have a very bright central source and a small amount of extended emission beyond it we fit the PSF in order to subtract as much of the PSF flux as possible and emphasise the extended emission, hence deriving residual profiles of the extended circumstellar shell. This is a computationally-simple, conservative, zeroth-order approximation to deconvolution. The right hand panels in Fig. 2.1(a) show the residual profiles for IRC+10216 at all four wavelengths.

Using the residual profiles we determine the maximum radius out to which extended circumstellar shell emission is detectable at at least 3 times the noise level, i.e. the 3σ radius ($\theta_{3\sigma}$). Hereafter we take this to be the maximum verifiable circumstellar shell extent of the source at the given wavelength for our observations. We also derive the

maximum physical circumstellar shell extension at 3σ brightness level ($R_{3\sigma}$); the age of the circumstellar shell at the measured 3σ brightness extension (look-back time). The derived values are listed in Tab. 2.3.

The average sky-subtracted total stellar fluxes (F_{total}) for the fifteen sources were measured using the python `Photutils` tools (Bradley et al., 2016). The $\theta_{3\sigma}$ values were used as the source aperture size and the sizes of the sky annuli were determined using several factors. The source brightness, emission beyond 3σ levels and visible surrounding background emission affected the choice of sky annuli. Brighter, more extended sources called for a larger sky annulus in order to obtain a better averaged background value. Further, the annuli were set to avoid any bright background structure or noise spikes. At all times we took care to not include the high noise background regions found at the edge of the observations.

By integrating over the PSF radial profiles we were also able to determine the PSF flux (F_{PSF}) for each observation. We then determined the flux of the extended circumstellar shell component (F_{ext}) by subtracting the calculated PSF flux from the measured total stellar flux. We also calculated the flux percentage of the extended component ($\% F_{\text{ext}}$) when compared to that of the total star. These results are also presented in Tab. 2.3.

2.3.2 Spectral Energy Distribution fits

In order to combine the residual profiles and fit the SEDs we regridded the residual profiles onto the $850\mu\text{m}$ radial grid, the one with the lowest resolution (1 pix = $4''$). By fitting a modified black body to the SED at each radial point of the extended component, we derive the temperature (T), spectral index of dust emissivity (β), and dust column density (Σ) profiles. The model chosen to predict the surface brightness assumes a single-temperature dust population represented by a black-body modified by a single power-law emissivity (Gordon et al., 2014). The following modified black-body equation was adopted for this purpose:

$$F_\nu \propto \lambda^{-\beta} B_\nu(T). \quad (2.1)$$

The temperature-dependent surface brightness of the dust is as follows:

$$S_\nu = \Sigma_\nu \kappa B_\nu, \quad (2.2)$$

where Σ_ν is the dust column density, B_ν is the Planck function and κ is the emissivity law

$$\kappa = \kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S \left(\frac{\lambda}{160 \mu\text{m}} \right)^{-\beta_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$ is the effective emissivity at $160\mu\text{m}$. The value of $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$ depends on the properties of the dust grains in the circumstellar shell. In this chapter, we use $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S = 26 \text{ cm}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ for C-rich sources and $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S = 8.8 \text{ cm}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ for O-rich sources (including the RSG and S-type star).

To obtain these values, we computed cross sections for spherical grains of average size $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ from the Mie theory, using the ACAR optical constants for amorphous carbon grains from [Zubko et al. \(1996\)](#) and the astronomical silicate optical constants from [Ossenkopf et al. \(1992\)](#). We then extrapolated these cross-sections from the mid-IR to longer wavelengths as required by this study. However, the value of κ depends on the composition and shape/size distribution of the grains in the envelope; in particular, amorphous carbon grains are more efficient absorbers in the IR than silicate grains, and CDE grains are able to reproduce the observed sub-mm flux with much lower total shell mass.

Our chosen values for $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$ translate to ~ 0.9 and $\sim 0.3 \text{ cm}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ at $870\mu\text{m}$ for carbonaceous and oxygen-rich dust respectively, with the extrapolation curve having a slope of -1.4. [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) find $\kappa_{870\mu\text{m}}$ values ranging from $2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for O-rich AGB stars to $35 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for C-rich AGB stars. We therefore expect our dust masses to be larger than

the [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) values for the same stars by a factor of ~ 6 for O-rich stars and ~ 40 for C-rich stars.

In order to carry out SED fitting we utilised the *emcee* python package ([Foreman-Mackey et al., 2013](#)). This package uses affine-invariant Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms to carry out Bayesian inference. We apply this to the SEDs derived from our observations in order to determine the the most probable values of T , Σ and β . The full description of this method is described in appendix [A](#).

2.4 Results

2.4.1 Extent and flux levels of the thermal dust emission

The radial profiles and SCUBA-2 $850\mu\text{m}$ images for IRC+10216 and U Hya are shown in Figs. [2.1](#), [2.2](#) respectively. Similar figures for the rest of the sample are presented in the appendix [B](#). The derived results are presented in Tab. [2.3](#). The physical size for each source was determined using the measured projected radius and distances from the literature given in Tab. [2.1](#). This was then converted to an age for the circumstellar shell by combining it with terminal velocities determined by [De Beck et al. \(2010\)](#).

As seen in Figs. [2.1\(a\)](#), [2.2\(a\)](#) and [B.1\(a\) – B.13\(a\)](#), all PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$ residual profiles show clear extended emission and circumstellar shell structure. The PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ $\theta_{3\sigma}$ can be traced out to a range from $48''$ for IRC+10011 to $285''$ for IRC+10216. The resulting $R_{3\sigma}$ ranged from 0.06 ± 0.01 pc for RX Boo to 0.74 ± 0.05 for NML Cyg. The circumstellar shell of R Leo was traced out an age of 4400 ± 800 yrs and was the minimum age tractable at this wavelength. The maximum tractable look-back time nearly five times greater was for NML Cyg. All values are listed in Tab. [2.3](#).

In all sources except IK Tau and IRC+10011, the emission appeared to be less extended in PACS $160\mu\text{m}$ with $R_{3\sigma}$ traceable from 0.012 ± 0.002 pc for R Leo to 0.30 ± 0.02 pc

Table 2.3 Surface Brightness Profile Results

Source	Wavelength (μm)	$\theta_{3\sigma}$ ($''$)	$R_{3\sigma}$ (pc)	lookback time (yr)	F_{total} (Jy)	% F_{ext}	RMS (mJy arcsec $^{-2}$)
CIT 6	70	91	0.19 ± 0.06	9200 ± 2700	173.9 ± 0.3	47 ± 1	0.53
	160	70	0.15 ± 0.05	7100 ± 2100	31.4 ± 0.1	50 ± 5	0.86
	450	12.0	0.03 ± 0.01	1200 ± 700	1.56 ± 0.02	28 ± 2	0.54
	850	44.0	0.09 ± 0.03	4400 ± 1300	1.190 ± 0.001	41 ± 1	0.02
EP Aqr	70	139	0.08 ± 0.01	6500 ± 500	33.6 ± 0.1	49 ± 1	0.35
	160	26	0.014 ± 0.001	1200 ± 100	3.5 ± 0.02	22 ± 9	0.78
	450	–	–	–	–	–	0.59
	850	–	–	–	–	–	0.02
IK Tau	70	83	0.105 ± 0.004	5500 ± 200	181.8 ± 0.4	26 ± 1	1.08
	160	99	0.125 ± 0.005	6600 ± 300	27.5 ± 0.1	47 ± 5	0.89
	450	38.0	0.048 ± 0.002	2500 ± 100	1.37 ± 0.07	32 ± 6	0.58
	850	24.0	0.030 ± 0.001	1600 ± 100	0.390 ± 0.003	26 ± 1	0.02
IRC+10011	70	48	0.17 ± 0.05	8500 ± 2500	93.0 ± 0.2	25 ± 1	0.25
	160	67	0.24 ± 0.07	12000 ± 3600	17.70 ± 0.04	44 ± 3	0.79
	450	10.0	0.04 ± 0.01	1800 ± 500	0.50 ± 0.03	29 ± 11	0.89
	850	20.0	0.07 ± 0.02	3500 ± 1000	0.200 ± 0.003	35 ± 2	0.02
IRC+10216	70.0	285	0.18 ± 0.02	12100 ± 1200	3482 ± 3	57 ± 1	0.37
	160	266	0.17 ± 0.02	11300 ± 1100	556 ± 1	59 ± 2	0.61
	450	60	0.038 ± 0.004	2600 ± 300	25.23 ± 0.03	63.5 ± 0.2	0.17
	850	64	0.040 ± 0.004	2700 ± 300	10.830 ± 0.003	55.90 ± 0.03	0.01
LP And	70	51	0.16 ± 0.05	11000 ± 3300	65.7 ± 0.1	32 ± 1	0.30
	160	45	0.14 ± 0.04	9600 ± 2900	11.50 ± 0.03	40 ± 4	0.84
	450	–	–	–	–	–	0.43
	850	20	0.06 ± 0.02	4300 ± 1300	0.350 ± 0.002	21 ± 1	0.02
NML Cyg	70	94	0.74 ± 0.05	21800 ± 1600	742 ± 2	16 ± 2	1.41
	160	38	0.30 ± 0.02	8900 ± 700	111.9 ± 0.3	27 ± 7	12.87
	450	–	–	–	–	–	0.72
	850	20	0.16 ± 0.01	4600 ± 300	1.780 ± 0.003	19.9 ± 0.2	0.02
α Ceti	70	147	0.07 ± 0.01	7900 ± 900	229.2 ± 0.4	51 ± 1	0.40
	160	93	0.041 ± 0.005	5000 ± 600	33.5 ± 0.1	50 ± 5	0.99
	450	50	0.022 ± 0.003	2700 ± 300	2.64 ± 0.02	55 ± 1	0.13
	850	40	0.018 ± 0.002	2100 ± 200	0.570 ± 0.001	37.7 ± 0.3	0.01
R Cas	70	141	0.09 ± 0.01	6200 ± 800	93.8 ± 0.2	47 ± 1	1.69
	160	122	0.07 ± 0.01	5400 ± 700	15.9 ± 0.1	42 ± 3	1.22
	450	10	0.007 ± 0.001	400 ± 100	0.72 ± 0.01	30 ± 4	0.44
	850	16	0.010 ± 0.001	700 ± 100	0.270 ± 0.002	21 ± 1	0.02
R Leo	70	118	0.04 ± 0.01	4400 ± 800	71.9 ± 0.2	27 ± 2	0.45
	160	35	0.012 ± 0.002	1300 ± 300	11.60 ± 0.04	17 ± 6	0.85
	450	12	0.004 ± 0.001	500 ± 100	1.09 ± 0.01	38 ± 2	0.32
	850	–	–	–	–	–	0.02
RX Boo	70	67	0.06 ± 0.01	6800 ± 800	40.5 ± 0.1	45 ± 1	0.16
	160	32	0.030 ± 0.003	3200 ± 400	5.80 ± 0.03	31 ± 8	1.15
	450	66	0.06 ± 0.01	6600 ± 800	5.9 ± 0.1	93 ± 3	0.56
	850	32	0.030 ± 0.004	3200 ± 400	0.230 ± 0.003	50 ± 2	0.02
TX Cam	70	73	0.14 ± 0.04	6300 ± 1200	61.8 ± 0.1	32 ± 1	0.50
	160	28	0.05 ± 0.02	2400 ± 700	7.80 ± 0.03	17 ± 4	1.03
	450	–	–	–	–	–	0.39
	850	56	0.10 ± 0.03	4800 ± 1400	0.46 ± 0.01	51 ± 2	0.02

Source	Wavelength (μm)	$\theta_{3\sigma}$ ($''$)	$R_{3\sigma}$ (pc)	lookback time (yr)	F_{total}^1 (Jy)	% F_{ext}	RMS (mJy arcsec $^{-2}$)
U Hya	70	130	0.13 ± 0.01	15100 ± 700	37.1 ± 0.1	83 ± 1	0.44
	160	125	0.13 ± 0.01	14500 ± 700	15.2 ± 0.1	92 ± 1	0.97
	450	–	–	–	–	–	0.62
	850	20	0.020 ± 0.001	2300 ± 100	0.080 ± 0.002	28 ± 4	0.02
W Aql	70	69	0.11 ± 0.03	5500 ± 1700	55.9 ± 0.1	48 ± 1	0.29
	160	54	0.09 ± 0.03	4400 ± 1300	10.3 ± 0.03	54 ± 3	0.92
	450	64	0.11 ± 0.03	5200 ± 1500	17.6 ± 0.3	97 ± 3	0.98
	850	80	0.13 ± 0.04	6500 ± 1900	1.07 ± 0.01	77 ± 1	0.02
W Hya	70	141	0.07 ± 0.01	8200 ± 1000	183.7 ± 0.4	38 ± 1	0.41
	160	86	0.04 ± 0.01	5000 ± 600	32.7 ± 0.1	36 ± 5	1.03
	450	–	–	–	–	–	2.19
	850	56	0.028 ± 0.003	3300 ± 400	1.01 ± 0.01	50 ± 1	0.03

¹ All uncertainty values of SCUBA2 F_{total} carry an absolute calibration uncertainty of 10% in addition to the presented uncertainties (Dempsey et al., 2013, Mairs et al., 2017).

² The large RMS at $160\mu\text{m}$ for NML Cyg is a result of the bright background emission by the Cygnus X superbubble.

for NML Cyg. The minimum and maximum traceable look-back times at $160\mu\text{m}$ were for IRC+10011 and U Hya respectively. At both PACS wavelengths a significant portion of the total flux was found to be emitted from the extended component. We measure the weighted average of % F_{ext} at $70\mu\text{m}$ as $(52.6 \pm 0.2)\%$ with a standard deviation of 17%. At $160\mu\text{m}$, these results were $(64 \pm 1)\%$ and 19% respectively.

In the SCUBA-2 observations, the sources appear to be only marginally extended. This due to a combined effect of several factors: mainly the sensitivity differences between SCUBA-2 and PACS and beam size difference between the two filters. The larger beam size of SCUBA-2 could cause the filamentary extended emission to be blurred out and blended with the background.

While unlikely, the lower circumstellar shell extensions seen at SCUBA-2 wavelengths may also be due to the aperture defining the source region being set to $1.5'$ during SCUBA-2 data reductions. As described in section 2.2.2 we set the radius to $1.5'$ as it was the value at which the combined effect of *blooming* and *negative bowling* was minimised.

However circumstellar shell emission at 3σ levels beyond the constraining radius for this sample is unlikely given the results for IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti. Both IRC+10216 and Mira

have extensions greater than $1.5'$ at PACS wavelengths and both sources have observation times ≥ 21 times the other 13 sources. IRC+10216 is also the brightest source in our sample at all wavelengths. The reduction process used for these two sources as described in section 2.2.3 does not have the constraining radius set and therefore no emission is ignored. Considering all these factors we still see $\theta_{3\sigma}$ less than $1.5'$ allowing us to surmise that the 13 sources reduced with the constraining radius do not have any emission beyond the $1.5'$ radial limit in excess of the 3σ level.

However, in case there is circumstellar shell emission beyond the limiting aperture radius which is unaccounted for we assume the results derived for $\theta_{3\sigma}$ and $R_{3\sigma}$ are lower limits. This assumption also allows us to account for the fact that these two radii are dependent on the noise levels.

While 13 of the 15 sources in our sample showed extended circumstellar shell emission at 3σ levels at $850\mu\text{m}$, only 9 sources showed circumstellar shell extensions at $450\mu\text{m}$, due to the relatively higher noise levels at this wavelength. The traceable projected radii for these sources varied from $16''$ for R Cas to $80''$ for W Aql at $850\mu\text{m}$. At $450\mu\text{m}$ they varied from $10''$ for IRC+10011 and R Cas to $66''$ for RX Boo. In the case of W Aql we suspect that the detected larger extent may be a result of the background within the source aperture being enhanced during the reduction process (as described in section 2.2.2). The $\theta_{3\sigma}$ values for SCUBA-2 observations for this source are comparable to those of the PACS observations which is unlikely. Furthermore, W Aql is less extended than IRC+10216 at *Herschel* wavelengths but more extended in SCUBA-2 wavelengths, providing possible evidence for the circumstellar shell being merged with the enhanced background making it difficult to separate the two. The same conditions may also result in the extensions seen for RX Boo at $450\mu\text{m}$ which also has extensions greater than that of IRC+10216 at $450\mu\text{m}$.

The APEX LABoCa $870\mu\text{m}$ radial profiles presented in the previous study by [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) show that only 4 out of 9 sources are extended at 3σ brightness levels, while we see extended emission at 3σ brightness levels in the $850\mu\text{m}$ SCUBA-2 observations in 13 out

of 15 sources. Furthermore, for the three sources in common with Ladjal et al. (2010); IRC+10216 (Fig. 2.1(a)), IRC+10011 (Fig. B.4(a)) and *o* Ceti (Fig. B.7(a)), we are able to detect extended emission $\sim 10\%$ - $\sim 25\%$ further out than Ladjal et al. (2010). This is due to a factor of ~ 1.5 lower noise levels of the SCUBA-2 observations compared to that of the APEX LABoCa instrument. It is therefore clear that this factor of ~ 1.5 difference is significant when considering the faint outer extended emission of these sources.

The physical radii of the circumstellar shell at $850\mu\text{m}$ ranged from as low as 0.010 ± 0.001 pc in the case of R Cas to 0.16 ± 0.01 pc for NML Cyg. We trace a minimum look-back time of 700 ± 100 years for R Cas at this wavelength, while the maximum age traced out to at 3σ surface brightness level is 6500 ± 1900 years for W Aql. At $450\mu\text{m}$ the least extended physical radius, 0.004 ± 0.001 pc, was observed for R Leo and the most extended source at this wavelength was W Aql with $R_{3\sigma}$ equal to 0.11 ± 0.03 pc. At $450\mu\text{m}$, the emission ages traced out to a range of 400 ± 100 years for R Cas to 6600 ± 800 years for RX Boo.

For the sample of objects studied, we calculate a weighted averaged $\% F_{ext}$ of $(54.9 \pm 0.03)\%$ at $850\mu\text{m}$ with a standard deviation of 17% and for $450\mu\text{m}$ it was found to be $(63.1 \pm 0.2)\%$ with a standard deviation of 28% . This shows that while there is little detected extended emission a significant portion of the total flux is still emitted by the extended region at these wavelengths.

The stellar radial and circumstellar shell residual profiles also reveal sources which deviated from uniform mass-loss as well as several circumstellar shell features. They are seen in the form of bumps or enhancements in an otherwise smoothly decreasing surface-brightness profile. Sources observed to have non-uniform mass-loss or showing a significant circumstellar shell feature at PACS wavelengths, such as EP Aqr (Fig. B.2(a)), *o* Ceti (Fig. B.7(a)), R Leo (Fig. B.9(a)), U Hya (Fig. 2.2(a)), W Aql (Fig. B.12(a)) and W Hya (Fig. B.13(a)) all show such enhancements. At SCUBA-2 wavelengths all 15 sources in our sample were observed to be nearly spherically symmetric and hence show no such enhancements.

2.4.2 Radial variation in dust properties

The radially dependent T , β , Σ profiles derived for IRC+10216 and U Hya are presented in Figs. 2.1(b) and 2.2(b) and are discussed in detail in Sect. 2.4.3.2 and 2.4.3.3. Figs. B.1(b) – B.13(b) in appendix B present the parameter profiles for the rest of the sample. The profiles are plotted against both radius as well as time, with the time being the number of years elapsed since the corresponding mass has been ejected by the star calculated assuming a constant outflow velocity. Due to the PSF subtraction in the central position, the innermost $\sim 16''$ – $\sim 20''$ of the parameter profiles are unreliable.

The shape (curvature) of the fitted modified blackbody depends on both temperature and β . It has been shown that β is well constrained by the Rayleigh-Jeans tail of the SED, i.e., by longer wavelengths ($\lambda \geq 300\mu\text{m}$) (Doty & Leung, 1994, Shetty et al., 2009, Sadavoy et al., 2013). Therefore our β results are constrained by SCUBA-2 data. The temperature at each radial point is expected to be constrained by the SED peak and Wien tail of the energy distribution (Shetty et al., 2009). The temperature profile will therefore be constrained by the shorter wavelength PACS data. The circumstellar shell dust column density could be constrained by either PACS or SCUBA-2 data.

2.4.2.1 Radial Variation in β

Outside of the region affected by PSF subtraction, we see a trend of a relatively steeply increasing β profile for 11 out of the 15 sources, followed by the profile more or less flattening out. The sharply increasing region ranged from as low as 0.003 pc in the case of W Aql up to 0.08 pc for NML Cyg. The average physical size of this region was found to be 0.03 pc with a standard deviation of 0.02 pc.

This steep increase in β is most likely a result of the multiple temperature components probed along a line of sight. Along each line of sight we observe multiple dust layers and hence multiple temperature/density components. These components decrease with increasing radius meaning we probe a larger number of temperature components in the

inner region and the number probed decreases as the stellar radius increases. A larger number of temperature components will result in a broader SED peak causing β to be biased towards lower values. MCMC attempting to fit this will therefore only be able to produce a lower limit of β within this region. As we move away from the inner region the temperature components will decrease resulting in the sharpening of the SED peak allowing MCMC to better fit β , resulting in more accurate values of this parameter with increasing radius.

For all sources except IRC+10216 (discussed further on in Sect. 2.4.3.2), β flattens out to an average of $\sim 1.95 \pm 0.01$ outside of the steep inner region. For EP Aqr, R Cas, R Leo and U Hya, the four sources without the steeply increasing inner region, the radial profile is flat from the innermost reliable radial point. It is possible that the steeply increasing region for these four sources fell within the PSF reduction affected region and hence removed resulting in a near flat profile from the start.

At large radii, the β profile tend to be prior dominated. As β is is constrained by the Rayleigh-Jeans end of the SED and hence the long SCUBA-2 wavelengths, non-constraining non-detections at these wavelengths causes this effect. Therefore there are two competing effects, the multiple temperature components in the inner regions and the non-constraining non-detection in the outer regions which prevents the β profile from being constrained accurately.

As shown by Fig. A.1, the measured average of β is consistent with the peak of the probability-density function used as our β prior. This β distribution is obtained from Smith et al. (2012) who found the average ISM β of M 31 to be 1.9 ± 0.31 , consistent with the β values of the Milky Way ISM. Therefore as our β profiles are prior dominated we see no evidence for the difference between dust grain size and composition in the outer circumstellar environments and the ISM dust grain sizes and compositions. Therefore in order to better constrain β we most likely require deeper better resolved longer wavelength (i.e. SCUBA-2) observations.

2.4.2.2 Temperature Radial Variation

The presence of detections at larger radii in the PACS observations allowed MCMC to produce well-constrained temperature radial profiles. Using these profiles we were able to discern several key features of the circumstellar shell.

The inner region of the temperature profiles for all sources (top panels of Figs. 2.1(b) and 2.2(b), and Figs. B.1(b) – B.13(b) show a trend of decreasing temperature gradient with increasing radius. This is followed by a region of well constrained temperatures with an almost flat gradient. These two regions are then followed by a final region of noise dominated radial points.

The decreasing gradient trend seen in the inner $\sim 40''$ region is consistent with temperature gradient of an optically thin centrally heated spherical dust shell. The following near flat temperature gradient region has an average temperature of (37 ± 3) K, consistent with dust grains heated by a uniform Interstellar radiation field (ISRF). Dust within this region has the same temperature distribution as it is heated by the same uniform ISRF, giving rise to a single temperature dust component. Therefore the temperature radial profiles allow us to estimate the region at which stellar radiation is the dominant heating source of circumstellar shell dust and at which point the ISRF takes over and becoming the dominant source. We estimate that ISRF domination begins from $\sim 0.06 \pm 0.02$ pc for our sample translating to an average circumstellar shell age of $\sim 3300 \pm 500$ years. The point at which grain heating by the central source is balanced out by grain heating due to the ISRF is dependent primarily on the stellar luminosity. Assuming a constant ISRF, brighter sources will have larger transition radii. The transition radii are presented in Tab. 2.4, which are in qualitative agreement with the above hypothesis.

The temperature profile of five of the fifteen sources (EP Aqr, R Leo, RX Boo, TX Cam and W Aql) is noise dominated, meaning we were unable to discern the point at which the ISRF domination occurred. The temperature profile of NML Cyg, the only RSG in

Table 2.4 ISRF transition region

Source	ISRF transition region		
	(arcsec)	(pc)	(yr)
CIT 6	44	0.09	4400
EP Aqr	-	-	-
IK Tau	28	0.04	1900
IRC+10011	24	0.09	4300
IRC+10216	68	0.04	2900
LP And	24	0.07	5100
NML Cyg	24	0.19	5600
<i>o</i> Ceti	36	0.02	1900
R Cas	28	0.02	1200
R Leo	-	-	-
RX Boo	-	-	-
TX Cam	-	-	-
U Hya	52	0.05	2400
W Aql	-	-	-
W Hya	60	0.03	3500

the study deviates significantly from the rest of the sample and is discussed in detail in Sect. 2.4.3.1.

2.4.2.3 Radial variation in the dust column density

When inspecting Σ radial profiles we found them to be the best indicator of historical mass-loss variations. We compared these profiles to a Σ profile expected for uniform and constant mass-loss (Σ_{um}), which was generated by projecting a 3-dimensional model onto 1 dimension. The Σ profile of all 15 sources in our sample noticeably deviated from Σ_{um} , indicating that none of them experienced uniform and constant mass-loss in their recent evolutionary history.

Ten of the 15 sources show an increase in mass-loss rate (MLR) with increasing radius and hence look-back time, meaning these AGB stars underwent higher mass-loss in the past when they were younger. While this is what we observe for the overall Σ profile trend (i.e. large time scales) all sources also show minor modulations in their profiles indicating short time scale mass-loss variations. This increase in MLR with increasing radius could also

mean that we maybe including emission from the astrosphere where AGB winds sweep up the ISM (Wareing et al., 2007).

IRC+10216 and U Hya deviate from the increasing MLR trend with the gradients of their Σ profiles being more steep than the Σ_{um} . This points to an increasing mass-loss rate as the source evolved and it had lower mass-loss in the past (see Sect. 2.4.3.2 and 2.4.3.3).

Σ profiles LP And, RX Boo and TX Cam were noise dominated and therefore we could not determine the exact nature of their MLR variation. Due to the limitation of the observations and the resulting MLRs it is difficult to determine any further parameters such as the acceleration parameter as it would require much better constrained data. In order to overcome this, higher resolution data at longer wavelengths and better sampling are required in order to constrain the SED and hence the temperature.

The density enhancements seen in these parameter profiles allowed us to determine the presence several features for several AGB stars:

1. As seen by Fig. B.1(b), the wave-like pattern between $20'' - 70''$ in CIT 6 could be indicative of a period of ~ 5000 years where the MLR varied more rapidly instead of a smooth MLR variation.
2. The density enhancement between $48'' - 128''$ is clear evidence for the detached shell of U Hya which is discussed later on in the chapter.
3. The enhancement seen in Fig. B.12(b) up to $60''$ corresponds well to the observed denser Eastern region of the circumstellar shell of W Aql confirmed by Mayer et al. (2013).

By studying these density enhancements and the circumstellar shell age at which they occur, we were also able to determine an average of the maximum time scale for events of large scale MLR variation. We determined large scale MLR variations is observed up to $\sim 7400 \pm 1000$ years for the stars in our sample. These time scales are comparable to

thermal pulse time scale as seen by [Olofsson et al. \(1990\)](#) but are much greater than the mass-loss modulations seen by [Marengo et al. \(2001\)](#). The variations in total dust masses, MLRs and resulting dust-to-gas ratios are discussed further in Sect. 2.4.4.

2.4.3 Notes on selected sources

2.4.3.1 NML Cyg

The only Red Supergiant in our sample, NML Cyg, is understood to have its circumstellar shell shaped by the nearby Cyg OB2 association within the Cygnus X superbubble ([Schuster et al., 2006](#)). The strong emission from the background superbubble has much substructure at all wavelengths and therefore blends with the circumstellar shell emission making it near impossible to discern the difference between the two. This emission is a result of the large dust content of the Cyg X superbubble ([Zhang et al., 2012](#)). [De Beck et al. \(2010\)](#) derived a constant gas MLR of $8.7 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for this RSG and an outer circumstellar shell radius of 0.07 pc based on this constant MLR.

While NML Cyg does show 3σ brightness level extensions of $\sim 1.5'$ in the PACS $70 \mu\text{m}$ observations, it shows little to no extension in all three of the other wavelengths. This is shown by Fig. B.6(a). The converted circumstellar shell physical radius at $70 \mu\text{m}$ is 0.74 ± 0.05 pc which is ~ 10 times greater than the outer circumstellar shell predicted by [De Beck et al. \(2010\)](#). Similar to our results, [Cox et al. \(2012\)](#) also find the MESS PACS observations of NML Cyg to not be well resolved and only provide a predicted extension of ≤ 25.4 pc.

The T, Σ and β profiles as shown by Fig. B.6(b) are all indicative of strong background domination from very inner regions of the parameter profiles. All three parameter profiles begin to comparatively flatten out at ~ 0.19 pc with well constrained uncertainties. The gradient of the T and Σ profiles however do show a small change with look-back time. The T profiles appears to have a negative gradient with increasing look-back time but is still well within the expected temperature limits for ISRF dominated dust. The Σ

profile on the other hand show a slightly positive gradient. These features suggest strong ISRF and background emission domination within this region, indicating emission from the circumstellar shell of NML Cyg being blended with the surrounding Cyg X interstellar dust.

2.4.3.2 IRC+10216

The extensively studied C-rich AGB star IRC+10216 (CW Leo) is one of the brightest sources in the near-IR sky. It is also a very bright sub-mm source making it a good pointing calibrator at SCUBA-2 wavelengths. At 130 ± 13 pc (McDonald et al., 2017), it is the nearest C-rich AGB star and has a present-day mass-loss rate of $1.6 \times 10^{-6} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (De Beck et al., 2010). Mauron et al. (2013) carried out optical observations of IRC+10216 and found a spherical circumstellar envelope with extended emission outwards to an angular radius of $46''$. Cox et al. (2012) shows the presence of a wind-ISM interaction bow shock at $6.6'$ (0.23 pc). Using PACS $70\mu\text{m}$, $100\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$ observations, Decin et al. (2011) observe the extended dust envelope of IRC+10216 to be composed of multiple arcs extending outwards up to $\sim 5.2'$.

Fig. 2.1(a) shows extended emission up to a projected radius of $\sim 1'$ at the two SCUBA-2 wavelengths and $\sim 4.5'$ at the PACS wavelengths. The SCUBA-2 extent seen is comparable to the optical extent seen by Mauron et al. (2013). In addition, more than half of the emission is from the extended component at all wavelengths. The PACS extents found are smaller than those measured by Cox et al. (2012) and Decin et al. (2011) and we do not see any evidence for the dust arcs in our azimuthally averaged radial or residual profiles. This is expected as the dust arcs are non-concentric and hence will be smoothed out by azimuthal averaging.

The temperature profile shows evidence for ISRF domination from ~ 0.04 pc where it flattens out to $\sim 35.2 \pm 3.2$ K. The Σ profile has a negative overall gradient slightly steeper than Σ_{um} . This is evidence for an increase in mass-loss rate over time as confirmed by both Cernicharo et al. (2014) and Dehaes et al. (2007).

Unlike all other sources which flatten out following the steeply increasing region discussed in Sect. 2.4.2.1, the β profile of IRC+10216 show a clear negative gradient prior to flattening out. This downward trend could be caused by several factors. A change in temperature of $\sim 50\%$ or more, could result in such a negative trend. As the temperature decreases the peak of the SED will shift towards the sub-mm SCUBA-2 wavelengths causing the slope of the SED, hence apparent value β , to change. However as the temperature profile is nearly flat this is unlikely. Optical depth effects could also give rise to such a trend, however again this scenario is unlikely too. If this were the case β would evolve differently with increasing radius, i.e. the optical depth decreases with radius therefore β would increase with radius. Furthermore, the optical depths which could cause such an effect are expected to be much higher. At sub-mm wavelengths the optical depths needs to be ≥ 1 to result in such a change. Therefore this trend in β could provide evidence for the dust grain properties such as size and/or composition in the circumstellar shell of IRC+10216 evolving with radius and hence changing circumstellar shell age.

The negative gradient region of β ranges from 2.7 – 1.9 from the central star to the outskirts. This range differs from the beta values for amorphous carbon derived by [Mennella et al. \(1998\)](#), who find values close to 1 using laboratory measurements. The dust in the outskirts of IRC+10216 is comparable to silicate dust ([Mennella et al., 1998](#)) and to graphitic dust ([Draine, 2016](#)). The dust grain in the inner region agree with models by [Jones et al. \(2013\)](#) of hydrogenated amorphous carbon dust.

2.4.3.3 U Hya

U Hya is a long-period semi-regular variable carbon star with a confirmed detached shell ([Waters et al., 1994](#)). The detached shell of U Hya is the largest in angular size observed to date.

It was studied in detail by [Izumiura et al. \(2011\)](#) using far-IR AKARI observations at 65 μm , 90 μm , 140 μm and 160 μm . They measure fluxes of the decomposed detached dust shell to be 45.5 ± 0.5 Jy at 65 μm and 23.0 ± 1.5 Jy at 160 μm , integrated over the total

Figure 2.1 Observational and modelling results for AGB star IRC+10216. (a): surface-brightness profiles (blue lines; grey lines correspond to the PSF profile) and the PSF reduced residual profiles (orange lines) as a function of projected radius ($''$) and physical size (pc) for PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$ and SCUBA-2 $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$. The observed peak location is a result of the shape of the PSF being subtracted; (b): Profiles of the temperature (red lines), surface density (purple lines), and emissivity spectral index (green lines) as a function of projected radius and time. The surface density for a uniform mass-loss rate is also shown (yellow dashed lines). The shaded grey region highlights an artefact effect which arises due to the SCUBA-2 beam and should be ignored; (c): Reduced SCUBA-2 $850\mu\text{m}$ observation of source with the FWHM of the PSF (grey circle) and the maximum extension at 3σ brightness level (white circle).

shell. [Izumiura et al. \(2011\)](#) utilised a detached dust shell model and derived a dust shell temperature of 40 - 50 K and a shell β of 1.2.

Evidence for the detached shell is seen in the PACS stellar radial profiles and the residual circumstellar shell profile as shown by Fig. 2.2(a) as an enhancement between $60'' - 132''$. For the detached shell component we measure $\sim 30\%$ less flux at $70 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 40\%$ less flux at $160 \mu\text{m}$ compared to the AKARI $65 \mu\text{m}$ and $160 \mu\text{m}$ fluxes reported by [Izumiura et al. \(2009\)](#) (see Sect. 2.4.1).

The T and Σ profiles, seen in Fig. 2.2(b), also provide evidence for the detached shell. The T profile has a flat single-temperature component dominated region between $0.05 \text{ pc} - 0.13 \text{ pc}$ from the central source position. This is located in the region where the detached shell has been previously confirmed to be and is consistent with typical spherical detached shell properties. The average temperature of $35.1 \pm 0.7 \text{ K}$ measured in this region is slightly lower than that measured by [Izumiura et al. \(2011\)](#). However it is consistent with ISRF heated dust as expected given the large distance of the detached shell from the central star.

The Σ profile, which deviates significantly from the Σ_{um} profile, has a clear density enhancement from 0.05 pc to 0.13 pc . This corresponds to the region of the detached shell visible in PACS observations allowing us to obtain a measured width of 0.08 pc for the detached shell which fall well within the range of shell of thicknesses determined by [Izumiura et al. \(2011\)](#).

The MLR suddenly increased between 14000 and 15000 years into look-back time. Then the slope decreases significantly moving towards the present indicating the mass-loss rate decreased as time progressed. The scenario is well matched with the MLR variations expected for a detached shell. Using these results we are able to determine that the high mass losing event, hypothesised to be a thermal pulse, which created the detached shell, occurred $\sim 14000 - 15000$ years ago.

The β profile is prior dominated, and hence flat due to the lack of detections in the long-wavelength observations. Therefore we can not draw any conclusions on the grain properties of U Hya using this profile.

2.4.4 Dust mass-loss Rates and Dust-to-Gas Ratios

Assuming that the gas mass-loss rate is constant, we utilised the terminal velocities measured using CO line emission and the CO MLRs presented in [De Beck et al. \(2010\)](#) to obtain the CO gas mass of the extended component for each of our sources. Combining resolved extended MLRs with point source MLRs and/or assuming constant MLRs for extended sources may not be justifiable. However applying these commonly-employed methods enables us to test the effects of such assumptions.

We employed the PACS $160\mu\text{m}$ $R_{3\sigma}$ extensions, presented in [Tab. 2.3](#), as the shell radii for this purpose. This radius was chosen over the more extended PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ radius as MCMC is able to better constrain Σ and its uncertainties with two detections at a given radial point.

We then derived the dust mass of the extended circumstellar shell components by integrating over the Σ profile up to the same PACS $160\mu\text{m}$ radii. By dividing the integrated dust mass by the age of the circumstellar shell we also derived the dust mass-loss rate which can be compared to the gas mass-loss rate. Further, by dividing the integrated dust mass by measured CO gas mass we were able to acquire the dust-to-gas mass ratios for the sources in our sample.

The resulting values are presented in [Tab. 2.5](#) and the dust-to-gas mass-loss rate comparison is shown in [Fig. 2.3](#). When comparing the dust-to-gas ratios of sources we noticed five of the fifteen were outliers with dust-to-gas ratios > 0.050 . The sources were IRC+10216, *o* Ceti, R Leo, U Hya and W Hya, three O-rich and two C-rich sources. When calculating averaged results we therefore left these sources from consideration.

Figure 2.2 Observational and modelling results for AGB star U Hya. (a): surface-brightness profiles (blue lines; grey lines correspond to the PSF profile) and the PSF reduced residual profiles (orange lines) as a function of projected radius (") and physical size (pc) for PACS 70 μm and 160 μm and SCUBA-2 450 μm and 850 μm . The observed peak location is a result of the shape of the PSF being subtracted; (b): Profiles of the temperature (red lines), surface density (purple lines), and emissivity spectral index (green lines) as a function of projected radius and time. The surface density for a uniform mass-loss rate is also shown (yellow dashed lines); (c): Reduced SCUBA-2 850 μm observation of source with the FWHM of the PSF (grey circle) and the maximum extension at 3σ brightness level (white circle).

Table 2.5 Total Dust and Gas Masses and MLRs

Source	\dot{M}_{gas} ($M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	$\log(M_{\text{gas}})$ (M_{\odot})	\dot{M}_{dust} ($M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	$\log(M_{\text{dust}})$ (M_{\odot})	Dust/Gas Ratio	\dot{M}_{GRAMS} ($M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
CIT 6	5.9×10^{-6}	-1.38	2.7×10^{-8}	-3.72	0.005	1.18×10^{-8}
EP Aqr	3.1×10^{-7}	-3.43	3.6×10^{-10}	-6.46	0.001	9.04×10^{-10}
IK Tau	4.5×10^{-6}	-1.53	1.4×10^{-7}	-3.02	0.032	1.39×10^{-8}
IRC+10011	1.9×10^{-5}	-0.65	3.7×10^{-7}	-2.35	0.020	7.37×10^{-8}
IRC+10216	1.6×10^{-6}	-1.74	9.2×10^{-8}	-2.99	0.057	1.69×10^{-8}
LP And	4.6×10^{-6}	-1.36	1.7×10^{-8}	-3.80	0.004	1.52×10^{-8}
NML Cyg	8.7×10^{-5}	-0.11	2.3×10^{-6}	-1.69	0.026	–
<i>o</i> Ceti	2.5×10^{-7}	-2.90	1.3×10^{-8}	-4.19	0.052	5.28×10^{-9}
R Cas	4.0×10^{-7}	-2.67	6.2×10^{-9}	-4.48	0.015	2.11×10^{-9}
R Leo	9.2×10^{-8}	-3.91	2.3×10^{-8}	-4.52	0.249	1.44×10^{-9}
RX Boo	3.6×10^{-7}	-2.94	2.5×10^{-9}	-5.10	0.007	1.11×10^{-9}
TX Cam	6.5×10^{-6}	-1.80	1.1×10^{-8}	-4.59	0.002	1.21×10^{-8}
U Hya	4.9×10^{-8}	-3.15	8.8×10^{-9}	-3.89	0.180	3.00×10^{-8}
W Aql	1.3×10^{-5}	-1.24	3.7×10^{-8}	-3.79	0.003	6.43×10^{-9}
W Hya	7.8×10^{-8}	-3.41	2.4×10^{-8}	-3.90	0.319	1.20×10^{-9}
IRC+10216	$2 - 4 \times 10^{-5(*)}$	-0.47	9.2×10^{-8}	-2.99	0.003	1.69×10^{-8}

The gas MLRs presented in column 2 (except *) are from [De Beck et al. \(2010\)](#). The gas MLR of * is from [Cernicharo et al. \(2014\)](#). The total gas and dust masses in column 3 and 5 are measured up to PACS $160\mu\text{m}$ $R_{3\sigma}$ radius given in table 2.3. The dust MLR is derived by dividing the total integrated dust mass by the age of the CSE at PACS $160\mu\text{m}$ $R_{3\sigma}$ radius.

Figure 2.3 Gas mass-loss rate vs. Dust mass-loss rate. Blue circles: O-rich AGB stars; Crimson stars: C-rich AGB stars; Green square: S-type AGB star; Maroon triangle: RSG; Orange dashed line: the accepted dust-to-gas ratio of 1/400 for C-rich sources; Blue dashed line: the accepted dust-to-gas ratio of 1/160 for O-rich sources.

The average dust-to-gas ratio measured for the combined sample of C-rich and O-rich is somewhat inconsistent with the canonical value of ~ 0.005 . We measure a dust-to-gas ratio of 0.011 ± 0.004 which is however close to the canonical value at lower limits. When sources (excluding the outlying sources) are grouped by their chemistry we find the resulting dust-to-gas ratios to be similar to their respective dust-to-gas ratios within uncertainties. The canonical C-rich dust-to-gas ratio of 0.003 measured by Knapp & Morris (1985) fall well within the uncertainty limits of the averaged C-rich dust-to-gas ratio of 0.004 ± 0.001 . Similarly, the Knapp & Morris (1985) O-rich dust-to-gas ratio of 0.007 is similar within error-bars to the averaged O-rich dust-to-gas ratio of 0.013 ± 0.005 .

While the average dust-to-gas ratios are somewhat consistent with their respective canonical values we also observe a significant scatter in our measured ratios, as shown by Fig. 2.3. This scatter is mainly due to the uncertainties in our measurements, particularly having to do with treating the CO mass-loss rate as constant, while we allow the dust mass-loss rate to be variable. It is also a result of the varying mass-loss, grain properties and chemistry of the sources. The difference between the two canonical ratios for C and O-rich chemistry is much smaller than the scatter in the measurements. Given the intrinsic difficulty in determining the dust-to-gas ratio, and the variation from source to source, it is hard to see that the existence of two distinct values for this ratio is justified, depending on chemistry, with such a small difference between them. We conclude that it is possible to study a total population using canonical values but such values can not be applied to individual sources.

When considering the outlying sources, IRC+10216, *o* Ceti, R Leo, U Hya and W Hya, they are all sources with complex envelopes and show clear dust mass-loss variations with time. The large variation seen in these sources and the range of ratios seen in the rest of the sample can be attributed to several reasons. Dissociation of CO could cause the gas mass measured to be significantly lower resulting in a larger than expected dust-to-gas ratio. This would particularly be a likely for sources with low MLRs. Alternatively, the De Beck et al. (2010) gas MLRs used is only a snapshot of the central present day gas MLR as they are derived from central position CO observations, thus lacking spatial

information. Further they are derived assuming uniform mass-loss. However as shown by Decin et al. (2007) and Cernicharo et al. (2015) gas mass-loss also varies with time. Considering these factors extrapolating a total gas mass from central position observations assuming uniform gas MLRs is difficult to justify.

Cernicharo et al. (2015) measured an averaged gas mass-loss rate of $2 - 4 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for IRC+10216 over a period of 10000 years using CO observations of the circumstellar shell and hence incorporating the spatial gas MLR variations. This average rate is ~ 20 times greater than the central position CO MLR measured by De Beck et al. (2012). Replacing the De Beck et al. (2010) MLR with this new MLR, we derive a new dust-to-gas ratio of 0.003, which is significantly lower than what was derived using the De Beck et al. (2010) MLR and closer to the canonical dust-to-gas ratio, further proving the importance of incorporation spatial information in these calculations. It must be noted that as described before, for sources with varying expansion velocities, MLRs and symmetries (eg: detached shell source U Hya), therefore there is no reason to expect the dust-to-gas ratios to be the canonical values. IRC+10216 is observed by Cernicharo et al. (2015) to expand with a nearly constant velocity. Combined with its spherical symmetry, this means it is reasonable to expect the overall dust-to-gas ratio to match that of the central region.

The above factors further emphasise the importance of not limiting observations of evolved stars to only the central point source, but instead to include spatial information on the source when aiming to obtain such measurements. This is the goal of a follow up study. By combining our measured dust MLRs with these new CO gas MLRs we can obtain a much more accurate and representative dust-to-gas ratio. Furthermore, the Nearby Evolved Stars Survey (NESS; Scicluna et al., *in prep.*) aims to obtain accurate CO gas MLRs by observing the extended circumstellar shell component of a volume-limited subset of its sample in low-J CO lines.

Another cause for the varying dust-to-gas ratios could be caused by the chosen $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$ used to derive the dust masses. As discussed in Sect. 2.3.2 varying κ_{eff} results in changes

to the Σ profile and hence the dust masses derived. For example, [Mennella et al. \(1998\)](#) observes a range of κ_{eff} where the upper limit is twice as large as the lower for amorphous Carbon laboratory measurements at $160\mu\text{m}$. Considering such a range in κ_{eff} our dust masses will vary by a factor of two.

We measure dust mass-loss rates ranging from $3.6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ M}_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ to $2.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the total sample with a standard deviation of $5.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. We derive the dust MLRs using the GRAMS fitter for this sample and find that the dust MLRs measured by us are on average greater than the GRAMS dust MLRs. This deviation is due to GRAMS being biased by the mid-IR spectrum and therefore measuring only a very small fraction of the total dust mass. By fitting the mid-IR spectrum we are only sensitive to the hot inner region of the source and thereby we disregard the outer circumstellar shell component and only very weakly constraining and underestimating the total dust mass. Further this deviation provides possible evidence for the presence of an additional cold dust component unaccounted for by the GRAMS fitter results and which should be included when deriving more accurate dust MLRs in evolved stars.

When comparing the dust masses we derive to the results from [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) for IRC+10011, *o* Ceti and IRC+10216 we find that our dust masses are decidedly larger by factors of 26, 60 and 86 respectively. This is the result of several factors. The primary reason of this large difference is the deviation between $\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$ values used by us and [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) as discussed in Sect. 2.3.2. Further [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) uses a fixed outer radius of 10^3 times the inner radius which is approximately 30 and 4.7 times smaller than the $R_{3\sigma}$ radii used by us as the outer for IRC+10216 and IRC+10011 respectively. This will result in a lower dust mass estimation by [Ladjal et al. \(2010\)](#) when compared to our measured results.

2.5 Summary

We observed a sample of 14 AGB stars and one RSG using SCUBA-2 at $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ and combined these observations with published *Herschel* PACS data to study their dust mass-loss histories. By analysing the radial surface brightness and residual profiles we infer the variation of the dust properties of the circumstellar shell with radii and hence time.

The PACS observations show extended emission at both wavelengths: At $70\mu\text{m}$ we observe extended emission at 3σ brightness levels from 0.04 pc to 0.74 pc averaging at 0.16 ± 0.04 pc. The observations allowed us to observe the mass-loss histories up to an average of 9000 ± 1100 years, ranging from 4500 – 21800 years. At $160\mu\text{m}$ $R_{3\sigma}$ and look-back time averaged 0.011 ± 0.02 pc and 6500 ± 1000 years respectively. At both PACS wavelengths, the circumstellar shell structure and extended emission we measured are consistent with the results from [Cox et al. \(2012\)](#).

The sources are typically marginally resolved in the SCUBA-2 observations. The $R_{3\sigma}$ at $850\mu\text{m}$ ranged from 0.004 pc – 0.11 pc, averaging 0.04 ± 0.01 pc. Despite the small $\theta_{3\sigma}$ extents we found a significant fraction of the total stellar flux was within the extended component: $\sim (63 \pm 0.02)\%$ of the total flux at $450\mu\text{m}$ and $\sim (55.0 \pm 0.03)\%$ of the total flux at $850\mu\text{m}$ is within found to be in the extended component.

Outwards of the SCUBA-2 3σ radius, β is prior dominated and flattens out 1.95 ± 0.01 . As this value is consistent with that of the ISM prior used we see no evidence for deviations from the interstellar grain properties in our β profiles.

All radial temperature profiles show a flattening out when the temperature has dropped to $\sim 37 \pm 3$ K, which occurs at the point where the dust is heated in equal amounts by the central sources and the ISRF. Therefore we estimate the ISRF begins dominating at $\sim 3300 \pm 500$ years for our sample.

As we expect these AGB stars to all experience roughly the same uniform ISRF, the column that is affected by the ISRF, in terms of e.g. dust heating, is comparable for each object. Therefore the transition radius could be used as another measure of the region of influence of the AGB star.

The Σ profiles of all 15 sources deviate decidedly from the uniform (or constant) mass-loss case over the past $\sim 10,000$ years. Ten sources show an overall less steep Σ gradient compared to that of Σ_{um} indicating that their MLRs decreased as the sources evolved. Density enhancements seen in the Σ profiles correspond to circumstellar shell features of several sources, such as the detached shell of U Hya and the denser eastern circumstellar shell region of W Aql. We estimate a time scale of $\sim 7400 \pm 1000$ years on which large scale MLR variations took place in our sample.

The β profile of IRC+10216 show a negative gradient before prior domination. The likely scenario for this feature is the variation of dust grain sizes and properties in this region hence indicating their evolution with time and radius. The Σ profile of this AGB star indicates an increasing MLR as the star evolves differing from majority of the sources in our sample.

We see clear evidence for the detached shell of U Hya between 0.05 pc – 0.13 pc. The detached shell is measured to be 0.08 pc in width which is consistent with previous studies. We estimate the thermal pulse which resulted in the detached shell occurred $\sim 14000 - 15000$ years ago.

The derived dust-to-gas ratios showed a large amount of scatter around the canonical values for C-rich and O-rich outflows, in part due to uncertainties in our measurements where we have treated the CO mass-loss rate as constant, while allowing the dust mass-loss rate to be variable. It is important to note that the difference between the canonical values for the C-rich and O-rich chemistry is smaller than the scatter seen within our sample. Therefore we conclude that it is possible to study a total population using canonical values however, they can not be applied to individual sources. Additionally, these results emphasise the need to take into considerations the total source including the extended

regions hence the importance of the spatial information of a source when deriving such measurements. Further this also show that extending the central, present day dust-to-gas ratio to the outer older circumstellar shell regions is in general not feasible, especially in the case of sources with large scale circumstellar shell structure and MLR variations.

Chapter 3

The Nearby Evolved Stars Survey: I. JCMT/SCUBA-2 Sub-millimetre detection of the detached shell of U Antliae

The work in this chapter has been submitted for refereeing to MNRAS under the title The Nearby Evolved Stars Survey: I. JCMT/SCUBA-2 Sub-millimetre detection of the detached shell of U Antliae. The work in this chapter is fully reproducible and the scripts and data required to reproduce this analysis, figures and tables can be downloaded from https://github.com/Thavisha/UAnt_DetachedShell.

Abstract

We present the highest resolution single-dish submillimetre observations of the detached shell source U Antliae to date. The observations were obtained at 450 μm and 850 μm with SCUBA-2 instrument on the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope as part of the Nearby Evolved Stars Survey. The emission at 850 μm peaks at 40'' with hints of a second peak seen at $\sim 20''$. The emission can be traced out to a radius of 56'' at a 3σ level. The outer peak observed at 850 μm aligns well with the peak observed at Herschel/PACS wavelengths. The spectral index of dust emissivity is shown to vary radially indicating changes in grain properties. Combining these results along with radiative transfer modelling of multiple scenarios for the structure of the shell, we suggest the detached shell of U Ant to be that of a single extended shell with

substructure of a different grain composition. Projection effects causes the substructure to appear close to the central star, giving rise to the inner peak at 850 μm . Using radial point-to-point SED fitting we determine a total shell dust mass of $(2.0 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ and established that the thermal pulse which gave rise to the detached shell occurred 3500 ± 500 years ago.

3.1 Introduction

In the final stages of stellar evolution stars expel their outer layers enriched with the products of nucleosynthesis into the interstellar medium (ISM). For intermediate-mass stars ($1M_{\odot} \leq M \leq 8M_{\odot}$), the majority of this mass loss occurs while on the Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) in a pulsation-enhanced, radiation-pressure driven wind (Höfner & Olofsson, 2018).

AGB stars are often treated as quasi-stable systems, without incorporating treatment of their evolution, while their winds are treated as spatially and temporally homogeneous outflows. The existence of complex structures such as elongations, detached shells and bipolar outflows (Zijlstra et al., 2001, Olofsson et al., 2010, Ramstedt et al., 2011, Cox et al., 2012, Maercker et al., 2012), indicates that the true mass-loss mechanisms are far more complex than commonly inferred. Particularly uncertain is the extent to which the stellar wind is enhanced in mass and/or momentum when the star undergoes a thermal pulse (He-shell flash). Thus, further observational constraints are required before we can statistically model mass loss from AGB stars accurately. By studying the extended dust emission and comparing it to constant-outflow models and detailed numerical simulations (e.g Bowen & Willson, 1991, Höfner, 2008), we can study the properties of this non-uniformity and accurately determine time-variant mass-loss and dust-production rates and establish the properties of the grains that enter the ISM.

Of the variety of structures shown by AGB envelopes, detached dust shells are among the most striking features. They are thought to result from a period of strong mass loss due to a thermal pulse, during which the star may expand and brighten dramatically for a

few centuries (Willems & de Jong, 1988, Vassiliadis & Wood, 1994, Marigo et al., 2017). According to evolution model predictions (e.g., Mattsson et al., 2007) the mass-loss rate during the thermal pulse is more than an order of magnitude greater than before the thermal pulse, mainly driven by the temporal increase in luminosity. A faster wind speed during this period means that the older, slower wind in front of the density-enhanced wind piles up at the shock interface into a shell (Mattsson et al., 2007). Such a detached shell source would be observed as a nearly symmetrical ring of gas and dust surrounding a near empty region around the star (Zijlstra et al., 2001, Schöier et al., 2005).

Similar morphologies have been observed in a number of objects (e.g. Olofsson et al., 1988, 1990, Izumiura et al., 1996, 1997, 2011). After the thermal pulse the star's luminosity rapidly diminishes to below pre-pulse levels, and then gradually recovers. This would have led to a drop in mass-loss rate and wind speed soon after the increase in both of these quantities (Steffen & Schönberner, 2000). Because the effect of luminosity on mass-loss rate is greater than that on wind speed (e.g., Eriksson et al., 2014, Goldman et al., 2017), this reversal exacerbates the contrast in wind density in the wake of the shell.

U Antliae is a C-rich AGB star located at a distance of 268 ± 39 pc (van Leeuwen, 2007). It is surrounded by a well-defined detached shell, estimated to have been expelled by the star ~ 2800 years ago (Kerschbaum et al., 2010). Independent scattered-light, ^{12}CO low-J rotational line emission, mid-IR and far-IR observations of U Ant all show radically different structure, making this source rather unique. We summarise the published results in Table C.1 in the appendix and a schematic diagram showing their mean shell radii and FWHMs in Fig. C.1.

Optical scattered-light observations by González Delgado et al. (2001, 2003) show the detached shell separated into four sub-shells at $\sim 25''$, $37''$, $43''$ and $46''$ from the star (hereafter ss1, ss2, ss3, ss4), with the innermost two shells only tentative detections. They derive shell widths of $\sim 3''$, $\sim 6''$, $\sim 3''$ and $\sim 10''$ for ss1, ss2, ss3 and ss4 respectively. These authors find ss3 to be dominated by line-scattered light (i.e. resonance scattered

light) instead of dust-scattered light indicating that ss3 is dominated by gas instead of dust.

Similarly, as shown by the schematic diagram presented in Appendix C, [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) also observed ss3 and ss4 in optical scattered light at $\sim 43''$ and $\sim 50''$ with shell widths of $\sim 2''$ and $\sim 7''$. They find ss3 appearing to be fainter in dust-scattered light and brighter in line-scattered light reaching the same conclusion that ss3 is most-likely dominated by gas. The authors also observe peaks at the positions of ss1 and ss2 in their azimuthally-averaged surface-brightness profiles. While these peaks could be indeed due to the ss1 and ss2, the authors argue that they are more likely due to substructure of ss3 and ss4 projected towards the inner regions of the detached shell. Mid-IR and far-IR observations from AKARI show that the surface brightness peaks at $\sim 41''$ ([Arimatsu et al., 2011](#)). However, they assume the double shell model (including peak radii and FWHMs) presented in [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) when analysing their data. [Izumiura et al. \(1997\)](#) et al., suggest the presence of two shells at $\sim 46''$ and $\sim 3'$ based on IRAS images. The latter has not been recovered by any other observations to date.

Adding to the curious nature of this detached shell, far-IR observations from Herschel/PACS appear to be dominated by ss3, peaking at $40''$ ([Kerschbaum et al., 2010](#), [Cox et al., 2012](#)). As described, in all other instances ss3 is observed to have very faint emission in dust continuum but very bright in gas emission.

The azimuthally averaged surface-brightness profile of the APEX $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ observation derived by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) clearly peaks at the location of ss3 and has a measured shell width of $\sim 2.6''$. Prior to this [Olofsson et al. \(1996\)](#) also detected the gas shell in CO (1-0), (2-1) and (3-2), albeit at much lower resolutions, at $41''$ (width = $13''$). High spatial resolution ($1.5''$) ALMA $^{12}\text{CO}(2-1)$ and (1-0) observations by [Kerschbaum et al. \(2017\)](#) also only detect a single CO gas shell coinciding well with ss3. The CO shell is located at $42.5''$ from the central source and has a measured width of $\sim 5''$. The ALMA observations also show filamentary sub-structure within the gas shell.

Based on these observations at multiple wavelengths in both gas and dust it has been suggested that ss1, ss2 and ss4 are gas poor hence only visible in the dust continuum. Sub-shell 3 deviates from the others and is suggested to be gas dominated ([Maercker et al., 2010](#), [Kerschbaum et al., 2017](#)).

As mentioned above, [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) suggest that ss3 and ss4 are real, while ss1 and ss2 are filamentary substructures of ss3 and ss4 projected against the inner regions of the detached shell. They show that the small distance between ss3 and ss4 and the corresponding time scales (~ 110 yrs) suggest that these sub-shells could not have occurred due to multiple thermal pulses. The most likely scenario is a single thermal pulse ~ 2800 yrs ago gave rise to the detached shell following which a secondary mechanism shaped the single detached shell into the multiple sub-shells observed.

A model for multiple shell formation in AGB and post-AGB stars was proposed by [Simis et al. \(2001\)](#). They suggest alternating dust and gas shells 200 – 400 years apart formed as a result of dust and gas decoupling. In a similar vein for U Ant, [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) proposed the splitting of a single detached shell (located at the position of ss3) into two is an effect of gas-grain decoupling due to varying expansion velocities, resulting in a single, gas-rich sub-shell and a dust component at larger radii due to the higher expansion velocity. In this scenario the gas velocity slows down in the wind collision region while the dust sails through.

Should ss1 and ss2 be real, an as-of-yet unknown mechanism is required to explain their formation. One possibility is that instabilities at the interaction between the fast and slow winds may have created multiple shock fronts with dust decoupling in the swept back shock, resulting in ss1 and ss2 ([González Delgado et al., 2001](#), [Schöier et al., 2005](#), [Kerschbaum et al., 2017](#)). The presence of filamentary structure in the gas-rich shell in the ALMA observation by [Kerschbaum et al. \(2017\)](#) provides evidence for a reverse shock. Another is that these shells could be a result of density and velocity modulations which took place during the thermal pulse ([Villaver et al., 2002](#), [Maercker et al., 2010](#)).

While U Ant is well studied from the optical to the far-IR, only a few sub-mm continuum observations of the source exists. Archival observations obtained using the JCMT/SCUBA instrument (the predecessor to SCUBA-2) in 1997 (PI: Greaves) were never published until now, and do not clearly show the detached shell due to a low signal-to-noise ratio (see Appendix F). U Ant was also part of a sample of three detached shell sources studied by Maercker et al. (2018) at 870 μm using APEX/LABOCA. The authors report a sub-mm excess in the detached shell when comparing the observed fluxes to the output from radiative transfer models derived by combining data from the optical to the far-IR and extrapolating to the sub-mm. They measure an excess which is 2.3 ± 0.3 times greater than the model predictions.

In this chapter we present the highest angular-resolution ($13''$) submillimetre dust continuum detection of the detached shell of U Ant to date. The observation was obtained with the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope's (JCMT) Sub-millimetre Common-User Bolometer Array 2 (SCUBA-2; Holland et al., 2013) instrument, as part of the Nearby Evolved Stars Survey (NESS; Scicluna et al., *in prep.*).

Using this new sub-mm data, combined with archival Herschel/PACS data we study the dust properties and masses in this unique detached shell source. The analysis is carried out with the aim of reconciling the differences seen in the various types of observations. Using radiative transfer modelling we will evaluate whether our observations are consistent with the dust distribution over the multiple sub-shells as reported in the past.

3.2 Observations and Data Reduction

U Ant was observed on 18th of January 2018 as part of NESS (program ID: M17BL002) with SCUBA-2 on the JCMT. The observations were carried out at 450 μm (beam FWHM = $7.9''$) and 850 μm (beam FWHM = $13''$) using the CV-daisy scan pattern. The total observing time was 2.1 hours broken into four repeats.

The data were reduced using the modified SCUBA-2 pipeline presented in [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#) via Starlink ([Currie et al., 2014](#)) version 2018A. In general SCUBA-2 pipelines are built to handle bright point sources such as quasars or large extended structure such as molecular clouds. Compared to these evolved star circumstellar emission in the sub-mm is only marginally extended, leading to standard pipelines being unable to recover the circumstellar emission efficiently. Therefore in [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#) we developed a modified pipeline which can recover the marginally extended faint circumstellar emission optimally while suppressing artefacts.

3.2.1 Removing CO(3-2) Contamination

The wide bandwidth of the SCUBA-2 instrument (790 μm – 940 μm) contains the frequency of the CO(3-2) rotational transition. If this transition is strong enough, it may contaminate measurements of the continuum flux¹ ([Drabek et al., 2012](#)). Therefore we carry out ¹²CO(3-2) subtraction on our SCUBA-2 850 μm observation. A full description of the methodology used to carry out this subtraction is presented in appendix D.

We find a $\sim 30\%$ reduction in 850 μm flux when the subtraction is carried out. This is on the upper end of the range reported by [Drabek et al. \(2012\)](#) when extreme cases are excluded. In the analysis to follow we use the ¹²CO(3-2) subtracted SCUBA-2 850 μm observation.

3.2.2 Archival Herschel observations

We combine the SCUBA-2 observations with Herschel/PACS 70 μm and 160 μm imaging observations of U Ant as part of our analysis (FWHMs of 5.46×5.76 and 10.65×12.13 respectively). These data are a part of the Mass-loss of Evolved StarS (MESS) program ([Groenewegen et al., 2011](#)) and are publicly available for download via the Herschel Science

¹<https://www.eaoobservatory.org/jcmt/instrumentation/continuum/scuba-2/contamination/>

Archive². Here we use the Level 2.5 reduced products, the highest available pipeline-reduced data products calibrated using PACS calibration version *PACS_CAL_77.0*.

In addition to Herschel/PACS data we utilised the Herschel/SPIRE data from the MESS survey. The SPIRE beam FWHMs are 18'' at 250 μm , 24'' at 350 μm , and 42'' at 500 μm , therefore the resolution of SCUBA-2 even at 850 μm is at least a factor of 1.5 better. As the primary goal of this project is to analyse the sub-mm emission from the detached shell of U Ant, in order to preserve the SCUBA-2 resolutions we opt to not include the SPIRE data when carrying out spatial observational analysis. Therefore, we only use the SPIRE data for the SED analysis when carrying out radiative transfer modelling in Sec. 3.3.2.2.

3.3 Analysis and Results

3.3.1 Surface-brightness Profiles

The SCUBA-2 450 μm map has an RMS of 0.24 mJy arcsec⁻² and a pixel size of 2'' (see Fig. 3.1(a)). Presented in Fig. 3.1(b), the final CO subtracted 850 μm map has an RMS of 0.02 mJy arcsec⁻² and a pixel size of 4''. The 850 μm image clearly shows a circumstellar envelope (CSE) extending over the full region of the detached shell of U Ant.

We derive the surface-brightness and PSF-subtracted residual profiles using the methods described in Dharmawardena et al. (2018) (see Fig. 3.2).

The uncertainties on the residual profiles are the quadrature sum of the fractional uncertainty on the PSF and the uncertainty on the radial profile:

$$\sigma_{res}^2 = \sigma_{SB}^2 + \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{PSF}}{F_{PSF}}(r = 0) \right) F_{PSF} \right]^2, \quad (3.1)$$

²<http://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/herschel/science-archive>

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.1 (a) $450\ \mu\text{m}$ observation of U Ant (1 pix = $2''$); (b) CO (3-2) subtracted $850\ \mu\text{m}$ observation of U Ant (1 pix = $4''$). Dashed white circle: 3σ surface-brightness extent ($56''$) at $850\ \mu\text{m}$. Filled white circle in the bottom left corner: SCUBA-2 beam ($450\ \mu\text{m}$ beam FWHM = $7.9''$ and $850\ \mu\text{m}$ beam FWHM = $13''$)

where σ_{res} is the uncertainty on the residual profile, σ_{SB} is the uncertainty on the surface brightness profile and σ_{PSF} is the uncertainty on the PSF after it is scaled to the central peak pixel. The fractional uncertainty on the PSF (i.e. $\frac{\sigma_{PSF}}{F_{PSF}}(r = 0)$) is equal to the fractional uncertainty on the peak of the radial profile to which the PSF is scaled. The shape of the SCUBA-2 PSF is well known, therefore no significant uncertainty arises due its shape. As we align the PSF with 0.1 pixel precision, any effects due to misalignment are negligible.

The 850 μm residual profile show a broad peak centred at 40". We also observe hints of an additional inner peak centred at $\sim 20''$. The outer maximum corresponds well to their Herschel/PACS counterparts. The 850 μm residual profile has a surface-brightness extent of 56" (0.07 ± 0.01 pc) at 3σ detection limit ($R_{3\sigma}$), which is comparable to the $R_{3\sigma}$ we measure at both Herschel/PACS wavelengths.

The 450 μm profiles shows hints of emission from the detached shell once again at $\sim 40''$. However, the low signal-to-noise of the observation limits our ability to constrain this emission any further.

Background-subtracted total fluxes (central source + extended component: F_{total}) at 450 μm and 850 μm were measured to be 435 ± 70 mJy and 199 ± 34 mJy respectively. Fluxes at both wavelengths are derived using an aperture of 56" ($R_{3\sigma}$ at 850 μm) and a sky annulus from 80" to 120". The PSF-subtracted (or extended) component of the CSE accounts for 80% of the total flux at 850 μm .

3.3.2 Shell Modelling

We carry out two sets of modelling in order to discern the detached-shell properties of U Ant in a step-by-step manner. The first of these interprets the extended emission observed in the far-IR and sub-mm in isolation (further described in Sec.3.3.2.1). Here we fit the four-point Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) at each radial point of the extended circumstellar envelope derived by combining the residual profiles (following the subtraction

Figure 3.2 Surface-brightness and residual profiles of U Ant. Left hand panels: The blue dashed lines represent the source surface-brightness profiles and the grey solid lines represent the PSF profile of the instrument at the given wavelength; Right hand panels: The orange lines represents the PSF subtracted residual profiles for each wavelength.

of the central point sources) at each of the four wavelengths. By fitting the thermal dust emission of the extended CSE at each radial point we derive the dust Temperature (T), Spectral index of dust emissivity (β) and dust mass column density (Σ).

Second, we carry out self-consistent radiative-transfer modelling of the entire system, i.e. star + shell (further described in Sec. 3.3.2.2). We do this in an attempt to compare structures suggested in the literature to the global SED and far-IR and sub-mm extended emission and potentially exclude some scenarios due to incompatibility with our observations of U Ant.

3.3.2.1 Radial point-to-point Spectral Energy Distribution Fitting

By combining all four residual profiles we derive the Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs) at each radial point. These SEDs are fitted with a single-temperature blackbody model modified by an effective emissivity law (e.g., Hildebrand, 1983, Gordon et al., 2014) using the method presented in Sec .3.2 of Dharmawardena et al. (2018). This results in radial profiles for the dust T , β and Σ .

As with Dharmawardena et al. (2018), the input dust model consists of a mixture of 90% amorphous carbon (optical constants from Zubko et al. 1996) and 10% silicon carbide (optical constants from Pégourié 1988). The grain size distribution is as prescribed by Kim et al. (1994) (a power-law with an exponential falloff); where we use a minimum grain size of $0.01 \mu\text{m}$ and an exponential scale factor of $1 \mu\text{m}$, with a power-law slope of -3.5 . This results in an effective emissivity at $160\mu\text{m}$ ($\kappa_{\text{eff},160}^S$) of $26 \text{ cm}^2\text{g}^{-1}$. We use this same dust model in the analysis throughout the entire chapter in order to ensure consistency between the different types of modelling carried out.

The fitting is performed with the python package EMCEE, (Foreman-Mackey et al., 2013), which uses affine-invariant Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms to carry out Bayesian inference on the SEDs to the specified model, and find the most probable value for each parameter at every radial point. The 1σ uncertainties of the profiles are the central 68% of the samples with the median being used as the estimator.

We made several modifications to the SED fitting MCMC code presented by Dharmawardena et al. (2018) to suit this analysis. In particular, the limits in the T prior are set to $20 \text{ K} < T < 300 \text{ K}$, with the inner temperature set to 1800 K . The β limits are set to be $\beta > 1$. We find these modifications allow for better converged results for U Ant.

As described in Sec. 4.2 of Dharmawardena et al. (2018), the curvature of the fitted modified blackbody depends on both β and T . The temperature is constrained by the peak of the SED at each individual radial point, thus by the Wien end of the SED (Shetty et al., 2009). Hence the T profile is constrained by the far-IR PACS detections. The β

profile is constrained by the longer wavelength ($\lambda \geq 300\mu\text{m}$) SCUBA-2 detections as it describes the Rayleigh-Jeans tail of the SED (Doty & Leung, 1994, Shetty et al., 2009, Sadavoy et al., 2013). The Σ profile is constrained by either the PACS or the SCUBA-2 detections.

There is a known anti-correlation between T and β in all three-parameter modified black-body models and the best way to overcome this degeneracy is to employ hierarchical Bayesian inference (Kelly et al., 2012). However as we lack the required sample size to carry out hierarchical Bayesian inference we use an informative prior on β (probability distribution function of β observed in M31). While it can not completely remove the degeneracy, it helps to minimise its impact.

The resulting T , β and Σ profiles are presented in Figure 3.3. By integrating over the Σ profile from $12''$ to $56''$ we derive a total dust mass of $(2.0 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ in the detached shell. This mass is assumed to be constant throughout the rest of this chapter. This assumption may have an impact on the model SEDs and surface brightness profiles in Sec. 3.3.2.2, but the very low optical depth of the shell means the effects will be negligible

3.3.2.2 Full Radiative Transfer Modelling

In order to qualitatively determine the location of the far-IR/sub-mm dust emission we generate models using the python radiative-transfer package HYPERION (Robitaille, 2011). We compare the resulting model SEDs to the observed global SED of U Ant from optical to sub-mm (see Table E.1 in the appendix). Further, we qualitatively compare the resulting surface-brightness profiles to those derived from the SCUBA-2 and PACS observation. The best fit model SEDs and surface-brightness profiles allow us to narrow down the most likely CSE structure of U Ant.

We choose six different model scenarios based on our observations and past literature reports. Since four distinct sub-shells have been reported we have experimented with scenarios that put all of the dust that we have measured in the radial SED fitting (Sec. 3.3.2.1)

Figure 3.3 SED fitting results of U Ant; Top: Temperature (T) radial profile of U Ant; Middle: Dust mass column density (Σ) radial profile. Orange dashed line represents the expected dust mass column density for a uniform mass-loss rate; Bottom: The spectral index of dust emissivity (β) profile of U Ant.

in one of each of these shells. For the fourth shell, two different radii were reported by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Kerschbaum et al. \(2010\)](#) using dust continuum observations. Therefore in total we arrive at five distinct model scenarios: Mss1; Mss2; Mss3, Mss4-M2010; Mss4-K2010. A sixth scenario sees all dust distributed between the four sub-shells with the mass distribution determined from literature (Mfourshells; [González Delgado et al., 2001, 2003, Maercker et al., 2010, Maercker et al., 2018](#)). The input parameters for the individual models are presented in Table 3.1. While the detached shell has an expansion velocity of 20.5 km s^{-1} ([De Beck et al., 2010](#)) we do not use this as input parameter as we have placed the sub-shells in their correct positions our static models.

In the case of U Ant, the angular resolution of the JCMT/SCUBA-2 at $850 \mu\text{m}$ is comparable to the distance between the innermost and the outermost sub-shells. Therefore we are only able to test the extreme scenarios presented above. Further exploration of the distribution of dust and finer shell structure is not informative as we are unable to meaningfully constrain the free parameters.

Table 3.1 Input parameters for individual models

Model	Sub-shell	Shell Radius	% of total dust mass
Mss1	ss1	$23.5'' - 26.5''$	100%
Mss2	ss2	$34'' - 40''$	100%
Mss3	ss3	$41.5'' - 44.5''$	100%
Mss4-M2010	ss4	$46.5'' - 53.5''$	100%
Mss4-K2010	ss4	$34'' - 46''$	100%
Mfourshells	ss1	$23.5'' - 26.5''$	22.5%
	ss2	$34'' - 40''$	22.5%
	ss3	$41.5'' - 44.5''$	5%
	ss4	$46.5'' - 53.5''$	50%

To derive the appropriate input synthetic stellar photosphere and its parameters required as input to Hyperion (e.g., stellar luminosity and effective temperature) we fit the observed global SED of U Ant from optical – mid-IR ($0.5 - 10 \mu\text{m}$) to the COMARCS stellar photosphere model grid (Aringer et al., 2009). Past reports have found that the optical depth of the detached shell of U Ant is very low from optical – sub-mm (e.g., Kerschbaum et al., 2010) confirming that the optical – mid-IR SED of U Ant is unaffected by the detached shell. Therefore the parameters derived are also unaffected by the detached shell, with the central stellar emission dominating in this wavelength range.

The input parameters to all models are as follows:

- Total shell mass: $(2.0 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ (see Sec. 3.3.2.1);
- Expansion velocity of present day mass loss: 4.5 km s^{-1} (Kerschbaum et al., 2017);
- An inverse-square dust density distribution in the detached shell/sub-shells.
- Stellar luminosity: $7000 L_{\odot}$;

- Stellar effective temperature: 2600 K;
- stellar surface gravity: $\log(g [\text{cm s}^{-2}]) = -0.5$;

The synthetic stellar photosphere parameters derived are consistent with the study by [Di Criscienzo et al. \(2016\)](#), who find that stars of metallicities typical of the solar neighbourhood, and mass in the range $1.2 - 2 M_{\odot}$, reach the C-star stage with luminosities and temperatures similar to the best-fit parameters given above (see Fig.6 in [Di Criscienzo et al. \(2016\)](#)).

We use the same dust composition as described in Sec. 3.3.2.1. We do not include an underlying contribution from mass-loss pre and post thermal pulse. The COMARCS model provides a good fit to the optical – mid-IR component of the observed global SED, implying that the present day mass-loss provides virtually no contribution to the thermal dust emission.

The resultant model SEDs are plotted along with the observed SED in Fig 3.4. The model surface-brightness profiles at each wavelength are shown along with the observed surface-brightness profiles in Fig 3.5. The chi-squared values per observed data point (χ_p^2) of the models when compared to both the observed SED and surface-brightness profiles are presented in Tab. 3.2.

Table 3.2 χ_p^2 comparison between modelled and observed SED and surface brightness profiles.

Model	SED	Surface Brightness Profiles χ_p^2			
	χ_p^2	70 μm	160 μm	450 μm	850 μm
Mss1	20596	6635	111	1	16
Mss2	2259	610	21	1	18
Mss3	635	148	15	1	19
Mss4-M2010	687	258	19	1	19
Mss4-K2010	1224	297	16	1	18
Mfourshells	1722	569	21	1	18

Figure 3.4 Comparison of model SEDs (synthetic photometry points connected by lines) with the observed SED (see Table E.1). Black dots: observed SED; Grey dotted line: COMARCS model; Bright green dots: SCUBA-2 points; Dark green line: Mss1; Violet line: Mss2; Light green line: Mss3; Red line: Mss3-M2010; Gold line: Mss3-K2010; Blue line: Mfourshells.

3.4 Discussion

3.4.1 Surface-brightness emission

We find that approximately 80% of the total flux is emitted from the extended component in all four of the PACS and SCUBA-2 observations (see Sec. 3.3.1). This result is $\sim 25\%$ larger than the average reported in Dharmawardena et al. (2018), as expected for a bright detached shell source.

Figure 3.5 Comparison of model surface-brightness profiles with the observed. The legend shown in the SCUBA-2 450 μm panel applies to all other panels too. From top to bottom the plots show 70 μm , 160 μm , 450 μm and 850 μm respectively. Black dots: Observed surface-brightness profiles; Dark green line: Mss1; Violet line: Mss2; Light green line: Mss3; Red line: Mss3-M2010; Gold line: Mss-K2010; Blue line: Mfourshells.

The peaks at 70 μm , 160 μm and the outer peak at 850 μm align well at 40'', despite the large difference in resolution, and match the weak emission at 450 μm . Additionally, [Kerschbaum et al. \(2010\)](#) report the same peak intensity radius, also using the Herschel/-PACS observations from the MESS survey. Interestingly, none of the scattered-light peaks

correspond to this result. This far-IR/sub-mm peak is located between ss2 and ss3. Further, the inner broad peak observed only at 850 μm also does not correspond to any one of the scattered light sub-shells and is located interior to ss1.

The aligned peaks in the SCUBA-2 and PACS profiles seen in Fig. 3.2 point towards the presence of a single dust shell, with a far-IR/sub-mm peak at $\sim 40''$. We expect the peak is somewhat smeared by the beam sizes of the corresponding instruments. Such a single dust shell is consistent with the single gas-rich shell reported by [Kerschbaum et al. \(2017\)](#) using ALMA observations. [Kerschbaum et al. \(2017\)](#) suggests the gas-rich shell to have strong gas and dust coupling resulting in the peaks observed in both the CO observations and dust continuum observations.

However we note another reason for the lack of distinct sub-shells could be the resolution of our observations. The separation between sub-shells is comparable to the FWHM of the SCUBA-2 beam ($13''$) resulting in the merging of shells in the observation. Nevertheless, if this were the case the multiple sub-shells should most likely have been visible in the Herschel/PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ observations which has a much smaller beam size of $6''$, the approximate width of the shells in scattered light.

A naive interpretation of the additional peak in the residual profile at 850 μm compared to shorter wavelengths would be that the 850 μm observation is sensitive to an additional component of cold dust in the inner region. This is unlikely as the dust temperatures required for such a component is expected to be ~ 4 K, from Wien's law. Normally we expect the dust closer to the central star to be warmer, contrary to what we observe. In order for warmer dust to contribute more to the emission at 850 μm than at 70 μm and 160 μm it must have significantly different dust properties. In this case, larger or more amorphous grains may be preferentially located in the inner ejecta, enhancing the sub-mm emission from this region. For example the results in ([Testi et al., 2014](#)) suggest $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$ or larger grains are required to reproduce the small β values observed in Sec. 3.4.2, which if present are expected to be a minor contribution to the grain size distribution in AGB

outflows. Should larger or more amorphous grains be the case we should see evidence for such grains in either the T or β profiles presented in Sec. 3.4.2, which we do not.

Following this, the inner brightness peak at $850\ \mu\text{m}$ is most likely a result of projection effects due to emission from filament-like/clumpy substructure within the single shell, resulting in discernible structure in the inner region of the CSE when projected against the plane of the sky. This is consistent with suggestions by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) and the gaseous filamentary structure observed in past ALMA observations ([Kerschbaum et al., 2017](#)). The substructure likely possesses different grain properties to that of the overall average detached shell, hence causing it to appear only at $850\ \mu\text{m}$ and not at the PACS wavelengths. We discuss this further in Sec. 3.4.2 by analysing the T , Σ and β profiles.

$R_{3\sigma}$ at $850\ \mu\text{m}$ ($56''$) coincides well with the outer edge of ss4 detected by [González Delgado et al. \(2001, 2003\)](#) and [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) in scattered light. This is also consistent with the outer-most shell in mid-IR previously reported by [Arimatsu et al. \(2011\)](#). This radius lies within the interquartile range measured for the sample of fifteen evolved stars by [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#).

Assuming a detached-shell expansion velocity of $20.5\ \text{km s}^{-1}$ ([De Beck et al., 2010](#)) and a distance of $268 \pm 39\ \text{pc}$ ([van Leeuwen, 2007](#)), we trace the circumstellar shell out to a look-back age of $3500 \pm 500\ \text{yr}$ at $850\ \mu\text{m}$ at the 3σ level. This age is comparable to the ages obtained by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Kerschbaum et al. \(2017\)](#).

3.4.2 Radial variation in dust properties

In Figure 3.3 we present the T , Σ and β SED fitting results calculated using EMCEE. The innermost $\sim 10''$ region of all three profiles is compromised by PSF-subtraction effects on the residual profile, and are therefore not included in the analysis or the figure.

All three profiles are well constrained from $12'' - 56''$, i.e. up to the $R_{3\sigma}$ radius at $850\ \mu\text{m}$. The temperature profile peaks at $40''$, aligning well with the peaks observed in surface-brightness residual profiles. The overall weighted-averaged temperature is $54 \pm 2\ \text{K}$ within

the region with constraints. The weighted-average dust temperature of the shell agrees well with the dust temperature reported in [Schöier et al. \(2005\)](#) using radiative transfer modelling. The temperature is also consistent with that expected for dust grain heating by the interstellar radiation field (ISRF). This suggests grains in this regions are heated by the same uniform ISRF and hence possess a similar temperature, giving rise to a single-temperature dust component.

As shown by the middle panel in [Fig. 3.3](#), the radial variation of Σ clearly deviates from the uniform and constant mass-loss model³ overlaid in brown. From $\sim 12'' - 56''$ the Σ profile follows an overall flat profile with no discernible peaks to indicate the presence of the detached shell. This could be due to interference of the substructure within the detached shell. Line-of-sight confusion – a result of the substructure – could cause the dust mass to appear spread evenly throughout the CSE when using this method. Therefore while we are able to estimate the outer radius of the detached shell using these parameter profiles, we are unable to identify the inner region. We see a sharp decrease in Σ following this, indicating that approximately 3500 ± 500 ago there was an event of high mass injection to the CSE, i.e. the thermal pulse which gave rise to the detached shell.

The integrated dust mass from $12'' - 56''$, $(2.0 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$ (statistical uncertainty only), is ~ 3 times smaller than that reported for ss4 by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) based on optical scattered light. Given the likely uncertainties in measuring dust masses from scattered light these two measurements are probably consistent. The derived dust mass is consistent with those reported by [Schöier et al. \(2005\)](#), [Arimatsu et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Maercker et al. \(2018\)](#).

By studying the upper and the middle panels in [Fig. 3.3](#), we see that the T and Σ are prior dominated from $\sim 80''$ outwards. The region immediately ahead of the thermal pulse (i.e. $56'' - 80''$) suggests there may be emission from pre-thermal pulse material below the 3σ level likely observed by Herschel/PACS.

³The constant mass-loss model is calculated by projecting a r^{-2} density distribution from 3-dimensions to 2-dimensions.

The final panel in Fig. 3.3 depicts the radial β variation of the detached shell. The variation of β up to $56''$ is a direct indicator that the grain properties vary radially. The difference from the canonical value of β for ISM dust (e.g. [Planck Collaboration et al., 2014](#)) demonstrates that there is no substantial contribution from a swept up ISM dust component. This supports arguments that the shell arises from a variation in mass loss rather than an interaction between the wind and the ISM ([Wareing et al., 2007](#)). Given the uncertainties it is difficult to pinpoint the location of the changes in β . The region beyond $56''$ is prior dominated as the best-fit value of β is dictated by the SCUBA-2 data, which no longer provide strong constraints beyond this radius.

The broad peak at $16''$ ($\beta = 1.85$) is aligned well with the inner residual profile peak at $850 \mu\text{m}$, indicating that grains in this region are different to that of the rest of the shell, i.e. within the substructure of the shell. The dip at $40''$ ($\beta = 1.1$) is consistent with the peaks in both the temperature and residual profiles. The minimum and maximum values of β observed are intermediate to those expected for amorphous carbon and graphite ([Mennella et al., 1998](#), [Draine, 2016](#)).

3.4.3 Self-consistent dust radiative transfer modelling

The model SEDs in Fig. 3.4 are indistinguishable from one another at wavelengths shorter than $11.6 \mu\text{m}$, reproducing the general trend in observed global SED and the COMARCS model from the optical to mid-IR. From $11.6 \mu\text{m}$ onwards the SEDs of all but the Mss1 align well with the observations up to $500 \mu\text{m}$.

As expected given previous reports ([Kerschbaum et al., 2010](#), [Maercker et al., 2010](#)) and as seen in Fig. 3.4, the scenario of only an inner shell is unlikely. This is consistent with the largest χ_p^2 value being derived for this model rendering it the least likely. This supports the suggestion by [Maercker et al. \(2010\)](#) that ss1 is an artefact. For a similar reason the model with all the dust in ss2 also does not provide a good fit. Given that the models of ss1 and ss2 do not fit well, it is expected for the Mfourshells to also not fit well. The

reason for this is likely related to the temperatures of dust at these distances, which is too warm to reproduce the observed FIR emission.

Interestingly having all dust in ss3 best reproduces the SED with having all dust in the outermost shell (M2010) following a close second. Further, having all dust in the K2010 variety of the outermost shell has a much larger χ_p^2 making it also unlikely (most likely due to warm dust in the inner region overlapping with ss2). Therefore it is possible that the detached shell of U Ant extends from $41'' - 54''$. Previous reports of shell 3 having little-to-no dust may be premature, agreeing with the peak of the Herschel/PACS radial profiles, which peak at the location of ss3 where the gas emission peaks.

We note that similar to [Maercker et al. \(2018\)](#), none of the models reproduce the flux at $850 \mu\text{m}$, however they did not account for the contribution of CO(3-2) to the $850 \mu\text{m}$ flux. Our analysis – including CO subtraction – still produces an excess in flux ~ 3 times the model predictions. This could be due to the difference in grain properties in the substructure only visible at $850 \mu\text{m}$. Further exploration into dust properties (e.g.: size, shape and/or composition) and emission mechanisms (e.g.: spinning dust grains) may help understand this effect. Longer wavelength observation at e.g. 1.1 and 1.3 mm from ALMA or the LMT will contribute towards confirming the presence and shape of this excess.

As seen in Fig. 3.5, at $70 \mu\text{m}$ and $160 \mu\text{m}$ none of the model surface-brightness profiles reproduce the observed surface-brightness profile up to $\sim 40''$. While not aligning well, having all dust in ss3 best reproduces the shape of the observed profile (only scaled up) once again agreeing with Herschel/PACS observations peaking within ss3. It is followed closely by Mss4-M2010 which is the second-best-fitting model, providing further evidence of the dust emission being within $41'' - 54''$ (with complex structure and varying dust components as suggested below within the shell).

In contrast to the PACS data, the inner regions of the observed SCUBA-2 profiles are well reproduced by all models and begin to deviate only at $\sim 30''$. However, at $450 \mu\text{m}$ even

with the lowest χ_p^2 results, the low significance of the flux prevents meaningful conclusions based on the current 450 μm data.

Results derived from the 850 μm profiles are significantly different compared to the other three wavelengths, with only a small deviation between the χ_p^2 values. Mss1, with the largest χ_p^2 values at the other wavelengths (and can therefore easily be ruled out as a possibility), is the lowest χ_p^2 at 850 μm . This could point towards the presence of a different dust component emitting at this wavelength at smaller projected separations from the star, suggesting the presence of shell-substructure projected inwards.

We suggest two reasons for our inability to reproduce the inner regions of the PACS profiles based on the fact that the central source is much more compact than the models predict. The first is that a present day MLR governed by a steeper density power law (< -2) needs to be applied. This would indicate that the present day MLR is increasing once more, consistent with the gradual recovery of the luminosity and MLR in the aftermath of the thermal pulse. The second is that there is a cut off in the density distribution as a result of the fast moving thermal pulse wind sweeping up the pre-thermal pulse mass loss essentially leaving a *cavity* behind it. In order for the central component to appear point like at PACS 70 μm (the smallest beam FWHM: $5.46'' \times 5.76''$) it must be no more than $\sim 1/2$ beam FWHM (e.g.: Table 2 in [Miettinen et al., 2015](#)). Higher resolution observations (e.g.: from ALMA) are required to probe this region.

These scenarios become less significant at longer wavelengths as the beam size increases essentially smearing out the emission. We therefore do not have a reasonable explanation as to why the SCUBA-2 profiles begin to deviate following the peak of the detached shell.

3.5 Conclusions

We present the highest resolution sub-mm observations of the detached shell of U Ant at 850 μm to date using JCMT/SCUBA-2. The detached shell is clearly detected at

850 μm and marginally at 450 μm . It has a 3σ extent at 850 μm of $56''$ (0.07 ± 0.01 pc), consistent with past publications. The PSF-subtracted residual profile at 850 μm shows two peaks centred at $\sim 20''$ and at $40''$. The outer peak is aligned well with the peaks of the Herschel/PACS residual profiles at 70 μm and 160 μm and the weak emission at 450 μm . Therefore the well aligned peaks at all four wavelengths can be explained by the presence of a single shell. Following this the inner residual peak observed at 850 μm is likely the result of substructure within the same shell, visible only at this longer sub-mm wavelength due to a difference in grain properties between the average shell and the sub-structure.

From radial point-to-point SED fitting we derive profiles for T , Σ and β . The T profile has a weighted averaged temperature of 54 ± 2 K (between $12'' - 56''$) and is consistent with dust heated by ISRF. The sudden mass-loss increase in the Σ profile at $56''$ points to the time of the thermal pulse which gave rise to the detached shell. We calculate it to have occurred approximately 3500 ± 500 yr in the past. By integrating the Σ profile observed we estimate a total shell dust mass of $(2.0 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}$. We see hints of pre-thermal pulse mass loss in the Σ from $\sim 56'' - 80''$. The radial variation of dust properties is necessary to explain the radial variations observed in the β profile, indicating the presence of dust grains with β values intermediate to amorphous and graphitic carbon.

In all six of the model scenarios tested using radiative transfer modelling we are unable to reproduce the flux observed at 850 μm . This excess may be due to the substructure discussed above, however further analysis is required to better understand it. Resolved continuum observations at 1.1 and 1.3 mm will reveal the nature of this excess.

We find that the two best-fitting models to both the global SED and the observed surface-brightness profiles are that of all the dust concentrated in sub-shell three and all the dust concentrated in sub-shell four with both having very similar χ_p^2 values. This is in disagreement with existing literature which claims that sub-shell three has little-to-no dust. The detached shell of U Ant thus likely extends from $\sim 41'' - 54''$.

At PACS wavelengths none of the models reproduce the inner $\sim 40''$ of the shell. At SCUBA-2 wavelengths the exact opposite occurs. The SCUBA-2 850 μm observation is best reproduced by the model scenario assuming a single inner shell which was previously ruled out.

Two scenarios could give rise to the models being unable to reproduce the inner regions of the PACS wavelengths: (i) A present day MLR governed by a steep power law needs to be applied since the present day MLR and luminosity maybe increasing as a result of post-thermal pulse recovery; (ii) A cavity is formed as a result of the fast wind arising from the thermal pulse. Both these scenarios result in a highly compact central component which can not be constrained with current observations. These reasons become less significant at SCUBA-2 wavelengths as the beam size increases. Therefore we are unable to understand the reasoning for the deviations seen in SCUBA-2.

Comparing the observations, derived surface-brightness profiles, dust parameter profiles and the radiative transfer modelling, we suggest that the detached shell of U Ant is a single dust shell. We see evidence for filamentary/clumpy substructure within this dust shell appearing closer to the central star due to line-of-sight projection effects. The grain properties of the substructure are different to that of the overall shell.

Taking into account existing ALMA CO observations as well, the gaseous shell is found to be located within the inner region of this detached shell. The dust shell is wider due to the distribution of dust velocities spreading the shell outwards similar to what is described by [Simis et al. \(2001\)](#), while the gas remains confined due to interaction with the surrounding environment. An alternative explanation could be shock-driven instabilities in a dust/gas shell with a thin, low-mass shock on the inner edge. This shock heats the gas, enhancing the CO emission and exciting the atoms that scatter the line emission, locally enhancing their brightness. Dust is much harder to heat this way, and its temperature is set by radiation. Therefore we may be observing the warm shocked gas component while the gas in the rest of the shell is unaffected. Complex 3-D hydrodynamical modelling is required to discern between possible scenarios and understand the formation of this substructure.

Continuum observations from ALMA and SOFIA/FORCAST in the future could help resolve the variations observed in the model comparisons. The high resolution observations will constrain the dust radii and the inner dust components allowing us to observe any cut off and therefore the correct dust density distribution. Further, polarimetric imaging observation in the sub-mm will help narrow down the dust grain shape and size thus constraining the properties of the substructure within the detached shell.

Chapter 4

Sub-mm Variability of IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti

*The work in this chapter has been submitted for refereeing to MNRAS under the title Sub-mm Variability of IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti. The work in this chapter is fully reproducible and the scripts and data required to reproduce this analysis, figures and tables can be downloaded from https://github.com/Thavisha/Sub-mm_Variability.*

Abstract

We present the sub-mm variability of two of the most well studied AGB stars, IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti. The data are obtained at 450 μm and 850 μm as part of pointing calibration observations for the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope's SCUBA-2 instrument over a span of 7 years. The periods are derived using non-parametric methods, `Gatspy Supersmoother` and `P4J` in order not to assume an underlying shape to the periodicity. These were compared to two Lomb-Scargle parametric methods. We find that for both sources and wavelengths the periods derived from all methods are consistent within 1σ . The 850 μm phase folded light curves of IRC+10216 show a time lag of ~ 540 days compared to its optical counterpart. Using radiative transfer modelling as well as findings in literature we attribute this to both the relationship between stellar pulsation and the dust formation/destruction cycle as well as a second unknown mechanism which needs to be narrowed down in the future.

4.1 Introduction

All Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars are variable with brightness variations occurring on timescales of a few hundred days. These long term periodic variations generally originate as a result of the stellar pulsations (Höfner & Olofsson, 2018). While there have been many studies into the variability of AGB stars, most of them are limited to the optical to mid-infrared. However, visual extinction at these wavelengths caused by large amounts of circumstellar dust around high mass-loss rate AGB stars makes their variability difficult to trace.

Therefore, far-infrared (far-IR) and sub-millimeter (sub-mm) wavelength studies are important for determining the nature of the variability of AGB stars such as periods, properties and origins. Sub-mm wavelengths are almost entirely unaffected by extinction from circumstellar matter. Furthermore, changes in molecular bands that plague optical and near-infrared (near-IR) observations do not affect the sub-mm. Monitoring sub-mm changes in source brightness allows monitoring of dust formation and the dusty envelope, effectively studying the total star including its extended dusty circumstellar envelope.

Located at a distance of 130 ± 13 pc (McDonald et al., 2017) IRC+10216 (CW Leo) is one of the most extensively studied AGB stars. It is an archetypal C-rich pulsating variable star with a spherically symmetric envelope expanding at a nearly constant velocity (Cernicharo et al., 2015). Due to the heavy presence of dust in the stellar envelope it is optically thick at optical wavelengths and hence only visible as a dim point source. The thick dusty envelope also makes it one of the brightest near-IR sources in the sky. We have measured the envelope which extends out to $\sim 1'$ in the sub-mm continuum at $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ (Dharmawardena et al., 2018) using the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope's Sub-millimetre Common Use Bolometer Array-2 instrument (SCUBA-2; Holland et al., 2013).

While IRC+10216 is well studied in many aspects its variability has only been determined a handful of times in the optical and infrared using sparse, unevenly sampled data; sub-mm to radio wavelength determinations are even scarcer. Menten et al. (2006) determined

the variability of IRC+10216 in the radio continuum (1.3, 2.0 and 3.6 cm) using VLA observations over a span of three years. They estimated a period of 535 ± 51 days and argue that the emission arises from the stellar photosphere or a somewhat more extended radio-photosphere. [Dehaes et al. \(2007\)](#) determine a period of 655.3 days using 1.2 mm continuum observations.

In a more recent study [Groenewegen et al. \(2012\)](#) determined a period of 639 ± 4 days from Herschel/SPIRE (250, 350 and 450 μm) data. The authors also hypothesize that the variability of IRC+10216 is directly related to the central star. Further the authors observed the bow shock of IRC+10216 located at $\sim 3.5'$ from the central source. However this bow-shock was not detected in the deep sub-mm map and resulting surface-brightness profile presented in our previous work ([Dharmawardena et al., 2018](#)), as it is outside the region that SCUBA-2 is sensitive to. Therefore when we refer to the far-IR periodicity determined by [Groenewegen et al. \(2012\)](#), we are only considering the period they determined for the central star and ignore any effects of the bow shock.

[Kim et al. \(2015\)](#) derived a period of 640 ± 0.9 days in the optical using data from [Drake et al. \(2014\)](#). Similarly they derived periods in the JHKLM bands using light curve data from [Le Bertre \(1992\)](#) and [Shenavrin et al. \(2011\)](#). Several reports which employed optical measurements show periods ranging from 630 – 650 days ([Witteborn et al., 1980](#), [Dyck et al., 1991](#), [Le Bertre, 1992](#)).

Additionally molecular line observations by [Teyssier et al. \(2015\)](#) using Herschel HIFI, SPIRE, and PACS show periods between ~ 600 – 760 days for the HCN in the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10216. Analysis of rotational lines emitted from several molecules and radicals from ~ 8 – 116 GHz using the IRAM 30 m telescope by [Pardo et al. \(2018\)](#) also show variability in similar time scales. [He et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Fonfría et al. \(2018\)](#) also show the variability and variability in relative line strengths of several rotational lines, including SiS and HCN.

The O-rich cool pulsating binary AGB star *o* Ceti A, commonly known as *o* Ceti or Mira is the archetypal Mira variable and is located at a distance of 91.7 ± 10.2 pc ([McDonald](#)

et al., 2017). Mira variables are well-known Long Period Variables (LPVs) pulsating in the fundamental mode, having stable periods of several hundred days. This variability is attributed mainly to the typical stellar pulsations and variability of the stellar temperature (Wong et al., 2016).

A well sampled unbroken optical light curve from 1902 to 2006 compiled by Templeton & Karovska (2009) displays a stable long period of 333.09 ± 0.04 days. The low optical depth of *o* Ceti facilitates the analysis of its light curves in optical wavelengths allowing the curves to be studied in detail for over a century.

In this chapter we present sub-mm variability studies of IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti. The observations are obtained by the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope’s (JCMT) Sub-millimetre Common-User Bolometer Array 2 (SCUBA-2) instrument at $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$ (Chapin et al., 2013, Holland et al., 2013). Both stars are commonly used as SCUBA-2 pointing calibrators since its inception.

In Sec. 4.2 of this chapter we present the data and data reduction used. In this section we also describe the Point Spread Function (PSF) photometry techniques used to determine the stellar fluxes and the methods used to derive the period from the fluxes. The resultant light curves and period determination techniques are presented in Sec. 4.3. In Sec. 4.4 and 4.5 we discuss the periods derived, compare them to past publications and analyse the phase folded light curves to understand the possible origins of the sub-mm variability. In Sec. 4.6 we present the conclusion of this chapter.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Observations and Data Reduction

IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti are two sources frequently used to calibrate the pointing accuracy of the SCUBA-2 instrument. As a result there are ~ 900 and ~ 700 pointing observations for each source respectively from January 2011 – December 2017. The observations

add up to ~ 45 hours per source with individual observations ranging from ~ 45 seconds to ~ 6 minutes. The full list of observations used along with relevant information such as observation date, time and length are provided in the GitHub repository. The observations were selected and reduced using the method presented in Sec. 2.2 and 2.3 by [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#). The sources were reduced using Starlink version 2017A and the standard SCUBA-2 FCFs ([Dempsey et al., 2013](#)).

4.2.2 PSF Photometry

As described in [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#) the reduced observations on occasion had artifacts known as negative bowling and blooming where the background is over-reduced to zero around the central point source or was enhanced to be as bright as the central source giving rise to what appears to be extended emission. If we were to apply aperture photometry to determine fluxes, these artefacts would mean tailoring the aperture radii to each individual observation in order to avoid the affected regions. Since we have many hundreds of observations this is not feasible.

To overcome this issues we opted to determine the source fluxes via PSF photometry. Both sources are shown to be extended in [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#), and therefore we applied a modified PSF to include the flux of the extended circumstellar envelope. We convert the radial profile of the co-added maps from [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#) into a pseudo-PSF function and employ that to derive PSF photometry. The composite images removed the effects of negative bowling and blooming seen in the individual observations during co-addition process. By using the composite image radial profiles as our *PSF* function we ensure the extended emission and the correct shape of the sources are taken into account.

Having determined a suitable PSF function we use the PSF photometry routines in the *Astropy* affiliated package `photutils` ([Bradley et al., 2016](#)) to carry out PSF photometry on our observations. The program produces background-subtracted PSF photometry

Table 4.1 Summary of PSF Photometry Results

Source and Wavelength	Flux Range (Jy)	Average Flux (Jy)	σ (Jy)
IRC+10216 450 μm	10 – 41	25 ± 0.20	5
IRC+10216 850 μm	8 – 14	11 ± 0.04	1
<i>o</i> Ceti 450 μm	0.12 – 9.9	2.7 ± 0.04	1.1
<i>o</i> Ceti 850 μm	0.02 – 1.5	0.6 ± 0.01	0.14

along with the uncertainties on the fluxes. We include a SCUBA-2 calibration uncertainty of 8% in addition to the uncertainties returned by `photutils`.

4.3 Results and Analysis

4.3.1 Light Curves

Fig. 4.1 presents the 450 μm (top) and 850 μm (bottom) light curves for IRC+10216, while Fig. 4.2 presents the same for *o* Ceti.

Table 4.1 presents the average flux, standard deviation and the flux range derived from PSF photometry for each source at each wavelength. The average fluxes of both sources at both wavelengths are consistent with the respective total fluxes reported in [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#).

4.3.2 Sub-mm Periods

When determining the periods for both sources, we have to take into account that our light curves are comprised of irregularly sampled data and select a method which will be able to handle these irregularities. We also want to avoid making any prior assumptions of the underlying shape of the periodicity. Therefore we primarily focus on two non-parametric methods to determine our periods.

For comparison we also employ two commonly used parametric codes, based on Lomb-Scargle (LS) periodograms ([Lomb, 1976](#), [Scargle, 1982](#)). LS periodograms are a Fourier

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1 Light Curves at $450 \mu\text{m}$ (top) and $850 \mu\text{m}$ (bottom) for IRC+10216

transform, power spectrum technique which detects periodicity in a set of time series data which is irregularly sampled. They assume an underlying sine shape for the periodicity. The Lomb-Scargle packages used are the python packages `Astropy Lomb-Scargle Periodograms` and `gatspy LombScargle` (VanderPlas & Ivezić, 2015, Vanderplas, 2015).

The first non-parametric method we chose is a linear regression algorithm known as Super-smoother, first presented by Reimann (1994). We use the implementation in the python package `gatspy` (VanderPlas & Ivezić, 2015, Vanderplas, 2015). Super-smoother is a non-parametric adaptive smoothing algorithm based on a local linear regression estimator with adaptive bandwidths (number of data points).

Figure 4.2 Light Curves at 450 μm (top) and 850 μm (bottom) for *o* Ceti

In essence this algorithm smooths the data along a smoothing length (the range of periods provided as prior estimates, which is then converted to frequencies for calculation purposes in the code). For each candidate frequency within the provided range, the algorithm phase folds the data and fits a straight line to calculate the scatter (density distribution) of the data points. This is carried out repeatedly for all periods in the input range. The period where the scatter is minimised is reported as the optimum period for that data set. This is ideal as the least scatter (scatter minimised the best) should occur when the data is smoothed over exactly one period.

As the second non-parametric method we chose the python package P4J ([Huijse et al.](#),

2018), which is ideal for unevenly sampled time series data (Principe, 2010). The package employs information-theoretic criteria which incorporate information on the whole probability density function of the process and hence is more robust than classical second-order statistics based criteria. It is also not limited to linear relationships or Gaussian probability density functions (PDFs).

The P4J package is based on a type of information criterion known as Quadratic mutual information criterion, where the divergence (statistical distance) between two sets of probability density functions (PDFs) of a random sample is measured: i) the joint PDF of a random sample (PDF of the total sample); and ii) a product of the marginal PDFs (PDFs of each data point in the sample). While there are several methods with which the divergence could be measured in P4J we choose to measure the divergence of the PDFs by the Cauchy–Schwarz statistical inequality (QMICS) in this work. The divergence between the PDFs is checked for a range of periods provided as input priors and the period which gives rise to the least divergent set of PDFs is reported as the best period for that data set. If the light curve is folded with the wrong period, the fluxes are independent of the phases and the structure in the joint PDF will be almost equal to the product of the marginal PDFs. The best-fit period is therefore the one with the maximum correlation between fluxes and phases (Huijse et al., 2018).

The uncertainties on our final periods were initially determined using Monte Carlo (MC) bootstrapping with one thousand iterations (σ_{MC}). These uncertainties are comparable to those derived in literature (e.g., Groenewegen et al., 2012). However, σ_{MC} is only a representation of the variations on the location of the peak of the periodograms from independent variations of each data point. As we can see, our periodograms have a wide peak representing a larger range of possible periods and therefore the power can not be localised as well as σ_{MC} implies. Therefore we choose to derive another uncertainty, σ_{FWHM} , which is the FWHM of the periodogram peak. We then present the confidence intervals (σ_{Tot}) of our period which is the square root of the quadrature sum of σ_{MC} and σ_{FWHM} as the final uncertainty period. As expected, σ_{Tot} is dominated by σ_{FWHM} since the FWHMs are much larger compared to the uncertainties derived from MC.

Table 4.2 Sub-mm Periods and Confidence Intervals of IRC+10216

Period Method	450 μm Period (days)				850 μm Period (days)			
	Period	σ_{MC}	σ_{FWHM}	σ_{Tot}	Period	σ_{MC}	σ_{FWHM}	σ_{Tot}
Astropy LombScargle	973	1	150	150	678	1	85	85
Gatspy SlowLomb	968	6	190	190	668	5	78	79
Gatspy Supersmoother	725	1	80	80	674	5	95	95
P4J QMICS	730	5	80	80	667	9	80	80

The σ_{Tot} presented for each wavelength is the square root of the quadrature sum of the σ_{MC} and σ_{FWHM} . We assume σ_{Tot} to be the final confidence intervals for our periods. The confidence interval is dominated by the σ_{FWHM} given its much larger values.

Table 4.3 Sub-mm Periods and Confidence Intervals of *o* Ceti

Period Method	450 μm Period (days)				850 μm Period (days)			
	Period	σ_{MC}	σ_{FWHM}	σ_{Tot}	Period	σ_{MC}	σ_{FWHM}	σ_{Tot}
Astropy LombScargle	336	5	29	29	336	1	28	28
Gatspy SlowLomb	332	1	30	30	332	2	30	30
Gatspy Supersmoother	350	1	30	30	310	8	95	95
P4J QMICS	345	2	31	31	328	3	29	29

See table notes in Table 4.2.

The derived periods along with their corresponding confidence intervals are given in Tables 4.2 and 4.3 for CW Leo and Mira respectively. The periodograms and phase folded light curves are presented in appendix G.

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Periodograms

All the periodograms presented show multiple features of different strengths. The most likely period nearly always dominates over these multiple features having the highest power. We also observe harmonics in the form of somewhat strong peaks appearing at periods of $1/n$ (VanderPlas, 2018). The strongest of these harmonics is observed as a strong narrow peak (with a similar but slightly smaller power to the period peak) in the case of IRC+10216 450 μm between a period of 200 – 400 days.

In the case of IRC+10216 we find the best fit period peak to be wide with a secondary peak at a lower power blended into it. For the parametric methods at $450\ \mu\text{m}$ this peak appears to correspond to the period determined at $850\ \mu\text{m}$.

In order to investigate this secondary peak we subtracted the best fit model produced using Astropy Lombscargle from the $850\ \mu\text{m}$ light curve of IRC+10216 and then refitted the data. This does not result in a meaningful period as this light curve (i.e. a residual profile) is dominated entirely by noise resonating around zero flux as shown in Fig. 4.3. This shows that for $850\ \mu\text{m}$ data a single period describes the data well, at the level of noise seen, as shown by the residual at $850\ \mu\text{m}$ when one subtracts the strongest period.

Figure 4.3 Phase folded residual profile dominated by noise.

Therefore it is likely that the $450\ \mu\text{m}$ IRC+10216 data are noise dominated and hence affecting its period result. Phase folding the $450\ \mu\text{m}$ data with the $850\ \mu\text{m}$ period does not alleviate the scatter observed showing no discernible shape. This further indicates that the $450\ \mu\text{m}$ data is noise dominated. The $850\ \mu\text{m}$ data has a higher signal-to-noise ratio and therefore is preferred in this instance to study the periodicity.

Further investigation shows that this secondary peak is very likely a result of aliasing with the window function¹. Using the observing window and the corresponding $850\ \mu\text{m}$ period – which we assume to be the true period – we are able to derive a similar period (937 days) to that of the secondary peak, demonstrating this. The aliasing is exacerbated by the noise which dominates the $450\ \mu\text{m}$ data causing the secondary peak be stronger than

¹The window function is a selection function which described when the data is observed. The light curve in essence is a convolution of the real light curve and this function. The window function can introduce a frequency which can interfere with the true frequency similar to the beat effect

the real period in some cases. Non parametric methods are better able to handle these adverse effects; the periods determined by these methods at 450 μm are less-strongly affected. Therefore for the periods determined by the parametric methods at 450 μm , where the aliased peak dominates we can consider the corresponding 850 μm period to be its real period.

4.4.2 Periods and Phase folded Light Curves

Despite, its light curve being less evenly sampled, the sub-mm periods of *o* Ceti at both SCUBA-2 wavelengths are much better constrained than those of IRC+10216. There is very good agreement between the periods found at both wavelengths and with the periods reported in the literature (Templeton & Karovska, 2009).

The 850 μm period of IRC+10216 are similarly constrained for all methods and is consistent with the optical – far-IR periods reported in literature (Le Bertre, 1992, Groenewegen et al., 2012, Drake et al., 2014, Kim et al., 2015). However at 450 μm , while consistent within confidence limits, the periods are significantly larger than those determined at 850 μm and in literature. This effect is likely due a combination of several factors: (i) the uneven sampling of the light curve, (ii) data scatter and (iii) the large uncertainties in individual photometric points. Given the ability of the non-parametric methods (P4J and Gatspy Supersmoother) to better handle uneven sampling, more noisy data and large data scatter we see that these 450 μm periods derived using these two methods are much better constrained compared to the parametric methods.

We must also note that we are somewhat limited in our ability to constrain the period. The sub-mm data available to us only pertains to ~ 3 cycles, given the periods determined. This therefore calls for further sub-mm monitoring of these sources to better estimate and understand the periodicity of these two sources.

The 850 μm phase folded light curves of IRC+10216 are the least scattered and best sampled, therefore showing a shape to its periodicity in the phase folded light curves.

This allows us to determine properties of the periodicity such as phase at which peak brightness occurs. We are unable to repeat this process for the 450 μm and *o* Ceti counterparts since no such visible shape is present in the phase folded light curves. Once again this most likely the result of the above mentioned factors: data scatter, noisiness and sampling.

Once we rebin and phase fold the data aligning them to the peak (T0) of the Catalina optical light curve (Drake et al., 2014, Kim et al., 2015), we find that there is a phase difference of $\Delta\phi = \sim 0.79$. This corresponds to a phase lag of 540 days between the optical light curve and the sub-mm peak of the phase folded IRC+10216 850 μm light curve.

Further investigation into the phases of IRC+10216 light curves show that from the optical - far-IR the phases are aligned in a similar manner (Drake et al., 2014, Groenewegen et al., 2012, Kim et al., 2015). Conversely when we compare the parameters of the radio light curve derived by Menten et al. (2006) to our results at 850 μm we find it to be similar in phase to our data. The peak phase of our data is only $\Delta\phi = \sim 0.2$ off phase with the radio data, given the uncertainties on period and phase determination this slight off-set can be negligible. The period determine by Menten et al. (2006) (535 ± 51 days) is shorter and determined using data covering only ~ 1 cycle. However their period is consistent with ours at the 2σ level. This similarity could point to a related mechanism giving rise to variability at these long wavelengths.

In the following section we explore several possible scenarios which could give rise to the sub-mm variability and the optical – sub-mm phase lag we observe.

4.5 Exploring the Origins the Sub-mm Variability and Phase-lag in IRC+10216

4.5.1 Light Travel Time

We first investigate whether this phase lag occurs as a result of the light travel times. Optical emission would peak at the moment of the stellar pulse, when the star is at its brightest. The corresponding travel time is ~ 50 days (0.04 pc; [Dharmawardena et al., 2018](#)), too short to explain the phase lag.

[Groenewegen et al. \(2012\)](#) identify a lag of 402 ± 37 days between the bow shock and the central source of IRC+10216 in the far-IR, which they attribute to light travel time between the star and the bow shock. This time lag is similar to what we derive. However the bow shock is located at $\sim 3.5'$, well beyond the point source observing window of our SCUBA-2 observations. Therefore we do not detect the bow shock in our sub-mm observations (see [Dharmawardena et al., 2018](#), and Sec.4.2.1 in this work), and it can hence be ruled out as a cause for the sub-mm variability and phase lag.

4.5.2 Molecular Line Contamination

We must also consider the possibility that some of this variability and hence the phase lag could be a result of molecular-line contamination. Many publications in the past have shown molecular-line variability of IRC+10216 in great detail ([Teyssier et al., 2015](#), [He et al., 2016](#), [Fonfría et al., 2018](#), [Pardo et al., 2018](#)). The variability of these molecular lines may contribute to the variations we observe here and attribute to the (dust) continuum.

In the case of the SCUBA-2 instrument the strongest line in the bandpass and hence the most likely source of line contamination is the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ line; other lines are typically much weaker ([Drabek et al., 2012](#)). The JCMT has analysed the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ line emission

of IRC+10216 extensively as part of their calibration process for the HARP instrument². In Fig. 4.4 we present the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ time series for IRC+10216 obtained by the JCMT from January 2007 to April 2019.

Figure 4.4 $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ time series data for IRC+10216 obtained as part of the JCMT/HARP calibration (data and original figure is available in the following JCMT web page: <https://www.eaobservatory.org/jcmt/instrumentation/heterodyne/calibration/harp-standards/>). Green dots: time series data; Black dashed line: The peak antenna temperature of the averaged spectrum of IRC+10216 - 32.9 K; Grey dashed lines: $\pm 10\%$ of the peak antenna temperature of the averaged spectrum.

From figure 4.4 we see that the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ line does not appear to show periodic variability at even a 10% level. Attempts made to fit this data to derive a period shows the light curve is dominated by noise and gives rise to an approximately one year period, which likely corresponds to the annual gaps in the data when the source is not visible. In addition, the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ line typically contributes only about $\sim 8 - 20\%$ to the SCUBA-2 850 μm flux (Drabek et al., 2012, Parsons et al., 2018). Taking these factors into account the maximum change in the continuum due to $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ is no more than 2% – assuming the highest level of contamination – and therefore is not the cause of the variability or phase lag observed. As this is the strongest line we do not expect the other lines to cause any significant changes to the observed continuum variability and phase lag.

²<https://www.eaobservatory.org/jcmt/instrumentation/heterodyne/calibration/harp-standards/>

4.5.3 Cycle of Dust Formation and Destruction

We also explore the possibility that the relationship between the stellar pulsation and dust formation cycle may explain the sub-mm variability and observed phase lag. The star's brightness and size increases during the stellar pulse and is best observed in the optical - near-IR, hence giving rise to the optical peak. At the stellar minimum, the material in the surrounding circumstellar envelope is at its coolest and therefore most favourable for dust formation (causing the sub-mm emission to peak). Dust is then illuminated and subsequently heated undergoing thermal emission over time. As the star approaches maximum light some of this dust is sublimated reducing the total dust mass. We suggest this cyclic dust cooling, formation, heating and destruction close to the central star is responsible for the sub-mm variability and hence the lag observed between the optical and sub-mm peaks.

Support for this provided by the self consistent C-rich AGB wind model **DARWIN** (Bladh, 2019). This model shows that the dust density increases out of phase in relation to the stellar pulse. The dust condensation region changes by $\sim 1 R_*$ with more dust formed closer to the central star at minimum stellar luminosity ($\phi = 0.5$) (see their Fig. 2, middle panel).

4.5.3.1 Radiative Transfer Modelling of IRC+10216

We generate radiative transfer models of IRC+10216 using the python package **Hyperion** (Robitaille, 2011). By doing so we explore the origins of the sub-mm variability, phase lag and a simplified version of the above scenario.

With **Hyperion** we are limited to static models as this method can not handle time-dependent radiative transfer or self consistent dust formation and destruction (unlike the **DARWIN** wind model). As a result we are only able to approximately model the light curve. The inherent non-linearity of the radiative transfer problem means that interpolation

between minimum and maximum luminosity snapshots would not capture the physical process at work.

Instead we present snapshots built along the bolometric luminosity light curve of IRC+10216 which allows us to generate a snapshot light curve in the sub-mm ignoring the time dependent effects. The stellar parameters were taken from [Menten et al. \(2006, 2012\)](#) and the dust parameters are derived by [Dharmawardena et al. \(2018\)](#). Key stellar parameters used are as follows: (i) Maximum stellar luminosity (L_{max}): $1.1 \times 10^4 L_{\odot}$; (ii) Minimum stellar luminosity (L_{min}): $4400 L_{\odot}$; (iii) Effective stellar temperature: 2750 K; (iv) Stellar radius (R_*): 1.9 au. In the case of the dust grain properties we assume a $\kappa_{1\mu m}^S = 1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. The dust is assumed to be a mixture of 90% amorphous carbon and 10% silicon carbide with their optical constants derived from [Zubko et al. \(1996\)](#) and [Pégourié \(1988\)](#) respectively. The grain size distribution is assumed to be a power-law with an exponential fall off as determined by [Kim et al. \(1994\)](#). Here we begin with a minimum grain size of $0.01 \mu\text{m}$ along with an exponential cut-off scale of $1 \mu\text{m}$ and a power-law slope of -3.5 . Hyperion uses BHMIE to calculate the weighted averaged grain cross section to use as the model input from the grain distribution described.

Hyperion iteratively removes dust above our input dust sublimation temperatures, therefore essentially assuming instant dust formation and destruction. This therefore ignores several parameters dictating dust formation/destruction in AGB stars, e.g., chemistry, shocks and hydrodynamical effects.

The resulting model sub-mm light curve is presented in [Fig. 4.5](#). While we observe a variable model curve we do not observe a phase lag compared to the input bolometric luminosity light curve. In order to test any time delays in dust formation/destruction we require time-dependent radiative transfer models such as DARWIN.

Further we only recover $\sim 4\%$ of the observed flux at $850 \mu\text{m}$ with each model forming the model light curve. However this is not an issue for our analysis as we are interested in the relative changes in flux and the resulting dust parameter, such as the dust condensation radius.

Figure 4.5 Modelled sub-mm Light curve generated using a series `Hyperion` static models.

However comparing the peak/trough ratio between the observed $850 \mu\text{m}$ light curve and the model light curve we find them both to be a similar ratio. The ratio of the observed light curve is 1.4 ± 0.2 while the model ratio is 1.6. Therefore we are able to recover the same magnitude of variation as the observed light curve.

Moreover, we are able to narrow down the region from which the bulk of the sub-mm emission arises by studying the radial profiles derived from our models (see Fig. 4.6). By studying the radial profiles of our models we find that 99% of the flux within the beam FWHM ($13''$ at $850 \mu\text{m}$) arises from the small inner $2''$ region. Therefore we are not sensitive to historic thermal dust emission from the outer circumstellar envelope along the line of sight of the beam FWHM in this instance. This inner $2''$ region well encompasses the expected dust formation region of IRC+10216 as well as the extended radio photosphere described in [Menten et al. \(2006\)](#).

Given a dust sublimation temperature `Hyperion` has the ability to calculate the dust sublimation region by iteratively removing dust above the sublimation temperature until the radiative transfer converges. We interpret this radius as the dust condensation radius.

Figure 4.6 Radial profile derived from peak sub-mm flux model depicted up to the SCUBA-2 850 μm beam FWHM ($13''$).

Using our models we find a shift in dust condensation radii by $\sim 1.0 R_*$ going from $R_* = 3.5$ at L_{max} to $R_* = 2.5$ at L_{min} (see Fig. 4.7). This is consistent with the shift in dust condensation radii predicted by the DARWIN wind models.

Therefore looking at our modelled results it is likely that the dust formation and destruction cycle may contribute to the variability of IRC+10216 to a limited degree. However some other mechanism in the inner regions of the envelope dominates over this.

4.5.4 Free-free emission

As discussed above, we find our phase lag to be similar to that observed in the radio by Menten et al. (2006). Menten et al. (2006, 2012) suggest the radio emission likely arises from a radio photosphere \sim twice the stellar radius. This photosphere extends approximately up to the beginning of the dust formation region observed in our models. They further suggest the dominant emission mechanism likely to cause the variability in the radio photosphere is free-free emission. These authors suggest that shocks travelling

Figure 4.7 Temperature as a function of stellar radius as a function of maximum stellar luminosity (red; stellar pulse at its peak) and minimum stellar luminosity (blue; stellar pulse at its weakest)

at speeds of approximately $10 - 15 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ can heat up the material causing the free-free emission in the outflow and producing the variability at 7mm.

Using the sub-mm - radio levels of free-free emission presented in [Menten et al. \(2006\)](#) (see their Fig. 2) we calculate the largest possible contribution of flux from free-free emission to our variability. At $850 \mu\text{m}$ free-free emission contributes 950 mJy, extrapolating from 3 mm with the spectral index of 1.96 provided in [Menten et al. \(2006\)](#). Therefore, we find that the free-free emission contributes only $\sim 10\%$ of the $850 \mu\text{m}$ flux that we observe. By the same logic applied to molecular lines above this rules free-free emission out as a likely cause for the observed sub-mm variability.

Therefore given the current constraints on our models we are unable to pin-point the cause of the sub-mm emission. However, given the coupled nature of the sub-mm and radio light curves suggests that both are driven by a single physical cause. Further investigation into this as of yet unknown mechanism is required to see what role it may play in the sub-mm continuum emission.

4.6 Conclusions

We characterise the sub-mm periodicity of two of the most well-known AGB stars; IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti. The observations were obtained from pointing calibrations from the JCMT/SCUBA-2 instrument at 450 μm and 850 μm .

In order to avoid assuming an underlying shape and to better account for the irregular sampling of the light curve we were motivated to use two non-parametric methods for period determination. For comparison we also employed two parametric methods. The derived periods of *o* Ceti agreed very well with published results and with each other at the two wavelengths. The 450 μm observations of IRC+10216, where the data scatter, large uncertainties in individual data points and the uneven sampling affects the period determination the most, the non-parametric methods were more effective in constraining the period. The periods of IRC+10216 at 850 μm agreed well with past publications.

Overall the periods determined have large confidence intervals. The precision and confidence interval of these sub-mm periods can in the future be improved using the following methods: 1) reducing the discontinuities in data by continuing to monitor these stars in the sub-mm; 2) reduce the uncertainties on the individual photometric points, and hence the scatter in data points. While higher signal-to-noise individual observations would help improve the uncertainties somewhat, in the 850 μm light curves we can clearly see that they are calibration limited and therefore deeper observations will not be very effective. Instead the individual photometric uncertainties can be improved by determining the relative uncertainties in flux variations using field stars. In order to do so however, we must expand the observation field in order to incorporate field stars in the field of view. The JCMT Transients project successfully uses this method to determine accurate light curves to detect unknown variability (Mairs et al., 2017).

We observe a ~ 540 day time lag between the published optical light curves and our 850 μm IRC+10216 light curve despite having similar periods at all wavelengths. A similar phase lag is observed in the radio, while shorter wavelengths match well with the optical.

Studying a set of models in the literature in combination with our own radiative transfer models suggests that there are several mechanisms contribute to the sub-mm variability. The relationship between the stellar pulse, luminosity and the dust formation cycles may play a role, as well as an as yet unknown dominant mechanism which results in both the sub-mm and radio variability. Shocks waves and dust heating may be responsible. Due to the limitations placed on our static models we are unable to discern the nature of this dominant mechanism. Time-dependent self-consistent radiative-hydrodynamical models, high resolution ALMA observations ($< 0.1''$) and time resolved imaging in the sub-mm will allow us to shed light on this in the future.

Should the dust formation cycle be found to dominate sub-mm light curves may be a key method for studying the life cycle of dust formation and destruction in the innermost regions of the stellar outflow which is extremely difficult to directly observe without the aid of deep high-resolution observations from facilities as ALMA and VLT.

Chapter 5

Stacking analysis of the Herschel/HERITAGE data to statistically study far-IR dust emission from evolved stars in the Large Magellanic Cloud

5.1 Introduction

Dust produced by evolved stars plays a key role in replenishing the interstellar medium (ISM) of galaxies with material, hence contributing to its chemical enrichment. For instance [Matsuura et al. \(2009\)](#), [Boyer et al. \(2012\)](#), [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#) and [Srinivasan et al. \(2016\)](#) have studied the thermal emission from dust ejected by evolved stars in the Magellanic clouds in detail using mid-IR Spitzer data, in particular from the Spitzer legacy project Surveying the Agents of a Galaxy's Evolution (SAGE; [Meixner et al., 2006](#)). However mid-IR dust emission from evolved stars is primarily due to the warmer ($T \sim a$

few hundred K) present day mass loss ignoring dust ejected in the star's past. In order to fully understand the role of evolved stars in ISM replenishment and the total amount of dust injected it is important to also study the cooler ($T < 50$ K) historic dust mass loss. This is facilitated by studying their extended circumstellar envelopes, visible at longer wavelengths from far-IR to sub-mm wavelengths.

As discussed in the three preceding chapters, studies in the far-IR – sub-mm of evolved stars in the Milky Way reveal extended circumstellar envelopes and variable mass-loss. These studies allow us to understand the role these sources play as well as calculate their contribution to the ISM (Groenewegen et al., 2011, 2012, Cox et al., 2012, Dharmawardena et al., 2018). While several such far-IR – sub-mm studies exist for Milky Way sources, resolution limitations mean very few sources are detected and analysed beyond the Milky Way.

The HERschel Inventory of The Agents of Galaxy Evolution (HERITAGE) program is a far-IR survey of the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds (LMC and SMC) using the Herschel PACS (at $100\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$) and SPIRE (at $250\mu\text{m}$, $350\mu\text{m}$ and $500\mu\text{m}$) instruments (Meixner et al., 2013). While this survey is one of highest resolution far-IR surveys of the Magellanic clouds to date, confusion caused by interstellar emission and limited spatial resolution makes it difficult to detect the evolved stars. Of the tens-of-thousand evolved stars identified by SAGE in the Magellanic clouds (e.g: Boyer et al., 2012, Riebel et al., 2012) only 14 were confirmed to have been detected as a point source in the HERITAGE survey (Jones et al., 2015b).

In order to overcome detection limitations, cosmologists have used an adept tactic to improve the S/N ratio by stacking a large number of sources (that are not individually detected), which allows them to study the properties of sources in a statistical manner (e.g., Pope et al., 2008, Rodighiero et al., 2010, Schreiber et al., 2015). We will explore the potential of this method to statistically analyse the far-IR dust emission from the evolved-star population in the Magellanic clouds by stacking Spitzer-identified evolved stars using postage-stamp like cutouts from the HERITAGE maps.

While this stacking method is optimal for high-redshift sources surrounded by little to no interfering interstellar background, care must be taken when applying it to the Magellanic clouds. The interstellar background in the Magellanic clouds is bright and structured in the far-IR and therefore can impede the detection of the sources of interest even when stacked.

The key goal of this project is to study the cold dust component of the evolved stars in a statistical manner by stacking cutouts (centred on the evolved stars) of the LMC HERITAGE maps. By doing so we will explore the possibility of the presence of a far-IR excess. This excess typically arises due to a previously undetected cold dust component resulting from historic mass loss. The evolved-star population for this purpose is derived from [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#), who studied the dust mass loss of evolved stars in LMC using Spitzer mid-IR data obtained as part of the SAGE survey.

We will compare the stacked fluxes to predictions from the Grid of RSG and AGB Models (GRAMS; [Sargent et al., 2011](#), [Srinivasan et al., 2011](#)). GRAMS is a pre-computed grid of evolved star SEDs (radiative transfer models) generated assuming stellar photosphere models surrounded by either silicate or carbonaceous circumstellar dust shells ([Sargent et al., 2011](#), [Srinivasan et al., 2011](#)). GRAMS assumes a constant mass-loss rate and hence ignores historic mass loss or variations. By comparing our stacked fluxes to the GRAMS predictions we will explore the existence or lack of a far-IR excess in the HERITAGE evolved stars, hence evaluating the validity of applying GRAMS to derive mass-loss rates of evolved stars and understanding its limitations.

In this chapter we present a proof-of-concept analysis of the evolved-star population of the Large Magellanic cloud using the HERITAGE maps at $100\ \mu\text{m}$. The PACS $100\ \mu\text{m}$ data have the highest spatial resolution and much better contrast when compared to its counterparts at longer wavelengths making it ideal for initial analysis. This allows us to test the stacking method and understand its merits and caveats when applied to confused fields (e.g., large scale structure, crowding and strong background emission) such as the

LMC. However a disadvantage of using the PACS 100 μm data is that it shows the least excess emission due to a potential cold dust component.

This chapter is presented in the following format: In section 5.2 we present the methodology explored; In section 5.3 we analyse our preliminary findings comparing the stacked fluxes to those predicted by the GRAMS models. We conclude this chapter with section 5.4 with a summary of our findings and the future outlook of this work.

5.2 Observations and Methodology

The data used were obtained from the Herschel open time key program HERITAGE, which mapped the LMC and SMC from March – September 2010 (Meixner et al., 2013). The observations for this survey were carried out at 100 μm and 160 μm using the Herschel/PACS instrument (Poglitsch et al., 2010) and at 250 μm , 350 μm and 500 μm using the Herschel/SPIRE instrument (Griffin et al., 2010). We downloaded the reduced HERITAGE PACS 100 μm User Produced Data Products (UPDP) directly from the Herschel Science Archive¹ for our analysis.

5.2.1 Removal of Contaminants and Selection of Stacking Categories

Riebel et al. (2012) presented a catalogue of 33503 evolved-star candidates identified in the mid-IR as part of the SAGE survey. By fitting the near – mid-IR spectrum of these sources with the GRAMS model grid the authors derived the chemical class and dust mass-loss rate (among other parameters) for each of the 33503 evolved star candidates. We employ this catalogue to derive the source sample for each of our chosen stacks.

Prior to dividing the population into categories we first removed the following sub-sets of sources from the population:

¹<http://archives.esac.esa.int/hsa/legacy/>

- The goal of this study is to evaluate the average behaviour of sources which are not detectable individually. Therefore we cross match the [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#) catalogue to the point sources detected in the HERITAGE survey ([Gruendl et al., 2008](#), [Meixner et al., 2013](#), [Seale et al., 2014](#), [Jones et al., 2015b](#)) and remove all sources in common from the [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#) catalogue. A total of 56 sources were removed from this initial cut. Of these 56 sources only 19 have been confirmed as evolved stars/candidates by [Gruendl et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Jones et al. \(2015b\)](#);
- Due to complex backgrounds in some of the cutouts (derived as described below), we removed 0.3% of the sources with the highest background RMS in their cutouts. This 3σ RMS cut removed a further 76 sources.

A further 715 sources were omitted as they were at the edges of the HERITAGE map and we could not get clear margins around the center. The remaining sample of 32656 sources were stacked and analysed based on the following categories:

- All evolved-stars;
- Initial stellar mass: AGBs and RSGs;
- AGB chemical class: C-rich and O-rich;
- Chemical classes split up by mass-loss rate decade;

5.2.2 Generating Cutouts and Stacking

In order to stack the sources we first create small square cutouts from the HERITAGE map of the chosen wavelength centred on the source. We opt to make each square cutout ~ 20 times the size of the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) of the Point Spread Function (PSF). This size allows for sufficient background to be displayed allowing us to accurately subtract the background when performing photometry. Key details of the HERITAGE PACS 100 μm map and the cutouts produced are presented in table [5.1](#).

Table 5.1 Key Information of the HERITAGE PACS 100 μm map and the Generated Cutouts

	PACS 100 μm
Primary beam FWHM	$5.46'' \times 5.76''$ ^[a]
Pixel size of Map	$2''$
Size of Cutout	$140'' \times 140''$
Size of Cutout (pixels)	69×69
Position of Source Center (pixel)	$35, 35$

^a (Bocchio et al., 2016)

To ensure that the source position (i.e. peak) is contained in the central pixel of each cutout, the cutout sizes (in pixel units) are always odd numbered. However at sub-pixel precision the source centre is typically misaligned within this central pixel, resulting in some smearing around the PSF when the sources are stacked. For example, in the case of PACS 100 μm taking into account the PSF FWHM and pixel size, each PSF will be $\sim 3 - 4$ pixel units. With some offset in the peak within the central pixel the smearing would extend over ~ 0.5 pixels. Therefore we may underestimate the stacked flux by $\sim 10\%$. For our testing purposes we ignore this smearing effect and assume the cutout centre is located at the central coordinate (peak position) of the source.

5.2.3 PSF Photometry and GRAMS predicted fluxes

To determine the photometric flux of the summed stack we use the Python package `photutils` to carry out background-subtracted PSF photometry. During this process we apply background subtraction to our stacks. We chose the `photutils` PSF photometry background subtraction routine `MMMBackground` based on the DAOPHOT algorithm by the same name. This background subtraction routine is optimised to handle complex large-scale background structure.

The PACS PSF is non-circular and depends on the orientation of the scan, i.e. telescope rotation angle, and the scan speed (Balog et al., 2014, Bocchio et al., 2016). However, due to the observation timeline and scan lengths the point sources in the maps appeared more circular. The final HERITAGE maps were generated by combining multiple observations

of lengthy scans of varying duration. During each of these scans the pointing uncertainties and position angle of the telescope change. Combining these scans of these different characteristics circularises the PSF compared to the original Herschel PSFs. For a more comprehensive description of this effect please see [Meixner et al. \(2013\)](#).

In an attempt to account for the effects described above, we first derive an azimuthally-averaged profile of the standard PACS PSF. This profile is then converted into a modified circular PSF using several `photutils` PSF-generation modules, which is what we finally use as the PSF (shown in Fig. 5.1(g)) when carrying out PSF photometry on our stacks. For our testing purposes presented in this chapter this method takes into account effects of telescope rotation, as the point sources themselves appear circular in the HERITAGE maps. However the HERITAGE PSF will be broader than the standard Herschel PSF (even when circularised), due to pixel alignment which as discussed above needs to be taken into account in the future.

We then derive the corresponding GRAMS predicted fluxes for each of our stacks. The GRAMS model for each source is comprised of an SED, fit to its mid-IR spectrum, which is then extrapolated to longer wavelengths to include the far-IR and sub-mm wavelength range. We interpolate the model of each source to ensure alignment during stacking. Each model stack is composed of the same set of sources which were used to obtain our observed stacks. The interpolated models are sum-stacked together to derive a single stacked model SED on which we carry out synthetic photometry to derive the final predicted fluxes at the required filters. In our case the filter is the PACS 100 μm filter.

5.3 Preliminary Results and Discussion

5.3.1 Photometric Results and Comparison to Model Predictions

Table 5.2 lists the photometric and model-predicted fluxes for our stacks. Any stack with a measured flux greater than $3 \times$ the background RMS was deemed to be a detection. For all other stacks we are only able to derive the upper limits on the fluxes. We assume these upper limits to be $3 \times BG\ RMS$.

As shown by column 4 in Table 5.2, we have detections in the two highest mass-loss rate bins of the C-rich AGB categories and the highest mass-loss rate bin of the O-rich category. These stacks along with the fitted PSF and residuals are presented in figure 5.1.

The flux of the highest mass-loss rate C-rich AGB bin is in agreement with the GRAMS prediction (see Fig. 5.2 top left). This indicates that GRAMS is able to reproduce the far-IR flux for these high-mass loss sources and there is no excess cold dust component detected. Alternatively, as discussed in the introduction to this chapter, we may not be sensitive to an extended cold-dust component at $100\ \mu\text{m}$ and analysis of the longer wavelength HERITAGE maps are required.

In the two other detected cases we determine a flux which is less than the model fluxes (see Figs. 5.2 top right and bottom). This contradicts studies of AGBs in the Milky Way (e.g., Chapter 2 and references therein) as they are shown to have complex extended envelopes. Further according to Jones et al. (2015b) the individually detected O-AGBs also show an excess in the far-IR (however their RSGs and C-rich AGBs do not).

It is also possible that GRAMS over-predicts the dust masses for these high mass-losing O-rich sources. Decin et al. (2019) recently found that for Milky Way OH/IR stars we are likely over estimating the mass-loss rates due to asymmetries caused by binary companions. Mass trapped by the companion causes it to appear as though there is a high-mass loss super wind phase in the inner region at low resolutions. However high

Figure 5.1 Stacks with successful detections of a point source. Row 1: C-rich AGBs $10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$ bin; Row 2 C-rich AGBs $10^{-8} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-7}$ bin; Row 3: O-rich AGBs $10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$ bin. Left: Stacked image; Right: PSF- and background-subtracted residual image. Row 4: modified PSF. In the Row 1 and 2 we can clearly see the change from subtracting the point source which is reflected in the statistical significance of the detection as presented in 5.2. Similarly while Row 3 does have a detections it is of lower statistical significance and hence the difference between the detection and residual is not as clear.

Table 5.2 Derived photometry and model predicted fluxes of the stacks

Category	\dot{M}_{bin}	Count	$F_{phot}^{[1]}$ (Jy)	F_{GRAMS} (Jy)	\bar{F}_{phot} (Jy)	\bar{F}_{GRAMS} (Jy)
C - AGB	$10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$	10	0.23±0.06	0.25	$(2.3\pm0.6)\times 10^{-2}$	2.5×10^{-2}
	$10^{-8} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-7}$	150	0.51±0.12	0.99	$(3.4\pm0.8)\times 10^{-3}$	6.6×10^{-3}
	$10^{-9} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-8}$	696	< 2.38	0.66	< 3.4×10^{-3}	9.5×10^{-5}
	$10^{-10} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-9}$	3310	< 12.3	0.43	< 3.7×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-4}
	$10^{-11} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-10}$	2803	< 8.34	0.18	< 3.0×10^{-3}	6.4×10^{-5}
	$\dot{M} < 10^{-11}$	42	< 0.23	0.002	< 5.5×10^{-3}	4.8×10^{-5}
	Total		7011	< 23.7	2.52	< 3.4×10^{-3}
O - AGB	$10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$	4	0.07±0.02	0.23	$(1.8\pm0.5)\times 10^{-2}$	5.6×10^{-2}
	$10^{-8} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-7}$	29	< 0.47	0.14	< 1.6×10^{-2}	4.8×10^{-3}
	$10^{-9} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-8}$	280	< 2.26	0.12	< 8.1×10^{-3}	4.3×10^{-4}
	$10^{-10} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-9}$	5706	< 24.4	0.24	< 4.3×10^{-3}	4.2×10^{-5}
	$10^{-11} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-10}$	5890	< 19.2	0.13	< 3.3×10^{-3}	2.2×10^{-5}
	$10^{-12} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-11}$	2807	< 9.12	0.06	< 3.3×10^{-3}	2.1×10^{-5}
	$\dot{M} < 10^{-12}$	5060	< 15.0	0.06	< 3.0×10^{-3}	1.2×10^{-5}
Total		19776	< 70.4	0.98	< 3.6×10^{-3}	5.0×10^{-5}
All AGBs	–	26787	< 94.1	3.50	< 3.5×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-4}
RSGs	–	5869	< 22.0	0.81	< 3.8×10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-4}
All Sources	–	32656	< 116	4.31	< 3.6×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-4}

Column 1: Stacked Category

Column 2: Mass-loss rate bin (\dot{M}_{bin})

Column 3: Number of sources in the stack

Column 4: Photometric flux of the stack (F_{phot})

Column 5: Summed GRAMS flux for the stacked sources (F_{GRAMS})

Column 6: F_{phot} per source

Column 7: F_{GRAMS} per source

^[1] All upper limits are presented as $3\times$ background RMS.

angular resolution reveals that it is actually an asymmetric bulge in the equatorial region caused as a result of the trapped mass. Once the binary interaction is taken into account, hydrodynamic models show a much lower mass-loss rate which at maximum could be $10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. As it is thought that the highest mass-losing O-rich stars – the ones which we have detections in the stacks for – are the LMC equivalents of the Milky Way OH/IR stars, 1-D models (e.g., GRAMS) may in the cases of OH/IR stars with binary interactions, over predict the mass-loss rates. This will predict too much dust and hence higher far-IR emission.

Figure 5.2 Comparison between GRAMS stacked SEDs and the determined flux of the stacks with detections. Grey dots: GRAMS stacked SED; Purple square: Derived flux of stack. Top Left: C-rich AGBs $10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$ bin; Top Right: C-rich AGBs $10^{-8} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-7}$ bin; Bottom: O-rich AGBs $10^{-7} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-6}$ bin.

Therefore while the stacking method has been successful in providing detections we are still exploring the flux calibration and analysis method to determine whether this is an artefact of the method or places new constraints on the parameters used by GRAMS.

In all other bins we have no detections and are only able to derive upper limits. These upper limits are all greater than the GRAMS predicted flux for these stacks. We may only derive upper limits in these lower mass-loss rate bins due to detection and brightness

limitations of the lower mass-loss rate sources. For example, the C-rich mass-loss rate bin $10^{-10} \leq \dot{M} < 10^{-9}$ has a total of 3310 sources contributing to its flux. Each of these are ~ 1000 times fainter than the sources in the highest mass-loss rate bin, assuming the source brightness scales linearly with mass-loss rate (a crude assumption but should be reasonable for high to moderate mass-loss rates). Therefore assuming S/N improves with the \sqrt{N} , we would require 1000^2 times more sources (i.e. in total \sim ten million sources required) to obtain a detection of the same significance as the highest C-rich mass-loss rate bin.

5.3.2 8 vs. 8 – 24 Colour Magnitude Diagram

The 8 vs. 8 – 24 colour magnitude diagram of the complete SAGE catalogue is presented in Fig. 5.3. The evolved-star population included in our stacks is overlaid on top of this. The evolved stars which have been individually detected in the HERITAGE survey and of those contributing to stacks which have a detection are further highlighted in this figure.

As we observe in figure 5.3, the evolved-star population from the Riebel et al. (2012) catalogue has a wide range of mass-loss rates. The typical O-rich AGBs and RSGs have lower mass-loss rates and hence higher 8 μm magnitudes. The 8 μm flux is dominated by the dust emission directly and not the stellar photosphere and hence giving rise to the higher 8 μm magnitudes for O-rich AGBs and RSGs with lower mass-loss rates than C-rich AGBs. The C-rich AGBs on the other hand have an on average lower 8 μm magnitude and therefore are currently in a high-mass-loss state.

The high mass-loss rate sources which contributed to the stacks with detections follow the expected trend and are some of the brightest and reddest sources in the figure. Six of the evolved stars/candidates which were individually detected stand out, having a 8 μm magnitude > 9 . None of these six sources were spectroscopically confirmed by Jones et al. (2015b) and are therefore categorised as "*Possible evolved stars*". They have also been ruled out as young stellar objects or galaxies (Seale et al., 2014). It is therefore likely

Figure 5.3 Spitzer 8 vs. 8 – 24 colour magnitude diagram. The grey cloud of points represent the SAGE catalogue with 24 μm observations. The pink, blue and green clouds represent the C-rich and O-rich AGBs and RSGs from the [Riebel et al. \(2012\)](#) catalogue respectively. The brown squares show the individually detected evolved stars/candidates from the HERITAGE survey ([Jones et al., 2015b](#), [Gruendl et al., 2008](#)) with both 8 μm and 24 μm fluxes available. The crimson circles represent the sources which encompassed the two highest C-rich mass-loss rate bins where we have a detection in the stacked image. The blue circles represent the highest O-rich mass-loss rate bin where we have a detection in the stacked image.

that they are indeed not RSGs or AGB stars but some sort of post-AGB candidate whose nature must be spectroscopically confirmed in the future.

5.4 Summary and Future Work

We have presented a proof-of-concept study exploring the far-IR excess and cold dust component associated with it in a large sample of evolved stars in the LMC. To overcome

confusion in the LMC field we employ a technique of stacking cutouts of a large number of sources centred which enhances the source signal allowing us to study them in a statistical manner.

In this preliminary study, we successfully detect a point source in three of the highest mass-loss rate bins in our C- and O-rich categories. For all other stacked categories we are only able to determine an upper limit. Both the detections and upper limits are valuable results as we can use both sets to constrain the amount of cold dust present as the study progresses. This preliminary study therefore demonstrates that the stacking method can indeed be successfully applied to fields with strong confusion such the LMC, albeit with caveats which require further investigation.

As we note in our methodology section we do not carry out sub-pixel realignment and do not take into account the effects of PSF rotation. However, in the future these effects must be considered for a more accurate understanding.

While sub-pixel realignment is going to have a limited effect on non-detections where the no flux is detected at the required significance level, it means we are smearing out hence disregarding $\sim 10\%$ of the total flux, which in the future needs to be taken into account. To do so we can shift the HERITAGE observation frame to be centred exactly on the Spitzer coordinate of the source for each cutout. This can be carried out through a process of oversampling and interpolation, with for example the `MultiDrizzle` package (Gonzaga & et al., 2012). By doing so we will later test the significance of the smearing out effect on our stacks. We may also be able to improve the detection rate of our sources by carrying out this realignment as a result of the 10% improvement in flux localisation.

In future in order to better understand and calculate the effects of the telescope rotation angle differences between the PSF and the HERITAGE maps we must de-rotate the observation to the angle of the PSF observation using an interpolation routine. While doing so we must also take care to note that all interpolation routines introduce a small amount of uncertainty due to noise, and this must be taken into account when measuring the fluxes following de-rotation.

Once we have perfected this method to apply to the confused LMC field at $100\ \mu\text{m}$, we will explore its application to all the other wavelength HERITAGE maps. HERITAGE observations of the LMC were also carried out at $160\ \mu\text{m}$, $250\ \mu\text{m}$, $350\ \mu\text{m}$ and $500\ \mu\text{m}$. These longer wavelengths may be more effective for detecting the excess cold dust component, which may not have been successfully detectable at the shortest $100\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength. However the lower resolution of the longer wavelength will result in higher confusion making it more difficult to separate the point sources from the large extended structure. We will explore additional methods which will take these resolution limitations into account and minimise large-scale background structure when analysing all the HERITAGE maps in the future.

Once we have successfully obtained far-IR – sub-mm SED for the stacks at the full HERITAGE wavelength range we will use them to derive several key results: 1) Similar to the preliminary study we will compare the stacked SEDs with the GRAMS model predicted SED at the same wavelength range in order to explore the presence of a far-IR excess. By doing so we will be able to constrain the accuracy and limitations of GRAMS when predicting fluxes at long wavelengths; 2) By fitting these SEDs with models assuming a range of temperatures and dust masses we will constrain the total cold dust component of each stack hence determining amount on average per source of the stack; 3) The total dust masses derived will be compared to total dust masses of the LMC in order to better constrain the percentage of dust contributed by evolved stars to the LMC. Following the successful completion of analysis of the LMC with the methods perfected, we aim to extend the study to the SMC as well in order to encompass the entire Magellanic system in the future of this project.

As described throughout this thesis it is key to take into account the historic dust mass loss in order to accurately determine the dust injection to galactic ISM. Simply analysing Milky Way sources is insufficient as we must explore the role of varying environments (e.g., changes in metallicity) and therefore we must study beyond the Milky Way to obtain a large scale view of this effect over the lifetime of the universe. The LMC and SMC are an ideal laboratory for such studies, due to its proximity and difference in nature when

compared to the Milk Way. Therefore we can explore the life cycle of dust and how it changes with galaxy environments in a more broad sense than only in the Milky Way. The HERITAGE data is likely going to be the only set of observations which will allow us to do so in a statistically significant manner (since it has mapped the entirety of the LMC and SMC) for the foreseeable future; no new missions will have either the field of view or wavelength range required to efficiently map the Magellanic clouds and study the historic mass loss from evolved stars.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this thesis we have analysed the far-IR and sub-mm dust emission, i.e. thermal dust emission, of evolved stars in both the Milky Way and the Large Magellanic Cloud to study their historic mass loss. We primarily employ imaging from Herschel/PACS 70 μm , 100 μm and 160 μm in the far-IR. The sub-mm observations are obtained from JCMT/SCUBA-2 at 450 μm and 850 μm .

From our analysis of evolved stars in the Milky Way we find that their circumstellar envelopes are significantly extended, particularly at the far-IR wavelengths, and that $\sim 60\%$ of the total far-IR and sub-mm flux originates from the extended envelope. From these observations we were able to explore mass-loss histories up to $\sim 9000 \pm 1100$ years. From the temperature, spectral index of dust emissivity and dust mass column density radial profiles we found that nearly all sources showed historic mass-loss variations.

Deeper analysis of the detached shell source U Ant showed the complexity of structure in circumstellar envelopes and the need for high resolution observations to better constrain the parameters of such circumstellar envelopes. Comparing these results to model predictions determined using a constant mass-loss rate we find the two contradict one another. With these studies we establish the need to systematically analyse the historic mass-loss

from Milky Way evolved stars and take its variations into account when measuring total dust production rates from these sources.

Studying the sub-mm variability of two of the most well-known AGB stars in the Milky Way, IRC+10216 and *o* Ceti, we find the measured periods are comparable to published periods derived using optical – far-IR data. However the periods we derive have large confidence intervals due to the high noise levels and uneven sampling in the observations, calling for continuous systematic monitoring to obtain improved estimates. Interestingly, from our study we find that IRC+10216 has an optical–sub-mm phase lag of ~ 540 days. We find that this phase lag is similar to that found in radio wavelengths. Using model predictions we determine that the sub-mm emission and hence the phase lag likely arises due contributions from the dust formation/destruction cycle as well as a yet unknown dominant mechanism which requires further analysis to discern. Given the similarities between the sub-mm and radio phase lags it is likely that there is a single physical mechanism which gives rise to both.

In a proof-of-concept analysis, we stack cutouts of evolved stars from the Herschel HERITAGE survey at $100\ \mu\text{m}$ to explore the possibility of a far-IR excess as a result of a previously undetected cold dust component in these sources. We obtain successful detections in the stacks of three of the highest mass-loss rate bins. Matters are still somewhat complicated due to detection limitations and strong emission from large scale background structure, giving rise to only upper limits in all other stacks. However, these non-detections also provide constraints on the total cold dust masses which maybe present and both these preliminary sets of detections and upper limits show the merits of the stacking method when applied to confused fields such as the LMC. Further investigation and development of the method, which is relatively new to this type of confused field, is required. A fully-developed stacking method can be applied to all the available HERITAGE maps allowing us to analyse the previously undetected evolved star population of the LMC and the SMC from far-IR – sub-mm and determine average cold dust masses present.

This thesis therefore further exposes the importance of studying thermal dust emission

from the cold outer envelopes surrounding evolved stars. Accounting for the historic mass loss can increase total dust mass estimates by a factor of 5, emphasising the need to take into these variations. Future studies must therefore consider these effects in a more systematic and detailed manner.

The ongoing Nearby Evolved Star Survey (NESS; *Scicluna et al., in prep*) aims to study the historic mass-loss from evolved stars in the Solar neighbourhood in a systematic manner which has previously not been attempted. NESS will observe and study the gas and dust emission from a volume-limited sample of ~ 500 Galactic evolved stars. Chapter 2 was a pilot study for this survey and Chapter 3 presents early science from NESS. NESS will build on these by expanding the sample by a factor of nearly 20, obtaining statistically-significant results for parameters such as dust-production rates, mass-loss variations and variation times scales to name a few. This will be achieved using observations from telescopes around the globe including JCMT, ALMA, APEX and Nobeyama 45m to name a few allowing for both high and low resolution observations exploring both small-and large-scale structures in circumstellar envelopes.

Future ground-based telescopes such as ASKAP and the SKA will provide unprecedented sensitivity and spatial and spectral resolution to the neutral Hydrogen, a new tracer, envelopes of evolved stars probing historic time scales approximately an order of magnitude longer. Extinction mapping from for example the Gaia mission will provide an alternative view of the complexities of the circumstellar envelopes of evolved stars. Further, SPICA and OST missions can trace the circumstellar envelopes in far-IR and sub-mm with a very high sensitivity over a large wavelength range, improving detections beyond the Milky Way significantly.

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Appendix A

Fitting radial SEDs with MCMC

We used the convenient and fast python package *emcee* (Foreman-Mackey et al., 2013) which employs affine-invariant Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms to carry out Bayesian inference on our observed data set and the resulting SEDs to derive the most probable T , Σ and β at each radial point. These results can be plotted as a function of radius to derive the T , Σ and β radial profiles.

The MCMC algorithms are optimised to carry out statistical inferences such as Bayesian inference on large data sets with multiple free parameters. They utilise Markov chains to converge via random walks towards a target distribution from which random samples are generated. In our case we assumed the T , Σ and β to be free parameters. The first step of this process was to generate synthetic photometry which will later be used by the model to compare to our observed data. The synthetic photometry were generated using the surface brightness equation 2.2 and then convolving it with filter response curves for each instrument at each of the four wavelengths, which is then normalised. The SCUBA-2 filter response curves were downloaded from the EAO JCMT SCUBA-2 filters page¹. The PACS filter response curves were downloaded from the SVO Filter Profile Service² (Rodrigo et al., 2012).

¹<http://www.eaobservatory.org/jcmt/instrumentation/continuum/scuba-2/filters/>

²<http://svo2.cab.inta-csic.es/svo/theory/fps/index.php?mode=browse&gname=Herschel&gname2=Pacs>

At each step, the code will generate a new set of possible initial T , Σ and β values which will be read into the synthetic photometry equation in order to generate the synthetic photometry. These initial values for the free parameter values are generated in the next step of the code where the prior is generated.

In order to carry out the MCMC algorithm, we need to define the prior, likelihood and posterior as required by Bayesian statistics (Hogg et al., 2010). The prior allows the inclusion of any previous knowledge we know about our free parameters. This will be an initial estimation of the free parameters randomly determined by MCMC given some input ranges provided by us. The Σ prior was set to be between 10^{-10} g cm $^{-2}$ to 10^{10} g cm $^{-2}$ in log scale to include a good density range.

In the case of the T prior having a simple uniform temperature range (flat prior) gave rise to a temperature profile with no trend and large uncertainties. Some of this uncertainty also bled out in to the final density values. Therefore we set the temperature prior to be a normal distribution. The mean temperature is given by

$$T_{\text{mean}} = T_{\text{inner}} \times \sqrt{\frac{r_{\text{inner}}}{r_{\text{outer}}}} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where, the inner temperature (T_{inner}) of the equation was set to 1300 K. We use the publicly available GRAMS models (Sargent et al., 2011, Srinivasan et al., 2011) to obtain an estimate for the typical range of values for (T_{inner}) (1300 ± 40 K). The inner radius (r_{inner}) was set to $0.03''$ and r_{outer} is the outer most radial point which is being analysed. The standard deviation defining the normal distribution was set to 40 K.

The T bounds were set to be in the range 2.7 K – 300 K. The lower limit is set according to the cosmic microwave background (CMB) which has a thermal black-body spectrum at (2.72548 ± 0.00057) K (Fixsen, 2009). The upper limit is an arbitrary temperature reasonably expected for AGB stellar dust shells and is high enough to guarantee that we do not resolve the region where the dust actually attains this value in any of our observations.

When defining a β prior we ran into many challenges. As many stellar dust properties such as temperature, grain size and composition are related to β and therefore an accurate value of β is required in order to obtain our other two free parameters, T and Σ , we needed a prior which is derived from a well sampled β data set. Simply setting upper and lower limits did produce a β profile which was artificially forced to be constrained within the given limits. Further as β is not yet well understood for AGB circumstellar environments at these wavelengths it was difficult to determine simple meaningful flat prior. This also meant we could not use a fixed β value. Instead, we opted to use a realistic distribution of β values measured for an interstellar medium environment, and identified the *Herschel* maps of M31 to be useful for this purpose (Smith et al. 2012).

The dust and gas properties of the Andromeda Galaxy (M 31) were studied at 100, 160, 250, 350 and 500 μm *Herschel*/PACS and SPIRE observations by Smith et al. (2012). By fitting a single temperature modified black body model to the SED (which also included Spitzer 70 μm (data) at each map pixel this study obtained the dust mass, temperature and β results at each pixel. This then lead to a galactic β map which we used as a well sampled and inclusive data set from which to determine our prior. By carrying out kernel density estimation on the β sample of M31, as shown in Fig. A.1 we produced the optimal β probability density function which can be used as our prior. A cosine kernel was used for this purpose and the bandwidth h was set according to Silverman’s rule (Silverman, 1986).

We define a likelihood function which is the probability we *see* our observed data is the same as the synthetic data produced by the generative model (i.e., the probability of the data set given the model parameters). The likelihood discerns the probability that the prior generated T , Σ and β probabilities chosen by emcee for the current step will produce fluxes that match those observed once they’re fed in to the generative model. Since we have data points with non-detections, especially limited by the SCUBA-2 450 observations which have no detectable extensions at 3σ levels beyond $\sim 30''$ (except for the deep IRC+10216 and *o* Cet maps). Therefore we defined a likelihood functions able to handle two different types of data. The first is a Gaussian function for detections,

Figure A.1 Normalised Histogram of the β map of M 31 overlaid with its probability density function estimated using cosine kernel density estimation.

data with a well defined value ($\text{flux} \geq 3\sigma$) with uncertainties. The second is a cumulative distribution function for non-detections, data with only an upper limit ($\text{flux} \leq 3\sigma$).

Finally a posterior was defined which will take the product of the prior and likelihood to produce the probability of the model given the observed data. MCMC combines the prior, likelihood and posteriors along with the observed data and run the sampler which will carry out Bayesian inference. We define $T = 28 \text{ K}$, $\Sigma = 1 \text{ g cm}^{-2}$, and β equal to 1 plus a small random perturbation, as the initial position for the walkers required by MCMC algorithms. From this position, the walkers explore parameter space to converge on the best value for each parameter. We set the number of walkers to 100 and the number of steps with which to explore the parameter space to 10000.

An *emcee* run generates a set of samples from the posterior for the model. Using the results for each of the three free parameters, we derived the median, 16th and 84th percentile values at each radial point. The median is used to approximate the centre of the distribution of samples. The 16th and 84th percentiles are its 1σ uncertainties. These final values were then used to produce the radially dependent T , Σ , and β profiles for all our sources.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figures for Chapter [2](#)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure B.1 Observational and modelling results for AGB star CIT 6. (a): surface-brightness profiles (blue lines; grey lines correspond to the PSF profile) and the PSF reduced residual profiles (orange lines) as a function of projected radius ($''$) and physical size (pc) for PACS $70\mu\text{m}$ and $160\mu\text{m}$ and SCUBA-2 $450\mu\text{m}$ and $850\mu\text{m}$. The observed peak location is a result of the shape of the PSF being subtracted; (b): Profiles of the temperature (red lines), surface density (purple lines), and emissivity spectral index (green lines) as a function of projected radius and time. The surface density for a uniform mass-loss rate is also shown (yellow dashed lines); (c): Reduced SCUBA-2 $850\mu\text{m}$ observation of source with the FWHM of the PSF (grey circle) and the maximum extension at 3σ brightness level (white circle).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure B.2 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star EP Aqr

Figure B.3 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star IK Tau

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure B.4 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star IRC+10011

(b)

(c)

Figure B.5 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star LP And

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure B.6 As Fig. B.1 for RSG star NML Cyg

Figure B.7 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star *o* Ceti

(b)

(c)

Figure B.8 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star R Cas

(b)

(c)

Figure B.9 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star R Leo

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure B.10 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star RX Boo

Figure B.11 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star TX Cam

(b)

(c)

Figure B.12 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star W Aql

(b)

(c)

Figure B.13 As Fig. B.1 for AGB star W Hya

Appendix C

Published Shell Radii and Schematic Diagram of U Ant

Table C.1 Published Shell Radii of U Ant.

Publication	Mean Shell Radius (")	Shell Thickness (")	Observation and Shell Type
Olofsson et al. (1996)	41	13	SEST CO (1-0), (2-1), (3-2) - gas
Izumiura et al. (1997)	46 180	– –	Far-IR IRAS - dust "
González Delgado et al. (2001) and González Delgado et al. (2003)	25 37 43 46	3 6 3 10	Optical scattered light - dust " " "
Maercker et al. (2010)	43 50 41	2 7 2.6	Optical scattered light - dust " APEX CO (3-2) - gas
Kerschbaum et al. (2010) PACS	40	12	far-IR Herschel/PACS - dust
Cox et al. (2012)	42	–	Far-IR Herschel/PACS - dust
Kerschbaum et al. (2017)	42.5	5	ALMA CO (1-0) and (2-1) - gas
3σ surface brightness extent derived in this paper	56	–	Sub-mm SCUBA-2 850 μm - dust

Figure C.1 Schematic diagram of the reported observations of U Ant showing mean Dust/Gas shell positions and FWHMs, arranged chronologically. A summary of the observations are presented in Tab. C.1. The top most grey dashed lines represent multiple SCUBA-2 850 μm beam FWHMs (13").

Appendix D

CO 3-2 subtraction

In order to carry out $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ subtraction we use JCMT/HARP $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ heterodyne spectral observations obtained from 2017/01/03 to 2017/01/13, once again as part of the NESS survey. These maps use a 5×5 jiggle pattern to produce a $2' \times 2'$ map, oversampled with $4.8''$ pixels. The HARP observations were reduced using standard JCMT Heterodyne REDUCE_SCIENCE_NARROWLINE pipeline (Jenness & Economou, 2015) and binned to 4 km/s resolution. See figure D.1. Using instructions provided by Parsons et al. (2018) (and in *SCUBA-2 Data Reduction – Tutorial 5* webpage¹) we generated the $^{12}\text{CO}(3-2)$ subtracted SCUBA-2 850 μm observation.

As seen in Fig D.1, HARP has two dead receptors meaning that no data was recorded for this section of the shell. Comparing the HARP observation to the ALMA CO observations by Kerschbaum et al. (2017) only the very edge of a small section of the shell falls within this missing pixel region and therefore has little effect on the CO flux (~ 15 pixels out of 154 pixels within the shell). In addition, the chop throw was set to $60''$, smaller than the diameter of the shell, resulting in some self-subtraction. Between these two effects we estimate that approximately 30% of the CO flux is missing and therefore incorporate additional uncertainty to account for this.

¹<https://www.eaobservatory.org/jcmt/science/reductionanalysis-tutorials/scuba-2-dr-tutorial-5/>

Figure D.1 Integrated ^{12}CO (3-2) HARP observation of U Ant used to carry out CO subtraction on the SCUBA-2 $850\ \mu\text{m}$ observation. Filled black circle in the bottom left corner: HARP beam with FWHM of $14''$. The figure is integrated over the velocity range of $[-26, 82]\ \text{km s}^{-1}$

Appendix E

Observed global SED fluxes of U Ant

Table E.1 Fluxes used to derive the wavelength dependent SED of U Ant.

Instrument/Survey	Wavelength (μm)	Flux (Jy)	Reference
Gaia	0.505	16.8 ± 0.3	Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018)
	0.623	73.1 ± 0.3	
	0.772	154 ± 2	
2MASS	1.24	591 ± 151	Skrutskie et al. (2006)
	1.66	1190 ± 370	
	2.16	1270 ± 490	
COBE/DIRBE	1.25	614 ± 36	Smith et al. (2004)
	2.22	1040 ± 30	
	3.52	725 ± 25	
	4.89	237 ± 10	
WISE	11.6	111 ± 27	Cutri & et al. (2012)
	22.1	35.8 ± 0.3	
AKARI/IRC	8.61	264 ± 15	Ishihara et al. (2010) , Doi et al. (2015)
	18.4	61.5 ± 2.3	
AKARI/FIS	65	25.8 ± 5.3	Arimatsu et al. (2011)
	90	20.1 ± 4.2	
	140	8.4 ± 3.1	
IRAS/ISSA	11.6	168 ± 7	Neugebauer et al. (1984) , Beichman et al. (1988)
	23.9	44.8 ± 1.8	
	61.8	27.1 ± 2.7	
	102	21.1 ± 2.3	
Herschel/PACS	70	23.06 ± 0.03	Observations from Groenewegen et al. (2011) - fluxes derived via aperture photometry in this paper
	160	5.96 ± 0.02	
Herschel/SPIRE	250	1.81 ± 0.26	Observations from Groenewegen et al. (2011) - fluxes derived via aperture photometry in this paper
	350	0.716 ± 0.172	
	500	0.243 ± 0.104	
JCMT/SCUBA-2	450	0.435 ± 0.070	This paper
	850	0.199 ± 0.034	

Appendix F

SCUBA observations from 1997

U Ant was observed for project M96BI17 on 1997/10/17 and 1997/10/20 for a total of 2.1 hours. The data were re-processed using the SURF package, using the standard calibration factor for the 850N filter at the largest available aperture size of 60'' [Jenness et al. \(2002\)](#). The reduction process included correction for opacity using skydips taken around the observations (yielding $\tau(850\mu\text{m})$ of 0.28-0.41 at zenith); cleaning with a 5-sigma clip, despiking, sky removal and bolometer weighting; and map reconstruction with median-regridding in 3 arcsec pixels, matching the native sampling of jiggle observations. The map was smoothed with a 9'' Gaussian to an effective resolution of approximately 17'' FWHM. There is no information in the map on scales larger than the 2' chop throw, so the true zero level is poorly established. The surface-brightness profile is around an estimated overall flux-centroid of 10:35:13.0, -39:33:52 (J2000), south of the expected position of the star (attributed to a poor pointing model at far-south declinations). The noise is estimated from the dispersion among pixels in each annulus, converted to a standard error based on the number of independent beams within the annulus.

(a)

(b)

Figure F.1 (a): SCUBA 850 μm observation of U Ant from 1997 (1 pix = 3"). The off-centred red dot indicates the position of the star. It is off center due to pointing accuracy problems in SCUBA; (b): Surface-brightness profile of the SCUBA observation.

Appendix G

Supplementary Figures for Chapter [4](#)

Figure G.1 Derived Periodograms and Phase folded light curves for IRC+10216 850 μm

Figure G.2 Derived Periodograms and Phase folded light curves for IRC+10216 450 μm

Figure G.3 Derived Periodograms and Phase folded light curves for *o* Ceti 850 μm

Figure G.4 Derived Periodograms and Phase folded light curves for *o* Ceti 450 μm